

**The Impact of Customer Relationship Management on Customer
Loyalty and Customer Retention within UK-based SMEs in the Beauty
Industry:
A Case Study of Panache Beauty**

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Executive Summary

Customer loyalty is an important aspect of the business, especially when it comes to the service sector. Loyal customers reflect the organisation's performance, and it helps the company gain a competitive advantage over rival brands. Time and again, it is proved that the retention of clients is a much more effective and cheaper method for business growth rather than gaining a new customer. With this awareness, companies are trying hard to take measures to retain their customers and maintain customer loyalty. Customer relationship management is the key to this, and the organisation needs to gain the trust and commitment of customers to retain them. The beauty industry is one of the most competitive industries in the service sector.

With so many competitors existing in the market and new ones appearing on a daily basis, organisations need to take measures to ensure customer retention. In the case of beauty salons, customers are the key assets. Only those organisations that identify and value this fact will be able to survive the high competition and rivalry existing in the market. This research explains the importance of customer relationship management, customer loyalty and customer retention that helps organisations in the service sector by analysing the customer relationship management of Panache Beauty, an SME in the UK that provides skin and facial treatments.

The research was conducted based on available literature in the field of customer relationship management, customer loyalty and retention in the beauty parlour industry. Other than depending on existing literature, a survey and a few interviews were conducted to understand the market and attitude of Panache Beauty customers. Surveys and interviews were also useful in studying the expectations of customers during their visit to the parlour. Various factors affecting customer relationship was also revealed during the survey and interviews. The results are analysed using statistical analysis methods available under SPSS and presented and compared under various subsections.

On analysing the survey results, it became clear that one of the most effective methods to overcome the risk posed by larger organisations to SME's in the beauty sector is to have loyal customers. It is wiser to retain existing customers than find new ones as it is cheaper than the latter method. The study also revealed that beauty parlours are considered a facility to get beauty-related treatments and as a place of relaxation. Thus, it was found that the overall environment also plays a crucial role in ensuring customer retention. The most important factor that influences customer satisfaction is staff behaviour. From the study, it became clear that the organisations that are able to ensure skilled and experienced staff, who are also good at communicating with the customer, are more likely to thrive in the business. Various other

aspects were also found important in customer satisfaction and retention in the beauty industry. The research also suggests various methods that can be adopted by Panache Beauty in order to ensure customer satisfaction and thereby customer retention as well as loyalty and thus overcome the tough competition posed by rival brands.

Dedication

I want to thank my family, my wife especially, and my academic lead supervisor with these I won't be able to finish this thesis; special thanks to my lead supervisor because, if he didn't believe I won't be able to complete this thesis, and all University staff member especially admin, library staff, my other supervisor, accessor, and as well getting this whole project in the right format.

I would like to dedicate this research to all the people who have contributed in some way to my success (mostly emotional and moral support received from the family and friends during tough times).

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	ii
Dedication	iv
Acknowledgement	v
Table of Contents	vi
List of Tables.....	ix
List of Figures	xi
1 Chapter One: Introduction	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Background Information	1
Panache Beauty: Company Profile	2
1.3 Problem Statement	3
1.4 Aims and Objective	5
1.4.1 Aim.....	5
1.4.2 Objectives.....	5
1.5 Research Questions	5
1.6 Significance of the Study	5
1.7 Methodology followed	6
2 Chapter Two: Literature Review	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Theoretical Background	10
2.3 Customer Relationship Management	12
2.4 Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention	17
2.4.1 Customer Loyalty.....	17
2.4.2 Consumer Retention.....	24
2.4.3 The function of CRM in Customer Loyalty and Retention	32
2.4.4 Empirical Studies on the Impact of CRM on Customer Loyalty and Retention.....	34
2.5 Consumer Culture.....	37
2.6 Consumption Styles.....	41
2.6.1 Conspicuous consumption	42
2.6.2 Symbolic consumption.....	43
2.6.3 Addictive consumption	43
2.6.4 Compulsive consumption.....	43
2.6.5 Shared consumption.....	44
2.6.6 Experiential consumption	44

2.7	Conclusion.....	48
3	Chapter Three: Research Methodology	50
3.1	Introduction	50
3.2	Research Philosophy – Positivism	51
3.3	Research Design- Descriptive	53
3.4	Type of Research: Mixed Methods	58
3.5	Sampling Technique and Sample Size	61
3.6	Data Collection.....	65
3.6.1	Primary data Collection: Questionnaire and Interview	67
3.6.2	Secondary data collection	69
3.6.3	Material	71
3.7	Procedure.....	73
3.8	Hypothesis	75
3.9	Practical Issues	75
3.10	Ethical Concerns	76
4	Chapter Four: Data Analysis	78
4.1	Introduction	78
4.2	Demographics and General Information of Study Participants.....	78
4.3	Customer Relationship Management of Panache Beauty (Independent Variable).....	81
4.4	Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention (Dependent Variable).....	95
4.5	Correlation of Each Independent Variable with Dependent Variable	98
4.6	ANOVA for Statistical Significance of the Relation between Study Variables.....	110
5	Chapter Five: Discussion on Findings	118
5.1	Introduction	118
5.2	Demographics.....	118
5.3	Gender	118
5.4	Age	118
5.5	Employment status	119
5.6	Proximity.....	119
5.7	Duration.....	119
5.8	Frequency	120
5.9	Independent variables.....	120
5.10	Customer relationship.....	120
5.11	Experience of staff.....	121
5.12	Analysing capacity.....	121
5.13	Service quality	122

5.14	Suitability.....	122
5.15	Environment	123
5.16	Pricing.....	124
5.17	Offers	124
5.18	Relationship with regular customers	125
5.19	Dependent variables.....	126
5.20	Revisit	126
5.21	Preference over other parlours	126
5.22	Reference	126
5.23	Correlation between dependent and independent variables.....	127
5.24	Frequency of visit and distance from Salon	127
5.25	Friendliness of staff and preference over other brands.....	127
5.26	Experience and understanding of staff.....	127
5.27	Professionalism.....	128
5.28	Quality and suitability of service	128
5.29	Environment and pricing	128
6	Chapter Six: Conclusion	130
7	Chapter Seven: Recommendations	138
7.1	Demographics.....	138
7.2	Independent factors	139
	References	149
	Appendices.....	172
	Appendix A: Questionnaire.....	172
	Appendix B – Interview Questions	175
	Appendix C- Gantt Chart	175
	Appendix D- Ethics Approval confirmation	178
	Appendix E- Participant Invitation	179
	Appendix F- Participant Consent form	180
	Appendix G- Certificate of Participation in International conference on Business and science	182

List of Tables

Table 2: Sample population chosen for the research	63
Table 03:Gender.....	79
Table 04:Age Groups	79
Table 05:Status of Employment.....	80
Table 06:How far is Panache Beauty from your residence?	80
Table 07:How long have you been a customer of Panache Beauty?	81
Table 08:How frequently you visit Panache Beauty?	81
Table 09:The Staff at Panache Is Very Sincere and Friendly	82
Table 010:The Staff at Panache Is Experienced in Their Jobs and Understand My Needs and Preferences Very Well.....	84
Table 011:The Staff at Panache First Assesses My Skin Before Applying or Using any Product to Avoid Negative Reaction	85
Table 12:The Quality of Services Provided at Panache Beauty is Excellent.....	87
Table 13:Services Provided at Panache Suits My Skin Very Well.....	88
Table 14:The Overall Environment and Atmosphere of Panache is Very Good and Relaxing.....	90
Table 15:The Services of Panache Beauty Are Rightly Priced According to The Quality	91
Table 16:Panache Offers Good Packages and Discount Offers.....	93
Table 17:Panache Offers also Offers Very Good and Different Packages, and Discount Offers to Its Regular Customers	94
Table 18:How Likely You Are Expected to Visit Panache Beauty Again?	96
Table 19:How Likely You Are Expected to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Other Salons?	97
Table 20:How Likely You Are Expected to Refer Panache Beauty to Others?	98
Table 21:Correlation of Distance from Residence and Frequency of Visiting the Saloon.....	99
Table 22:Correlation of Staff Sincerity and Friendliness with Customer Loyalty and Retention.....	100
Table 23:Correlation of Staff Experience and Understanding to Customers' Needs with Customer Loyalty and Retention.....	102
Table 24:Correlation of Staff Professionalism with Customer Loyalty and Retention	103
Table 25:Correlation of Quality of Services Provided with Customer Loyalty and Retention of Suitability	104
Table 26:Correlation of Services Provided for Customers' Skin with Customer Loyalty and Retention	105

Table 27:Correlation of Overall Environment and Atmosphere with Customer Loyalty and Retention	106
Table 28:Correlation of Service Pricing with Customer Loyalty and Retention.....	107
Table 29:Correlations of Provision of Good Packages and Discount Offers with Customer Loyalty and Retention	108
Table 30:Correlations of Provision of Special Packages and Discount Offers for Regular Customers with Customer Loyalty and Retention	109
Table 31:ANOVA of Staff Sincerity and Friendliness with Customer Loyalty and Retention.....	111
Table 32:ANOVA of Staff Experience and Understanding to Customers' Needs	112
Table 33:ANOVA of Staff Professionalism	112
Table 34:ANOVA of Quality of Services Provided	113
Table 35:ANOVA of Suitability of Services Provided for Customers' Skin	114
Table 36:ANOVA of Overall Environment and Atmosphere	115
Table 37:ANOVA of Service Pricing	115
Table 38:ANOVA of Provision of Good Packages and Discount Offers with Customer Loyalty and Retention	116
Table 39:ANOVA of Special Packages and Discount Offers for Regular Customers	117

List of Figures

Figure 1: Factors ensuring customer retention.....	49
Figure 2: Staff at Panache Is Very Sincere and Friendly.....	83
Figure 3: Staff at Panache Is Experienced	84
Figure 4: Staff at Panache has expert knowledge	86
Figure 5: Quality of Service is Excellent.....	87
Figure 6: Services Provided at Panache Suits My Skin.....	89
Figure 7: Overall Environment and Atmosphere of Panache is Very Good and Relaxing	90
Figure 8: Services Are Rightly Priced	92
Figure 9: Offers Good Packages and Discount Offers.....	93
Figure 10: Panache Offers Discount to Its Regular Customers	95
Figure 11: How Likely You Are Expected to Visit Panache Beauty Again.....	96
Figure 12: How Likely You Are Expected to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Other Salons.....	97
Figure 13: How Likely You Are Expected to Refer Panache Beauty to Others.....	98
Figure 14:Customer retention methods.....	141
Figure 15: Relationship management methods	146
Figure 16: Strategy to be adopted	147

1 Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The swift changes taking place in society today inevitably has an impact on how the business environment functions. It is probably not an exaggeration to state that virtually all the businesses that exist today are searching for avenues to enhance customer loyalty and retention. Customer loyalty reflects organisational performance, as it helps an organisation gain a competitive advantage over rivals, as far as consumer satisfaction is concerned (Liang & Wang, 2014). In today's world, customer loyalty is typically ascertained by organisations as pacesetters of monopoly (Liang & Wang, 2014).

Those organisations that value customer loyalty goes the extra mile in meeting customer needs and wants and at the client's convenience. Loyal customers purchase beyond the recognition of a trusted brand and a known price tag (Shahin & Teymuri, 2008). Hence addressing the issue of customer retention is as important as winning consumer loyalty. Many firms meet head-on because retaining a client is much cheaper than gaining a new one.

In this sense, companies are trying their level best to maintain customer loyalty as much as possible instead of looking for new ones, which is quite demanding as far as the business organisation is concerned. Against this backdrop, organisations have realised the significance of the role played by customer relationship management, in tackling both customer loyalty and retention. Managing customer relationship is about building a possible and viable liaison between an organisation and its customers, with the overall aim of creating loyal customers. To establish a stable relationship with consumers, it is important that there is a detailed understanding with regards to commitment and trust, as far as customer loyalty and retention are concerned. This then introduces customer relationship management, the area which this research focuses on.

1.2 Background Information

This research study focuses on three key variables, namely: customer relationship management, customer loyalty, and customer retention. It is important that these variables are understood in detail so that this work can be developed further, and an appropriate academic contribution can be made.

The creation of customer loyalty is more than a business concept in the current world since it is a critical success factor for any industry. To this end, organisations in the current era are continually seeking to identify and manage effective loyalty-building methods (Liang & Wang, 2014). CRM is a concept geared towards managing the interactions between an organisation and customers as been overemphasised through the five CRM definition perspectives and the potential sales prospects available; as organisations

go the extra mile in assuring customer satisfaction, CRM elements are considered. CRM is a complex process involving the use of technology to automate, synchronise, and organise business operations (Gutjahr, 2011). The objective of CRM is to enhance income, profitability, and customer satisfaction. In attaining CRM, various organisations put into use a set of technologies and tools and procedures in supporting the organisational-customer relationships to promote sales.

Thus, CRM is a strategic business issue and process, as opposed to a technical system. CRM is indeed a tool for managing associations between business organisations and their customers. Therefore, the concept of CRM focuses on how and where firms and customers externally or internally exchange information (Abdullatif et al., 2010). To this end, CRM's effectiveness is determined by the degree to which companies can associate with customers, both internally and externally, responsively and flexibly. With the aftermath of the 2007/2008 global financial crisis still fresh in companies' dealings, it is paramount that business organisations become sensitive and monitor the feelings and reactions of customers towards goods and services. However, this is only possible if they focus on CRM as a means of stabilising business operations within a fluctuating global market (Aihie & Bennani, 2012). This strategy is undertaken to win customer loyalty and retention.

According to Abdullatif et al. (2010), customer satisfaction is not sufficient. Customer satisfaction should have a direct impact on customer loyalty and retention. Beltman (2013) empathises the fact that there is increasing recognition that, customer satisfaction is only possible when there is consumer loyalty. This notwithstanding, customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention are interrelated factors. A customer who is satisfied by an organisational product or service, become loyal to an organisation by default, as their personal tastes and preferences are met (Beltman, 2013). Consequently, a loyal customer would be retained in an organisation, as the competitor's product/service is not preferable. As such, CRM leads to customer satisfaction, which has a triple-down effect on consumer loyalty and retention.

Panache Beauty: Company Profile

Panache Beauty is a small organisation in the U.K. that deals with skin and facial treatments, as well as focusing on nail treatments. Panache operates under various business segments/groups: facials, manicure and pedicure, waxing, threading, tinting, and tanning. To begin with, facial treatment, also known as microdermabrasion, is meant to make a face look brighter, smoother, and softer. In general, microdermabrasion treatment is primarily used to improve the skin's quality and texture (Panache Beauty, 2015). Such a treatment is fantastic in dealing with dull, rough, or dry skin and treating acne and eradicating superficial pigmentation. About hands and feet, the organisation is known for its excellent pedicure and manicure. Manicure is the treatment for nails and hands, and it is purposely done to check

on the health status of nails and hands: restyling and polishing the nails into the required shape and nourishing the back of the hand and feet (Panache Beauty, 2015).

Threading is done to perfect the eyebrows. Skilled threading personnel uses cotton and rolls it over the skin in a unique manner to “gently lift the entire hair from the follicle” (Panache Beauty, 2015). Threading makes the skin to be smooth. Waxing is also done to ensure smooth skin. The method or process uses various waxing forms such as warm and hot wax (Lyon) to remove hair from the skin leading to smooth skin (Panache Beauty, 2015). The tinting of the eyebrows is done to sharpen the eyelashes. The treatment also lengthens or extends the lashes, leaving the eyelashes natural and weightless (Panache Beauty, 2015). Tanning is carried out to address the effects of excessive sun exposure on the skin by using spray tans to make a stronger skin for the white individuals with little or no tanning (Panache Beauty, 2015). Panache also deals in nail treatment and extension for clients, making them durable and nice looking. The organisation also carries out customised massage therapy in addressing stress, irritating pains, and troubles experienced by customers. Finally, the organisation makes a herbal henna tattoo and hair extension and make-up.

Panache, as a small organisation falls under the category of SMEs in the UK’s beauty industry. It can be seen that the number of private-sector companies had grown to almost 5.5 million by the beginning of 2016, out of which 99.9% are SMEs (Experts in Business, n.d). Consequently, about 15.7 million people are employed by SMEs in the UK (Experts in Business, n.d). This indicates the SME sector's significance, especially the beauty industry that has attracted the majority of market players. Putting into consideration the significant role-played SMEs, the government has been offering support to these small businesses. To this end, there has been a tremendous growth of SMEs in every sector, given the remarkable role they play in the economy. Likewise, SMEs have been productive in venturing into areas that have not been fully utilised by large and established firms already in the market. As such, small business organisations are gaining considerable ground in every sector, especially in industries with high potential customers, such as the beauty industry.

1.3 Problem Statement

The role played by a CRM system within an organisation is beyond reproach. Customers are the key organisational assets and only such organisations that value this fact gain a competitive advantage. The high-tech competition and rivalry amongst various market players encourage them to provide similar goods and services, leading to reduced customer loyalty and retention. This has a cumulative effect on the cost of running SMEs (Dyche, 2012). To this end, CRM is proving to be a major factor, as it promotes

innovation, leading ultimately to product or service differentiation for most business organisations. Effective CRM is crucial to organisations functioning in the beauty sector worldwide (Dyche, 2012). The U.K.'s beauty industry comprises large and established enterprises and small and medium firms struggling to succeed in the highly competitive world market of the 21st century. Interestingly, multinational corporations in the beauty industry are doing little to gain customer retention, and customer loyalty is concerned (Tuu & Olsen, 2016). Additionally, these corporations do not invest in CRM as they believe that they have knowledge of a real customer database and therefore exert little effort in maintaining their existing clients. Therefore, they focus on the "high" number of customers they possess and do not see the need to acquire new ones, let alone retain the regular ones. The service sector requires many efforts regarding customer management because each organisation tries its level best to outdo one another and swindle the undecided consumers in the market.

Whereas large and established brands presume to be enjoying the market monopoly, the small and medium-sized business organisations are tirelessly looking for customers that they can serve to the best of their knowledge. In the long run, these prominent organisations have been losing a considerable amount of market share to the many upcoming SMEs that would do whatever is at their disposal to gain new customers and deliver personalisation.

Personalisation is a situation whereby SMEs customise production and service delivery as per the needs of their clients and their tastes and preferences, which often translates into gaining customer loyalty and retention (Ali, Khan, Ahmed, & Shahzad, 2011). Moreover, for SMEs to be better placed in the market, they know that they need to be fully engaged with CRM initiatives or programs to ensure business survival. Though retaining existing customers is easy compared to capturing and drawing new ones to the business. SMEs in the U.K.'s beauty industry is attracting more customers, as multinational corporations (MNC) have become relaxed in their approach to consumers (Reinartz et al., 2014). Furthermore, MNCs are more focused on economically valuable consumers and avoid economically invaluable ones (BoP customers). SMEs are developing and implementing CRM programs that impact consumer satisfaction, which potentially leads to increased customer retention and customer loyalty.

As already indicated, Panache Beauty, the organisation under study, has an extensive business portfolio with some products and services charged at £3. Such product or service diversification, coupled with affordable prices, are just subsets of the CRM system that the organisation invests in to serve every customer, ranging from low-class families to high-class individuals. Such CRM initiatives that make the organisations grow quickly within the market and enjoy a large following in a competitive market are worth investigating by a researcher. Therefore, this inquiry intends to examine how an SME in the competitive beauty industry can be able to enjoy customer loyalty and customer retention because of

implementing a CRM system. In short, CRM's impact on customer retention and customer loyalty is to be examined in the context of Panache Beauty in the U.K. within this study.

1.4 Aims and Objective

1.4.1 Aim

This research aims to evaluate and highlight CRM's impact on customer loyalty and customer retention within SMEs in the UK beauty industry.

1.4.2 Objectives

The following are the specific objectives that guide the study:

- 1) To examine the elements and processes of CRM within an SME in the UK-based beauty industry.
- 2) To identify CRM's function in accumulating customer loyalty and retention within an SME in the UK-based beauty industry.
- 3) To analyse the effect/impact of CRM on customer loyalty and customer retention within an SME in the UK-based beauty industry

1.5 Research Questions

The following are the research questions:

- 1) What are the processes and elements associated with CRM within a small-scale beauty organisation in the U.K.?
- 2) What is the function of CRM in customer loyalty and retention within a small-scale beauty organisation in the U.K.?
- 3) What is the impact of CRM on customer loyalty and retention within a small-scale beauty organisation in the U.K.?
- 4) How can CRM be improved, increase customer loyalty and retention within small-scale beauty organisations in the U.K.?

1.6 Significance of the Study

CRM as a new technological improvement within business management and marketing has attracted a plethora of studies by academicians and scholars. Since CRM is beneficial to most business organisations, maintaining customer relationships and its impact on customer loyalty and customer retention dominates the literature. Additionally, most studies related to CRM are associated with MNCs. To this end, the current research fills the gap in the literature by studying the impact of CRM on customer retention and

customer loyalty within an SME in the U.K.'s beauty industry. While most studies have examined the impact of CRM in maintaining consumer relations, there has been no work that has focused on the CRM strategies used by SMEs, or their extensive customer base, as manifested by Panache Beauty. This is where the contribution of this inquiry lies.

1.7 Methodology followed

The study follows a basic research method that employs a descriptive research design, which could help gain a better knowledge of the contributions made by CRM to small and medium enterprises in the UK beauty industry. The research philosophy adopted is positivism considering that the study observes a myriad of CRM phenomena in the beauty industry. Further, it also helps to keep the study as objective as possible. A descriptive study method was chosen to analyse the connection between each independent variable on the dependent variable. The research employs a mixed-method where both primary and secondary data will be analysed to draw a conclusion. The structure of Chapters this research thesis is divided into six sections.

To begin with, chapter one deals with the introduction, which focuses on the background of the study, the problem statement, research objectives and questions, and the significance of the study. The next chapter will delve into the literature review, in which previous research works related to the current topic will be analysed and will identify the academic gap. Chapter three presents the research methodology, whereby the research onion will be used, data collection will be discussed, and data analysis and data representation will be discussed. Chapter four deals with the outcomes as the primary data collection tools directly reveal them. Chapter five discusses the findings considering the literature review and try to corroborate the research results. Finally, chapter six presents the conclusion and recommendations drawn based on the literature review and data analysis.

2 Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Over the years, relationship marketing has burgeoned as one of the most interesting fields of marketing, focusing on developing and maintaining a relationship with consumers as well as other related parties. Customer relationship marketing (CRM) and customer management are quickly becoming an integral part of marketing functions in organisations. Relationship marketing has received the ubiquitous accolade in the marketing field (Chen & Popovich, 2003). In marketing theory, the concept has also secured significant attention. Relationship marketing is specifically significant to the service industry and businesses that need high-level interaction with consumers like the beauty industry (Østergaard & Fitchett, 2012). A major characteristic of relationship marketing is that it assists in retaining or maintaining customers, but it increases firms' profitability.

CRM is an organisational technique endeavour to establish, develop, optimise, and maintain mutually viable, long-term relationships among business organisations and its clients (Shaon & Rahman, 2015). The principal purpose of maintaining these relationships is to retain consumers that have previously been attracted to the organisation. Novel types of competition and structural frameworks in the transaction process have spurred the formation of long-term communication patterns among stakeholders in the market (Šebjan et al., 2014). Great competition across businesses due to the diversification of consumers' demands necessitates the need for effective communication to capture their needs (Choi et al., 2013). Furthermore, maintaining good communication and current consumers is much cheaper for businesses than attracting new ones (Lee, 2012). To ensure continuous communication and retain consumers, the Customer Relationship Management system has been employed in myriad cases.

Literature provides evidence that it is easy to maintain and retain existing profitable customers rather than gain new ones. Both researchers and marketing practitioners have gained increased interest in the subject (Peelen et al., 2009). As such, consumer retention has gained precedence over the past few years. The concept involved simplicity, doubled up with the promise of great financial returns, has received a high priority in many organisations (Grion, 2002). It is as the adage, “make new friends, but retain old ones.” Myler, a business to the business author, notes that long-term consumers are more profitable to businesses than single deal customers (Myler, 2016).

While keeping track of consumer satisfaction is key to ensuring that the consumers remain loyal, customer communication is even more important. Communication is key to ensuring that businesses understand their consumers and vice versa. It serves as the cornerstone of interactions with people or

consumers. Effective and good communication enables parties to understand the perspectives of each side. It helps consumers understand service providers or product manufacturers much better, bringing them closer to the other (Markides, 2011). As a result of communication, a novel domain is cropping up, new service development, which research presents as an imperative field to suppliers in the current highly competitive world market: communication that occurs during new service development itself (Athanasopoulou & Johne, 2004). Hence, organisations that can integrate good communication through the customer relationship management system stand better prospects in the market.

To achieve good communication, a good CRM strategy needs to be implemented by an organisation as customers are important organisational assets that need to be maintained at all costs (Chen & Popovich, 2003; Verhoef & Lemon, 2013). CRM is implemented to ensure that customer satisfaction is achieved to at least some level, and this is a process in its entirety. However, customer loyalty and customer retention need to be considered (Heller Baird & Parasnis, 2011). The retention of consumers is possible if an organisation focuses on meeting their needs and preferences and, in turn, prevents them from switching to the competitor's products or other similar substitutes.

Discourse on CRM often touches on key elements of CRM, which are organised differently. In one form of organisation, the elements are ordered as a series of occurrences, which follow each other. These events are clustered together by the form of events that are part and parcel of the fashion industry cosmetics (Rahman and Khan, 2017). According to Rahman and Khan (2017), this approach has seven significant components in the CRM model: prospecting, relations with consumers, interactive management, comprehending consumer expectations, empowerment, connections, and personalisation. According to Kumar (2003), consumer prospecting refers to the various ways, which firms employ to locate, track, and attract new consumers. Many organisations have set up servers that comprise detailed networking, with data on customers and prospects. In the process elucidated by Payne (2010), CRM's concept is understood with regards to a scale of loyalty, emanating from the prospects of the customer, through the client, the consumer, the partner, and the support.

Relations with the consumers are another significant component of CRM and focus on how organisations invoke, develop, sustain, and enhance associations with other organisations. Many definitions abound, on the relations with consumers, as representing the cornerstone of CRM, and this concept relates to the notion of consumer loyalty as detailed in the literature (Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012b). For instance, Chow and Holden (2011) estimate that organisations are oriented towards the advantages they can reap from consumer loyalty development. Gronroos (2000) proposed interactive management as being an essential part of CRM functions. It focuses on incorporating all actions put in place to change the prospective consumer, who gets in contact with representatives of the business (Mohammed & Bin

Rashid, 2012a). The ultimate focus is on ensuring that the consumer becomes an effective and active consumer. However, it is technically founded on reciprocity, which is one significant constituent element of CRM. At the core of interactive management is feedback, which helps firms get in touch with the consumer's perceptions.

Understanding the consumer's expectations is an important area of CRM, which helps to elaborate on the desires of the consumer and ensure that the products and services that are supplied meet the consumers' expectations. Chow and Holden (2011) define understanding the consumer's expectations as the strategy taken up by organisations to understand the consumer's expectations and needs better. The ultimate result is that consumers enjoy the best products and services to accumulate consumers' long-term loyalty (Hofman-Kohlmeyer, 2016). Empowerment refers to the firm processes adopted to reward and encourage employees who take initiatives, assist consumers, and make valuable contributions to improve the relationship with consumers.

According to Reichheld (2001), rarely do firms achieve extreme loyalty from their consumers without fostering a culture of loyalty amongst its employees. Most representatives in businesses prefer to deal with loyal and repeat customers, as they are easy to serve because they understand the company's preoccupations and have very few requests. Collaborations are created when suppliers are in close contact with consumers and add needed services to their conventional offerings. Payne (2010) considers collaborations or partnering as being at one end of the loyalty scale, considering it as an important phase that normally leads to developing a tight and long-lasting association between the supplier and the consumer. According to Wilson's (2014) CRM model, the selection of a partner is the first step of the CRM process.

Further, relationship marketing dimensions contribute to successful CRM, including trust, commitment, social bonding, and communications. Trust refers to the willingness to depend on an exchange partner who spurs confidence. Trust is a key component as it assists in establishing as well as maintaining successful inter-organisational systems. Commitment is also significant in relationship marketing, as it measures consumers' loyalty (Merilyn, 2017). Social bonding, defined as the aspect of a business relationship where the parties act in a nullified manner with respect to a goal, controls business as well as social behaviour and contributes to removing any doubt, developing trust, and forging close relationships. Communication has been a vital element in CRM as it provides an understanding of the intentions and the capabilities of the partners, hence forming the groundwork for developing trust between exchanging partners.

Arguably, the corporate image emerges in consumers' minds, especially in the tourism industry, when the name of a hotel or place comes to mind. Consumers tend to deal with firms that have images that are

consistent with their self-images. The image is also defined as the way the public perceives the image of an organisation's products and services (V. Kumar, 2012). It is associated with the name of the business, the ideologies, traditions, products, and the impression of the organisation's quality of products (Budianto, 2019). Further, product images comprise various associations, including the physical properties of products and the attributes and the feelings and benefits that emanate from the consumption of the product (Chen & Popovich, 2003). Meanwhile, from the corporate perspective, the image may be regarded as the functional accumulation of consumption and purchasing experiences over long periods.

2.2 Theoretical Background

CRM is a critical strategy with which organisations seek to ensure long-term customer relationships within an organisation (Saarijärvi et al., 2013). According to Payne, businesses and organisations are adopting CRM as a marketing strategy to collect and use customer data to increase customers' value, which, in turn, leads to consumer satisfaction. Firms focus on consumer satisfaction rates as they believe that they are a significant positive association between the quality of service provided by firms and the loyalty of customers. Researchers have indicated that the relationship is created when consumers perceive mutual thinking between them and their service providers. Relationships need two sides; the supplier and the consumer (Shalehah et al., 2019).

The relationship is related to attitudes, and from the organisation standpoint, relationships can develop only when the most critical consumer interactions and contacts with consumers are relationship-oriented. Thus, organisations ought to communicate and create interaction processes that motivate relationships. The definition of CRM varies from source to source since different pragmatic and academic points of view are used (Lipiäinen, 2015). However, there is a consensus that CRM identifies, strengthens, maintains, and even terminates relationships with consumers whenever necessary.

Over the years, CRM's concept has attracted many researchers who have focused on CRM (Baird & Parasnis, 2011; Campbell, 2003; Richards & Jones, 2008; Saarijärvi et al., 2013; Wang, Po Lo, Chi, & Yang, 2004). According to Campbell (2003), consumers' demands have promoted organisations to gain interest in the concept. However, to-date firms are still grappling with comprehending the internal processes that aid organisations in learning more about consumer relationships. Furthermore, Richard and Jones (2008) acknowledge that not everything about CRM has been understood, noting that both academicians and practitioners alike are yet to develop a framework to quantify CRM's impact on businesses.

As academicians and managers increase their attention on consumer relationships' real value, others are directing their questions on the unconditional and direct effect of the phenomenon (Damm & Monroy,

2011; Debnath, Datta, & Mukhopadhyay, 2016; Zineldin, 2006). As such, advances have been made in investigating the critical processes that underlie the connection between CRM and performance (Foss et al., 2008). Drawing from positions, studies, and performance concepts, CRM research is built on a model in which two major positions of firms - cost leadership and differentiation – mediate the impact of CRM on the performance of firms (Williams, Ashill, & Naumann, 2017). Theories elucidating CRM in detail include CRM behaviour theory and institutional theory perspective.

CRM research theoretical documentation is normally unrelated to pragmatic business situations, comprising overly abstract CRM concepts (Foss et al., 2008). CRM practitioner's research on the focus area normally addressed the success rate of technology-centric CRM projects. However, CRM is intricate, especially in corporate contexts. A tentative intricacy assessment carried out by some researchers, for instance, assessing the complexities of the communication industry by Labus (2010), shows that CRM activities cover a range of departments, including marketing, customer service, sales, and billing.

The institutional theory posits that the social milieu within which an organisation operates in the impact of organisations' behaviour causes firms to assume similar practices and structures (Hillebrand, Nijholt & Nijssen, 2011). In contrast to other theories, this model accentuates the role of social processes, norms, and expectations in elucidating organisational behaviour. Various actors in organisations' environments focus on social conformity that leads organisations to depict similarities in their practices. Much of the studies that build on institutional theory thus intend to elucidate homogeneity between firms and perceive diffusion speed and adoption decisions as critical dependent variables (Hillebrand et al., .2011; Hult, 2012; Wirtz, 2016).

CRM behavioural theory intends to help gain more understanding of CRM for corporate clients (Coviello, Brodie, & Munro, 2014). As such, the grounded theory-based approach identifies the main difference between CRM for consumers and CRM for corporate clients in its bid to provide clear direction for the CRM behaviour theory (Labus & Stone, 2010). Webster confirmed this, who contends that marketing for corporate clients is characterised by the intricacy of purchase processed and products. Coviello and Brodie (2014) note that marketing seems to be relational in corporate situations and more transactional in situations that concern consumers directly. However, there are some common scenarios; hence, similarities between CRM in corporate contexts and CRM in individual contexts.

In relation to the role of governance and observability, many of the attributes of transactions that have been shown to impact vertical contract design decisions and integration decisions by transaction cost studies may also impact consumer retention. One attribute of transaction that should impact consumers' retention is the difficulty in determining the quality of the results of projects. Consumers are more likely to return if the supplier does well on the project (Hillebrand et al., 2011). When the output quality can be

measured easily, it creates robust incentives for the supplier to act well since the consumer will observe any failures quite easily.

Measurement costs lead a significant hurdle by generating the association between the project and the outcome (Foss, Stone, & Ekinici, 2008). Suppose any significant dimension of the organisation's output is hard to measure. In that case, the supplier may have the impetus to shirk due to the final product's failures will be hard to observe. In such situations, the consumer is likely to take other means to monitor the supplier to ensure they compensate for the weak incentives.

2.3 Customer Relationship Management

The effective management of customer relationships is a topic of increasing interest for many academics and scholars, especially as the business environment within the 21st century is consistently changing and evolving with the emergence of technology. Business organisations must realise that customers are critical assets within an organisation. Furthermore, they have significant economic value and, therefore, companies must put strategies in place that promote consumer offering (Roya & Salmiah, 2010). Subsequently, it is undeniable that customer value indicators should enable companies to strengthen consumer ties.

This plays a key role in helping such firms to customise and tailor their strategies, intending to boost customer loyalty, while at the same time improving diminishing client turnover (Roger, 2010). To this end, customer relationship management is part and parcel of the base of consumer value. It presents a fruitful business composition channel in which innovations are incubated, nurtured, and used to foster new technological underpinnings that win customer loyalty (Bhat and Darzi, 2016).

The relationship-based approach to the management of firms is believed to have emerged from practitioners and academics in the fields such as marketing, supply chain management, and strategy (Martin & Bush, 2000). Bagozi (1975), during the 1970s, was interested in understanding marketing practices as an exchange between buyers and sellers and, therefore, forming a foundation for relationship marketing conceptualisation. As a result, the idea of relationship marketing was developed within industrial marketing and service marketing (Osarenkhoe & Bennani, 2007). Subsequently, Webster (1992) noted that there had been a paradigm shift from a "transaction focus to a relationship focus."

From a constricted focus of marketing of being mainly for-profit and volume maximisation, a broader orientation to a matured emphasis on the establishment of "long-term customer relationships" as well as management of "strategic alliances with customers" was assured (Webster, 1992). Indeed relationship marketing can be differentiated from traditional marketing in various ways; for instance, relationship

marketing is oriented towards customer retention. Whereas traditional marketing is on one-time sales; relationship marketing has a continual customer value, while traditional marketing is based on product features; relationship marketing is pegged on a long-term basis, whereas the other is on short-term; relationship marketing highly emphasises customer service, whereas traditional marketing on low customer service; and lastly, relationship marketing is concerned with quality concerns in the entire organisation, whereas limited quality concerns are inherent in traditional marketing (Dwyer, 2007).

Based on these different features, customer relationship management can be defined in various ways. To start with, the term customer relationship management (CRM), also referred to as relationship marketing, was first defined by Berry (1983) as an attraction, maintenance, and enhancement of customer relationships. Further, he stated that selling and servicing existing customers is key as long-term marketing successes attract and acquire new customers (Berry, 1983). Gronroos (2000) extended the definition of CRM to include channels and some aspects of operations by stating that CRM is a process of establishing, maintaining, and enhancing relationships with organisational customers and other partners in meeting the objectives of the involved parties at a cost/profit. Such is achievable through the achievement of promises and mutual exchange. According to Gronroos (2000), involved partners, beyond commercial interest, can realise the mutual benefit obtainable from customer relationships. Christopher et al. (2002) define CRM as acquiring customers and then keeping them. Such is only possible through quality customer service to marinate long-term relationships.

Shani and Sujana (2008) refer to CRM as an integrated effort to identify, maintain, and build a network with customers at the individual level and continuously reinforce such a network for mutual benefit via value-added and interactive contacts long run. They further strengthen the fact that CRM must be part of the long-term relationship between the organisation and customers for the value addition of service provision. Gummesson (2007) defines CRM as simply networks, relationships, and interactions. The emphasis is on the point that strengthening of relationships is possible through developed beneficial networks between the firm and its stakeholders. Moreover, Morgan and Hunt (2004) regard CRM as activities, which are directed toward developing, establishing, and maintaining successful customer relationships. The point of focus by Moran is on maintaining a relationship and highlighting the significance of cooperation, shared values, and trust to preserve such a relational exchange.

Gartner Group (2010) brings another aspect in the definition of CRM by referring it to as a philosophy and management discipline requiring firms to engage in recognition and nurturing of relationship with their customers. The management aspect enables organisations to identify customer needs and preferences and treating the individual customer as being an important organisational asset. According to Kumar and Reinartz (2010), CRM is defined as identifying the right customers with the potential of

forming long-lasting relationships, then engaging with them as individuals or group, followed by enhancing/growing their value, and finally retaining them effectively and efficiently. Also, CRM can be defined as a technique of establishing, developing, optimising, and maintaining mutually viable and long-term relationships between business organisations and customers (Berry, 2013). Moreover, CRM refers to the entire process of sustaining and building a profitable customer relationship through the delivery of superior customer satisfaction and value (Chen & Popovich, 2011). CRM is, therefore, a customer-concentrated business strategy to enhance customer satisfaction and increase their loyalty by providing customised and time-efficient products or services according to a consumer's request.

Based on CRM's various definitions, no consensus has been reached as to the accepted approach globally as far as the definitive reference is concerned. However, from the above definitions, it is clear that CRM aims to maintain long-term customer relationships, which is beneficial to both the involved organisation and customers. Since there are many definitions of CRM, divergent perspectives have also been developed to understand the concept better. The different definitions can be analysed from five main perspectives, as evident in the literature, and they include CRM as a process, strategy, philosophy, capability, and technology. From the perspective of CRM as a process, from the onset, a process simply denotes the collection of activities or tasks that together lead to a desirable business outcome (Hammer, 2006). In a business context, a process refers to a collection of activities that can transform organisational outputs into desirable outputs.

Since a group of activities can be aggregated or sub-divided into both higher and lower level processes, the particular nature of a business process is dependent on the aggregation level used for its definition (Chen & Popovich, 2011, 2011). For instance, Srivastava et al. (2009) refer to CRM as a macro-level, high sub-divided, process that capable of subsuming various sub-processes like the creation of customer knowledge and prospect identification. Furthermore, they propose that such sub-processes can be further sub-divided into additional more refined processes at the micro-level, such as data gathering and storage, which are micro-level processes forming part of customer knowledge creation. Therefore, for any given group of activities, the specification of the needed inputs and the envisioned outputs are entirely dependent on the aggregated constituent activities. In light of this, when perceived as a process, CRM can be defined at two different aggregation levels. In particular, some authors have defined CRM as a higher-level process, including all activities that organisations indulged in an attempt to build profitable, mutually beneficial, and durable customer relationships (Srivastava et al., 2009; Reinartz et al., 2013). However, a section of scholars has narrowly defined CRM as a process dealing majorly with managing customer interactions to encourage the establishment and maintenance of profitable and long-term relationships (Shaw, 2013). In comparing the two viewpoints, the former perception refers to CRM as a

macro-level process. In contrast, the latter defines CRM exclusively as interaction management, a sub-process at the macro-level. Irrespective of the aggregation level as far as CRM definition is concerned, the process view accounts for facets of developing and maintaining CRM. This means that the process perspective, compared to other viewpoints, is the only one that blatantly acknowledges the buyer-seller relationship's gradual development.

Another perspective in which CRM can be referred to as a strategy. The strategy can be simply defined as “overall plan for deploying resources to establish a favourable position” (Grant, 1998, p.14). The strategic outlook of CRM emphasises that the allocation of resources for building and maintaining customer relationship is the lifetime value to the organisation (Tan et al., 2012). More specifically, this perception of CRM suggests that all organisational customers are not equal regarding their value to the firm. Thus, maximum profitability is only achievable when accessible resources are targeted towards customer relationships with a guaranteed desirable return (Ryals, 2013). This implies that organisations are responsible for continually assessing and prioritising customers by anticipated lifetime value, particularly in building profitable and long-term customer relationships. The proponents of the strategic definition of CRM argue that firms can build the right form of relationship with individual customers (Kracklauer et al., 2011). Indeed, strategic CRM focuses not on the development and maintenance of relationships but more on building the right relationships’ type and its positive effect on corporate profitability. Therefore, CRM is closely connected to the belief that customer relationships are regarded as portfolios of investments or assets that require active management and profitability maximisation (Ryals, 2013).

About philosophy, CRM refers to the conception that the most effective way of achieving loyalty is through proactive seeking to build and maintain long-term customer relationships. Contrary to handling recurring business transactions between organisations and customers as quarantined events, the CRM’s philosophical view emphasises that customer loyalty is only achievable if interactions are perceived in the context of a continuing relationship (Shahnam, 2013). As a business philosophy, CRM is intricately linked to the concept of marketing, which holds that firms must be organised and responsive enough to customers’ changing needs (Narver & Slater, 2010).

This means that the philosophical perspective is cognizant that for customer relationships to last long, organisations should be continually able to deliver value to their customers. Furthermore, this perspective effectively builds the bridge between the paradigm of relationship marketing and marketing concept with a focus on the significance of customer value creation, which is not well represented by other perspectives. In a nutshell, the philosophical perspective advocates for a profitable and long-term customer relationship, which is critical for daily organisational activities as driven by understanding customers' evolving needs.

The CRM's capability perspective denotes that organisations must invest in developing and acquiring resources mix to enable them to continually engage in behaviour modification toward individual customers (Peppers et al., 2009). For example, supposedly, a gigantic hardware distributor supplies desktop computers and offer related services to a small advertising company. As time progresses, the small firm's economic condition improves coupled with unparalleled creativity and a growing reputation and doubles the supply size during the following year.

In the lens of CRM's capability perspective, the hardware distributor would capitalise on such a relationship-improving opportunity, which is heightened by the distributor's capability of anticipating the changing needs of customers and modification of its behaviour towards the small firm in a way reflecting the knowledge and understanding of the changing needs. CRM's capability outlook reiterates that a particular resource mix is required for effective management of customer relationships. In essence, it is the organisation's capabilities that make it possible to execute day-to-day operations (Day, 2004). Based on the example given together with the discourse above, it is evident that effective CRM, at the minimum, demands the firm to be capable of collecting intelligence regarding prospective and current customers and applying the gathered intelligence to configure subsequent interactions between the two parties.

The last perspective is technology, which is considered as the bedrock of CRM. In simple terms, arguably, CRM refers to a technological tool that enables organisations to develop customer relationships (Massey et al., 2011). Technology plays a critical role in realising CRM efforts such as seamless linking of the front (sales) and back office (logistics) functions to offer effective and efficient interactions management across various customer-touch points (sales call, direct mail, and Internet, among others) (Chen & Popovich, 2013). Additionally, CRM tools, which are developed by technological means, enable organisations to have the harnessing power of data mining, database, and interactive technologies in collecting and storing unprecedented consumer data amount to develop knowledge and disseminate the same in the entire organisation (Bose, 2012). This knowledge is very important to efficient and effective knowledge management. Therefore, underestimating or overestimating technology's role in achieving CRM initiatives results in detrimental effects on firms' efforts related to relationship management by firms (Kangu et al., 2017).

The above perspectives are significant in expounding on the reasons for CRM implementation by organisations. Virtually all businesses are or have been influenced by what is transpiring in the international marketplace. Business organisations are currently aiming to satisfy their customers and attempt to execute this duty more effectively and efficiently than their competitors do to gain a

competitive advantage in the marketplace. The most significant goal of any business organisation is “to maintain customer satisfaction and focus on a customer-centric approach in their organisational and marketing strategies” (Lam et al., 2010, p.89).

Client satisfaction is significant and cannot be underrated by organisations because a happy consumer converts to free advertising of products or services for an organisation. It is mandatory, where a business organisation puts its customers at the centre of operation of events, processes, and strategies, to improve product/service awareness (Aihie & Bennani, 2012). Businesses from various sectors set strategies in place, ensuring that customer satisfaction and retention, are an area of focus for their employees. Therefore, employees are often encouraged to be service/product-oriented and customer-focused, with the view to consistently satisfying the needs of consumers as well as anticipating them. This is primarily one of the reasons why business organisations engage in CRM.

2.4 Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention

2.4.1 Customer Loyalty

The concept of CRM and how it is facilitating the course of consumer retention and loyalty is age-old. Since the 1990s, the concept has been one of the most proliferating concepts and highly debated subjects among academicians and practitioners. Organisations have invested or are strategizing to invest colossal amounts of resources in implementing CRM strategies, infrastructure, as well as tools to win the highly competitive market (Henneberg, 2008). Therefore, the rising demand for CRM solutions has been witnesses. Gartner reported that the CRM software market surpassed \$7.4 billion as of 2007, representing a 14% increase in one year. Forrester reported that the industry would witness moderate growth in 2010. According to Forrester, by 2006, the global incomes for CRM software providers amounted to \$8.4 billion, and by 2010, it would be \$10.9 billion (Foss, Stone, & Ekinici, 2008). Researchers, e.g., Lipiäinen, 2015, have anticipated that the CRM industry's general growth is most likely to show steady growth, with services assuming an increasing portion of revenue for vendors.

According to organisational researchers from previous decades, the way relationship marketing works is explained through the commitment-trust theory where commitment, trust, communication, and conflict resolution, have a significant impact and can predict customer loyalty (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). According to Nam, Dam, Thi, Thi, and Quynh (2017), price perception, service quality, brand image, and value offers leads to customer loyalty. Studies have also focused on the indirect influences of loyal customers. They show that using a club card system (Tesco) leads to an increase in customer loyalty.

Examining the course of literature on loyalty, it is clear attempts to define what loyalty is among scholars have profound space. The researchers' most significant issue in these studies is the inability to attain a

mutual definition of consumer loyalty owing to the fact. However, consumers' loyalty is the main variable that elucidates keeping the customer within reach; it remains to be agreed upon by researchers whether loyalty is an attitude or a mix of both attitude and behaviour.

According to the behaviour-based approach, consumer loyalty stands as the behavioural reaction founded on prejudice as the result of the consumer's psychological processes in the presence of one or more options. The behavioural approach elucidated consumer loyalty based on the premise that consumer probability, consumption, and likelihood to consume a product again (Singh and Singh, 2016). Other researchers have also looked at multi-directional behaviours of consumption as a component of consumer loyalty.

The second approach is the one that deals with attitudes as well as behaviour brand loyalty and hence defining consumer loyalty as a form of repeat buying behaviour that mirrors conscious decisions to continue paying for the same type of product. As per this school of thought, for consumer loyalty to continue being in existence, repeat buying actions must go hand in hand with a positive attitude towards the product or a specific brand (Hillebrand et al., 2011). This school of thought does not, however, only subsume the behaviours of purchasing in the past but also the value systems and the attitude of the consumer.

Customer loyalty precedes retention, as only loyal consumers would like to be associated with a company that can be entrusted with their needs and wants (Bogomolova, 2011). Making it possible for a bigger share of the consumers in a firm to be loyal is the hope of many firms. Yet, it is not clear to make consumers loyal or loyal consumers whose loyalty is divided among service providers and firms (Bogomolova, 2011). It is worth noting that the organisations that tend to adopt CRM strategies are focused on gaining customer loyalty and ensuring customer retention, with the view to gaining long-term market share to survive in the long term. This particular study focuses on SME's from the U.K.'s beauty industry. SMEs within the U.K. is trying to compete with established brands such as Est'ee Lauder, MAC Cosmetics, Maybelline, Clinique, L'Oréal, and Cover Girl (Shen & Bissell, 2013) by incorporating new market synergies that could encourage customers to prefer them as a new brand, as opposed to old brands that already exist within the industry.

Customer loyalty focuses on an organisation's set of measures used in seeking positive behavioural orientation intentions of both current and future customers towards a vendor and obtaining stabilisation, which is relationship development with the customer (Bruhn, 2011). Customer loyalty is not achieved by mere customer clubs or customer loyalty cards but through the satisfaction of customer's expectations. Consumers usually compare their subjective perceptions before purchasing a product or service and making comparisons after experiencing the purchase. This comparison often leads to a condition of

satisfaction, or appreciation, or customer enthusiasm (exceeding customer expectations). Nevertheless, the correlation between customer satisfaction and loyalty is indirectly proportional.

Therefore, when consumers evaluate the satisfaction level of delivery/tender performance, it varies depending on the client (Nguyen et al., 2013). An item could be subjected to just-in-time delivery, full-time delivery, or pre-term delivery, and, hence, though customers would be satisfied, it is associated with different reasons. Customer loyalty is part and parcel of the cause and effect chain, which comprises processes from the original client contact to the business organisation's economic prowess and success. More specifically, the chain consists of five phases of customer loyalty building (Oliver, 2009).

Research notes that the way organisations deal with consumer loyalty has changed a great deal. In previous studies, consumer loyalty was employed as a dimensioning benchmark because the competition was low and the notion that activity would be more important and efficient in a market comprised of loyal individuals in terms of market activities (Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012). The first step is the initial contact with the business organisation, anticipating that the customer should buy a product or service. The second phase is whereby the customer assesses if the product/service meets the previous expectations and satisfaction level assessment. The third stage is where customer loyalty is built (Oliver, 2009). If the client's evaluation is favourable, in that the customers' expectations are achieved or exceeded, the customer's loyalty is won.

Nevertheless, if the purchasing conviction by the customer is attained, the client may recommend the product to another potential buyer during the fourth phase (Oliver, 2009). Lastly, the fifth phase is whereby the customer ultimately decides to buy the product and become loyal, leading to organisational and economic success. Thus, the potential customer becomes the customer to the firm.

Within today's business context, CRM is greatly accepted and recognised as common practice within the beauty industry's marketing and sales business unit. Within the growing and increasingly competitive beauty industry, many cosmetic firms are trying to focus on offering better consumer value against their rivals. Yang and Liu (2010) note that cosmetic firms competing in the beauty industry embrace CRM to fill in the gaps that may exist with regards to the limited information that they have with regards to their key consumers.

A more competitive market would consequently result in difficulties in gaining customer loyalty, as customers are always likely to switch between products and brands. In creating effective retention strategies, business organisations should be well conversant with customer needs and behaviour. Loyalty is both emotional as well as physical commitment, granted by customers whenever business organisations are successful in meeting their expectations. Emotions are the feelings (positive or negative) created with an idea or object in mind (Shoemakers & Hewis, 2009).

From this perspective, loyalty then refers to the state of mind and set of desires and attitudes of the customer-driven from his/her psyche (Leventha, 2006). However, business organisations don't necessarily focus on making all consumers loyal to their products or services, but instead, focus on the improvement of customer loyalty. Therefore, clients may react to services, products, and incentives or a combination of both. Additionally, the way the information is shared and exchanged is critical in determining customer loyalty. This is because such activity or practice provides a link between the behaviour and mood of the client. Loyal customers anticipate obtaining information from the organisation because communication is an essential part of a loyalty program.

There are many forms of customer loyalty discussed within the literature, and these are based on initiatives rolled out by organisations to capture clients' attention (Leventha, 2006; Bowen & Chen, 2011). They include a loyalty bonus, inertia loyalty, convenience loyalty, price commitment, and loyalty for life (Leventha, 2006). To begin with, a loyalty bonus happens when a business organisation provides customers with a benefit in the form of a gift and reward as a token for staying loyal to the company (Leventha, 2006). This type of loyalty may be short-lived if the rewarding system is terminated. Inertia loyalty is a situation whereby the organisation creates obstacles that bar the clients or customers from moving to their competitors' products or services (Leventha, 2006). This form of loyalty may not be genuine or long-lived, as force compels consumers to pay allegiance to the company's market offerings. Nevertheless, the business may be offering items that do not exist in the market, creating a monopoly in which customers can achieve their preferred tastes and preferences. Convenience loyalty is a situation whereby a customer remains loyal to a product/service because he/she has deliberately decided not to look for an alternative product or service (Leventha, 2006). Nevertheless, the brand switch is imminent when a customer gets used to the product/service and would like to try a new one. Alternatively, the brand or organisation, which may lack market offerings, will ultimately make a customer search for other products elsewhere. Price loyalty works on the principle that a business organisation that charges the lowest price enjoys a significant market share of the client base (Leventha, 2006). This form of loyalty frequently targets Below the Pyramid (BoP) clients, who have little disposable income to spend. As such, organisations will strive to attract this market segment since they represent 65% of the population worldwide (Bowen & Chen, 2011). Therefore, by default, people will be switching to products and services that charge the lowest price.

On the other hand, individuals who consider themselves high-class may opt not to be associated with the bourgeoisie. Therefore, it demonstrates a preference for premium brands, which charge higher prices for the products/services they offer. This consumer market segment is loyal to premium prices. Finally, there is loyalty for life, in which a customer decides to be faithful to a brand for his/her entire lifetime. This

form of commitment occurs when consumers decide to continue using particular products or services irrespective of other competitors' presence and substitute products. Such loyalty is only attributed to certain products, which are considered a matter of life and death, to specific consumers, such as insurance packages, automobiles, and financial services (Bowen & Chen, 2011). This has been defined as being “real” loyalty, as the customer is determined to remain loyal to an organisation no matter the circumstances.

These various types of customer loyalty have been combined to form an equation referred to as the reliability equation (Leventha, 2006). Hence, $Loyalty = Satisfaction \times Affinity \times Involvement$ (Leventha, 2006). The equation has only arrived when the product/service meets or even exceeds customer expectations. Otherwise, no customer loyalty can be created. Upon meeting consumer tastes and preferences (expectations), involvement is evident as the relationship between the client and the business is stable since customers' feedback and concern have long been taken into consideration and amicably tackled. Affinity will only occur when involvement and satisfaction are present. This is because customers are more convinced and believe that the institution is sensitive to their needs in providing goods and services that meet their expectations. They are also involved in the discovery process of their wants and desires. The more stable the customer-business relationship, the longer the duration the consumer stays loyal to the organisation. To this end, some business organisations value the relationship between them and their customers to involve them in the design of products and services and initiatives of improving customer service (Nguyen et al., 2013). Therefore, gaining customer loyalty requires some concerted efforts on the part of business organisations.

Customer loyalty is a condition in which customers become faithful to an organisational brand (Liang & Wang, 2014). As such, customers associated with an individual brand will continue to visit the business organisation, in which it is produced or offered, even if the item is not available. However, this is a consumer loyalty process, whereby consumers relate their previous experiences in informing their purchasing decisions. If the experience is positive, customers will repeatedly visit the brand or organisation, hence the lifetime loyalty. Consequently, upon understanding customer buying behaviour, an organisation can then deliver the desired client needs and desires to perfection with regards to buying history. In turn, it is creating an attraction on behalf of the business, in consumers' eyes. The CRM system is valuable to business organisations, as it enables them to measure customer buying history's effectiveness based on his or her loyalty (Roger, 2010). In a nutshell, CRM provides the incentives, products or services, needed to win customer loyalty. Also, the system ensures that the consumer buying behaviour and customer loyalty building process are influenced positively. In turn, they encourage the

client or consumers to exhibit various forms of commitment at their convenience. Thus, for a continued and effective loyalty program, CRM must be in place to oversee the same.

Through CRM, firms in the cosmetics industry hope to lure consumers through brand image and increasing perceived product quality, gaining customer loyalty through improved customer relationship management (Yang, Jayashree, and Marthandan, 2012). Given that CRM is a strategy that is proven to increase customers' numbers and optimise value, CRM can help cosmetic firms succeed in their business sector. According to Mokhtar, Hasan, and Halim (2016), beauty companies that have adopted CRM as a business strategy are expected to increase their market share at a faster pace, compared to the organisations within the same sector that have not adopted CRM (Mokhtar et al., 2016). Chen (2011) experiment relating to the data mining of customer relationship management information suggests that cosmetics firms stand to benefit significantly from adopting CRM strategies. By applying data mining to CRM information, many cosmetic firms can target potential consumers more specifically, and marketing teams can generate the right promotional tools and actions.

Relationship marketing has an important place in the cosmetics and beauty products industry. Firms within the industry have been demonstrated how they have invested in some key techniques to gain a bigger share of customers in their domain. Meanwhile, consumers are spoiled for choice with the myriad of options they have in the market (Walker, 2004). With the universal nature of technology, cosmetics firms are finding new ways to communicate directly with consumers (Park, 2012). As a result, great benefits in sales and performance are exhibited in business to business markets, especially as far as luxury skincare products are concerned. The increasing advantages of adopting a CRM strategy are being recognised more and more every day by the ever-growing beauty industry; in fact, CRM strategies are becoming commonplace in the beauty industry in the U.K.

The consideration of CRM strategies within the beauty industry in the U.K. is particularly significant, as there is increasingly intense competition. In such scenarios, CRM assists in ensuring the satisfaction of consumers and focuses on retaining consumers. The loyalty of consumers is developed through a blend of CRM strategies and loyalty programs in different packages. Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond (2003) note that this past decade has seen a proliferation of programs that focus on consumers, especially in the beauty industry. In the U.K., retailing companies collaborating with others locally and internationally from the U.S.A, Japan, and China, have engaged in various schemes to ensure that their customers are loyal (Uncles et al., 2003). Typically, the CRM programs aimed at enhancing consumers' loyalty offer relationships and financial rewards to consumers. In some cases, benefits are also accrued to other avenues, for instance, charity organisations.

There have been many conceptualizations, such as the CRM pyramid (Kubi & Doku, 2010), that have helped elaborate on the importance of the relationship between customer relationship management and loyalty. In fact, according to Liu, Pieniak, and Verbeke (2013), the best way to conceptualize consumer loyalty would be to permit the connection between the behaviour and attitudes of consumers, to be moderated by various factors like the circumstances of individuals, the situation of purchase and their characteristics. For example, if there is a strong beauty brand, there is no means of predicting whether the people will purchase their products or not (Liu et al., 2013). What's more, it's also important for brands and organisations to understand an individual's circumstances, such as budget, time pressures, peer pressure, etc.

Individual characteristics include the desire for a wide array of products, the capacity to conform, and risk tolerance (Dickinson, 2013). Situations that may impact purchase behaviour include the availability of the product, promotions, and specific occasions where consumers need to use the product. The difference between the two perspectives, the contingency and the attitude model, is that the contingency perspective variables are elevated from loyalty inhibitor status to a loyalty determinant level (Williams et al., 2017). For instance, Dickinson (2013) defined personal or individual attributes and the buying situations as nuisance variables that prevent the natural evolution of a consumer's loyalty. On the contrary, the contingency model considers these variables as inescapable and primary in assessing the consumer's behaviour patterns (Chang, 2012).

Tajeddini and Nikdavoodi (2014) note that the intricate behavioural and social processes exhibited by consumers are conceptualized in various CRM models. In these models, scholars (Chang, 2012; Williams et al., 2017) argue that individual variables that include consumer innovativeness, as well as perceptions and attitudes of consumers, would assist in gaining a greater understanding of the way perceptions are formed and the consequent role that they play in the intentions to purchase beauty treatment services. For instance, data collected from shoppers of beauty products in Sweden demonstrates three major antecedents to purchase intentions. These antecedents include attitude towards novel beauty products, newness in seeking trends, and consumers' attitudes to buying makeup and skincare products (Tajeddini & Nikdavoodi, 2014). A CRM system that can capture these three antecedents in the beauty industry stands a better chance of helping a company stay ahead of its competitors.

In defining and elucidating CRM, Mandina (2014) explains the direct and the subliminal effects of CRM concerning repurchase and loyalty behaviours among consumers. Here, it is noted that consumers' intentions to purchase increase as CRM assists in changing the relationship with a company, especially in the beauty industry. CRM also assists the firms within the beauty industry to understand their consumers well enough to develop relevant products and package them appropriately (Kocoglu and

Kirmaci, 2012). Thus, the objective of CRM is to recognize the needs of every consumer and treat every customer as per their needs (Mandina, 2014). As such, CRM helps firms in the beauty industry offer real, excellent and timed consumer service through the effective application of individual account data and information.

Kotler and Keller (2009) provide a comprehensive list of CRM's impacts on industries, including those in the beauty industry. Firstly, CRM helps firms develop relationships, investigate new consumers, and reduce the need to keep on recruiting new customers, as existing consumers' loyalty remains high. Ultimately, this helps to reduce organisational costs. Previous researchers (Sulaiman, Baharum, & Ridzuan, 2014b; Williams et al., 2017) suggest that CRM reduces sales costs. The costs of sales are reduced as current consumers become more responsive (Zineldin, 2006). In addition to understanding the changes and distributors in the business, the relationships become more efficient in reducing the costs of marketing campaigns (Foss et al., 2008).

CRM is also bound to increase firms' profitability by increasing the customer wallet share of beauty products. This is a direct function of increased selling, followed up sales, and cross-selling (Foss et al., 2008). According to Foss et al. (2008), the beauty industry also stands to benefit from increased consumer retention and loyalty. As the CRM strategy employed encourages customers to be more brand loyal and buy products more frequently. Thus, it can be said that customer retention is interlinked with customer loyalty and sales volumes. In this regard, it is also important to understand the strength of these interlinkages or relationships. In other words, CRM encourages consumers to take more initiative, which enables them to form more of a bond with the brand and, in turn, results in customer loyalty (Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012a).

2.4.2 Consumer Retention

Customer retention has become an increasingly important managerial concern, especially within a saturated market with a diminishing number of new clients. Additionally, it is having been acknowledged that customer retention is the chief objective of relationship marketing. It plays a key role in delivering potential "superior relationship economics," that is, it is less costly in retaining the existing customers than gaining fresh ones (Reinartz et al., 2014, p.231). The presumption is that the generalised theories, which focus on global applicability, are more likely to overlook the personal impact posed by the conceptualised business situations with regards to efficient and effective strategies for customer retention. The fact of the matter is that both managers and theoreticians ought to consider the business context in which the development and implementation of customer retention strategies are anchored (Baran & Galka, 2013). The arrival of the 4Ps of marketing theory back then in the 1960s, during the industrialised

or mechanised mass production and development era, has influenced the way marketers perceive their customers (Baran & Galka, 2013). During that period, whereby the classical or traditional approach was used, customers were considered “groups of homogenous potential buyers with the same needs” (Xu & Walton, 2005).

Marketers then proceeded to make predictions as to what customers wanted and manufactured such products accordingly. What’s more, they were then distributed to consumers through distributors or organisations then captured clients' attention by enticing them to buy items through manipulation of the 4Ps (marketing mix), that is, price, place, promotion, and product (Xu & Walton, 2005). Indeed, the classical marketing approach dominated the operation and thinking of most business organisations and marketing scholars and practitioners. However, with time, organisations began to identify the weaknesses or inadequacies of the traditional marketing approach and shifted their focus to the new marketing management approach, using industrial marketing and services marketing (Reinartz et al., 2014).

As a result, maintaining long-term relationships with customers became an important business mission. To this end, multinational corporations, as well as leading supporters of the mass marketing approach, such as Elida Gibbs and Lever Brothers of Unilever, started to restructure their departments of marketing. While appointing new managers and setting up new development teams who were mandated to maintain relations with customers and retailers across the brands offered by the organisation (Reinartz et al., 2014). Indeed, good business-customer relations retain consumers in a specific organisation. This is a form of marketing, whereby business organisations build a good rapport with customers and, therefore, customers would be retained irrespective of the situation.

With the cost of losing customers being so high to modern organisations, businesses are consistently searching for new ways of acquiring, retaining, and increasing their customer base portfolio. The service sector, which was ignored during the traditional marketing era, was a key concern in the realm of customer retention, and it has been recognised that it is more critical in the business environment of today as customers demand quality services for them to be retained (Chase, 2013). Overall, the approach adopted by most organisations within the service sector has changed fundamentally.

Traditionally, a service was regarded as a post-sale ability that provided technical assistance or methods to solve problems (Chase, 2013). Such a scope is currently considered limited to customers- where a service is regarded as a corporate organisational role rather than a departmental or functional role. As the relationship between clients and organisations continue to expand and grow, any agent from an organisation has the capacity of either jeopardizing or enhancing the relationship upon interaction (Tu & Olsen, 2016). In this sense, every organisational employee must present quality service and be endowed with the appropriate skills to respond to customer needs efficiently and effectively. For example, the

employee should have welcoming and questioning skills, as well as the ability to set achievable expectations and have product knowledge and sales skills.

Unfortunately, most organisations, have not been cognizant of the wider role played by services, and therefore haven't been able to focus on elaborately eliminating obstacles that are likely to exist between the service and sales departments, as well as with other functions that are related to supporting the service. For example, sales personnel comfortably promise too much to consumers in matters related to the delivery date. Yet, he/she has not checked the inventory to confirm whether there is sufficient supply. Moreover, the salesperson fails to engage in communication with the "customer service representative, who, in turn, must handle an angry delivery department and an angry customer" (Tuu & Olsen, 2016, p.212). Therefore, within the business organisations' jurisdiction, they ensure their employees are fully trained and fit the role of service providers, and more specifically, focus on customer retention.

Organisations, especially service providers, are attentive to customer's needs and demands. Customers are regarded to have received excellent service, under the following two conditions, namely: "when those firms providing services are empowered to act on behalf of clients in a timely manner, and when the organisation has a system in place to listen and respond to customer information gathered by those closest to the client-service providers" (Chase, 2013, p.254). Thus, organisations that overlook the importance of emphasizing, the significance of playing a role as a service provider to each employee incur high costs as they risk failure. Those employees whose roles are not directly linked to services and sales functions incur a higher price for failing to do so.

When people appreciate their customer retention and customer service roles, they manifest a different perspective on what their job description entails. Business organisations are differentiated on the level of service and product provisions that they provide to the client. Those that listen to the voices of consumers outweigh their counterparts that are not customer sensitive. Consumers are "very much aware of the value sellers add by making a product work for them from the start, along with delivering the types of long-term service that maintains quality over time" (Tanner, 2014, p.245). Organizations must focus on hearing the unique voices of customers and then define or comprehend what is meant by exceptional service to them.

Measures to retain customers involve a series of activities targeted towards enhancing the transaction's whole process by positioning him positively, leading to consequential successive purchasing readiness. Retention strategies optimally operate when the organisation's retention level is high since only a 5% retention increase can translate into a profit increment of 85% (Tanner, 2014). Retention strategies are profitable because they lead to an increase in revenue from loyal consumers. It is more cost-effective to maintain a long-term relationship with the customer than accumulate a new one. These two possibilities

can differentiate organisations based on customer satisfaction, constraint, and loyalty (Tu & Olsen, 2016). Such retention strategies are part and parcel of the organisational CRM system. Therefore, CRM, customer retention and loyalty are interrelated, demonstrating the sheer importance of the current study, which critically evaluates the impact of managing a good relationship with the customer on customer loyalty and retention at Panache Beauty, which an SME within the U. K's beauty industry. Many studies have concentrated on established firms and brands (Tanner, 2014; Tu & Olsen, 2016), making upcoming firms a good research area for the study at hand.

It is critical to note that CRM strategies and technologies have recently become important to the cosmetics industry. Mobile Customer Relationship Management (mCRM) is one of the most recent developments regarding CRM systems, assisting the beauty industry (Verma and Verma, 2013). Verma and Verma (2013) note that mobile CRM services play a critical role in the new trend, whose intention is to create well managed personalised relationships with consumers though innovations in the beauty industry within the UK and elsewhere are limited with regards to the use of mCRM, Coltman (2007) notes that market enthusiasm around the concept should be considered creatively to spark the necessary combination of business, human, and technical capabilities (Coltman, 2007). As such, it should not come as a surprise that vendors should be quick to highlight and allocate the needed resources for customer relationship management to generate novel forms of competitive advantage.

In enhancing CRM strategies, firms in the beauty industry need to note that most people only purchase what they require. According to Bolton, Kannan, and Bramlett (2010), most consumers do not use their loyalty development credit at one time. This is even though the program is meant to motivate consumers to make purchases specifically. Similarly, so et al. (2016) found that a significant portion of consumers in the market already have loyalty cards and are affiliated to a particular form of CRM and do not use their cards for at least three months. This, therefore, provides an opportunity to achieve a competitive advantage by establishing a stronger bond between consumers and beauty brands. It is envisaged that such an approach will help to stimulate demand for beauty products.

On the other hand, it is important to acknowledge that a CRM strategy can help develop a loyalty program, where consumers could purchase from a particular category even if they do not buy a specific brand. If such a program sufficiently appeals to consumers, then developing a new form of loyal consumers becomes possible. However, in such a case, the CRM program's significant appeal could also be seen as a program's weakness. It is noteworthy that this course of action is also likely to induce a quick counter-response from the heads of businesses whose brands stand to lose out significantly (Sulaiman et al., 2014b). Even as the CRM strategy is attracting consumers, the consumers are likely to develop a

relationship with the CRM program, rather than the brand that the program intends to boost (Bolton, Kannan, and Bramlett, 2010).

However, it is also important to recognise that some of the purchase is undertaken in more than one brand in a beauty category. Nevertheless, the development of CRM strategies in the beauty industry will improve as the developers consider these factors. For such consumers, there are opportunities for bringing about a realignment of purchasing, without necessarily demanding any significant shifts in consumers' behaviour or attitudes towards the brand's purchases, from the category of the product. It is not realistic for brand managers to suddenly expect consumers to become loyal to one particular brand if the customers have valid reasons for being loyal to various brands. According to empirical evidence (Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012b; Williams et al., 2017), consumers do not necessarily have the desire to watch one station of television, dress in one brand of clothing, or adopt one model of beauty product, and so forth, (Dopico and Porral, 2011). Given this diversity, it is a significant drawback for managers in the beauty industry to convince a sufficient number of consumers to minimize their beauty brands' repertoire. The propensity to purchase their specific brand goes higher enough to span over the program's overall expense.

2.4.2.1 Customer Retention in the Future

In the future, there will be a need for fashion CRM strategies to address the underlying causes of polygamy. Under such situations, the best method for consumers to reallocate some of their categories to a specific brand is to have a program that can address polygamy's real causes. Thus, members of a program might require greater access to fashion or a beauty brand, offer more options, or assist in consolidating their buying with fewer brands or providers (Angelova, 2011; Richards and Jones, 2008). However, previous research suggests that it is hard to devise a CRM or loyalty program that can differentiate well enough in repeat purchases and highly competitive markets (Petrescu, 2013b; Roggeveen & Grewal, 2016b). Additionally, studies also demonstrate that it is hard to separate the economic and functional benefits purely from the membership benefits program (Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012a).

It is important to consider a CRM strategy as an extension of the brand in the beauty industry. This perspective is critical towards the improvement of the results a CRM program can reap. In this case, consumers who are members of a firm's loyalty program in the beauty industry would be encouraged to purchase products that they would not have bought on a normal occasion from the provider. Essentially, the CRM strategy would be an extension of the marketing (Kearney, 2012). For instance, through such programs, Tesco attempted to expose some of its lower-margin goods to consumers. One issue is that

most cross-selling chances are in greatly competitive markets, which usually support loyalty programs. The implication is that only those truly exceptional programs will assist in changing the landscape in the beauty and cosmetics industry.

According to Kearney (2012), there is an even greater need for the beauty industry to enhance the experience at the point of sale (POS). For firms to differentiate their products in the competitive and crowded beauty industry, key CRM practices ought to be understood. Hence, an understanding of the POS experience and its influence on brands' performance is of particular significance to retailers and consumers. Such understandings would help to ensure a consistent experience in all channels of distribution. This will help the organisation to adopt a model that enhances customer experience at the point of sale.

Understanding the POS experience is critical as it can impact a brand's performance in the beauty industry in three major ways. Firstly, by enhancing brand image and customer satisfaction, the general atmosphere of the POS and the design of CRM directly impact the brand's overall perception among consumers in the beauty industry. This is particularly attributed to premium beauty products, where consumers and well-heeled shoppers have high expectations. This assertion is consistent with the literature that positions branding as an important element in organisations (Foss et al., 2008; Williams et al., 2017). Through efficient and effective branding, sufficient organisational return can be attained (Lahap, Ramli, Said, Radzi, and Zain, 2016). Thus, implementing a robust brand image helps to ensure the general success of the organisation.

Secondly, the POS experience can be viewed as a resource that guides traffic emanating from the media. Beauty companies need to invest sufficiently in the media to further a specific category or brand. For example, the idea of associating brands with special occasions and holidays. In a similar vein, consumers associate fragrances with Christmas, Valentine's Day, and other similar occasions. Yet, it is still unclear whether media-driven business visibility works to benefit a particular category or brand (Kearney, 2012). Other practitioners suggest that the POS experience can benefit a firm by multiplying the media's efforts or disadvantage a firm by dividing the same effect (Foss et al., 2008).

Thirdly, POS helps to stimulate incremental sales. The POS experience also influences incremental sales. However, the actual influence is hard to isolate, but the two are connected (Lahap et al. 2016). For example, Japan, which is arguably among the biggest beauty markets globally regarding its focus on the service industry, tends to spend more time building one-to-one relationships with consumers. This approach helps to increase productivity and sales. As such, the best counter managers lose a few customers (Kearney, 2012). Consistent with this view, Macy's in the U.S.A. initiated a CRM strategy across beauty brands known as Magic Selling. Here, the strategy allows customers to meet managers,

ask questions, receive options and advice, and get the inspiration to purchase. This helps to establish stronger bonds between Macy's staff and the consumers.

Kearney (2012) also notes that it is critical to have a CRM strategy that will help understand what is more important to consumers and retailers. In fact, in selling premium beauty products, sellers can separate the point of sale journey for a shopper into five significant steps, that include an introduction or welcome, the atmosphere, the touch and feel, consumer advice, and purchase or check out Lahap et al., (2016). Every step is critical, as it allows the seller to maximize the consumer's experience. If the seller misses out on one point, they are not selling at the maximum level (Kearney, 2012). For example, Nespresso stands out as shoppers who visit its boutique shops receive VIP treatment from the time; they make their way into the store. These customers receive an invitation to the coffee bar, right to the point where they make a purchase.

It is critical to understand how POS experience differs across regions. Research shows that what shoppers think varies from what retailers think Kearney (2012). Interestingly, previous research has observed that shoppers of beauty products in China and the United Kingdom have similar needs (Lahap et al., 2016). However, the shopping experiences have to be personalized to avoid frustration on the part of the shoppers. On the contrary, there are differences in retailers' needs and expectations in the United Kingdom and China. Chinese retailers assert that it is a combination of a premium brand (the best according to them being La Mer and Chanel) and the sales staff attitudes that work. In China, beauty firms should tailor-make their service and ensure that their products solve consumers' skin problems (Kearney, 2012).

On the other hand, retailers in the U.K. do not value the brand's image at the same level. They put a lot of emphasis on the retailer's image. However, the attitude concerning service is the same. For example, Debenhams in the U.K. has knowledgeable advisors, offers expertise, and a great diagnosis. Similarly, in the U.K., John Lewis also considers clarity as an important element (Pithers, 2014).

Retailers invest heavily in beauty brands and expect the brands to enhance consumers' buying experience (Izvercian&Potra, 2014). This helps them to grow sales in their physical stores. In the United States, big beauty brands, such as Sephora, Macy, and Ulta, have taken the time to create rich brand images and great store environments. Macy's introduced its Impulse Beauty strategy, which combines its well-known beauty counter products with kiosks that emulate gondolas for its niche brands (Kearney, 2012). The general use of space is highly innovative, and it is aimed at attracting young customers. Kearney (2012) proposed a fourth aspect related to replicating the POS experience across channels of distribution. Previous research suggests that only a few brands can recreate the POS experience through technological

advancements (Lahap et al., 2016), as in mobile phone applications that offer real-time information and instruction.

Additionally, services such as Clinique Forecast and The Next Best Thing are wonderful examples of mobile applications that serve to inform and instruct consumers of Estee Lauder on its Clinique brand (Zineldin, 2006). Given this background, it is suggested that managers in the beauty industry should seek to replicate their in-store experiences to capture more sales. The example of Sephora suffices in elucidating this concept; the online shop gives consumers an option of choosing from a collection of free samples once they reach the checkout point. Another important consideration that would enable organisations to enhance their CRM strategies is a deeper understanding of their beauty secrets.

Armoudoum and Ben-Shabat(2012) not understanding the behaviour of the consumer, the journey of the shopper, the expectations of the retailer, and drawing lessons from other firms in the luxury product business play a significant part in the cosmetics and beauty industry and their quest to offer a positive consumer experience at the point of sale (Kearney, 2012). In essence, enhancing the CRM strategy is critical because beauty is only as deep as the consumer's experiences. In drawing lessons from other firms, the U.K. beauty industry can learn a lot from the Japanese beauty market, where there is a cultural obsession with smooth, flawless skin. The beauty industry is among the biggest industries within the Japanese culture, with more people employed in this industry alone than the software and automotive industries combined (Lahap et al., 2016).

Regardless, it should be acknowledged that the beauty industry in the U.K. is beginning to draw important lessons from Japanese beauty firms' beauty websites, which are considered gold mines of information (Kearney, 2012). They are taking heed of the beauty secrets shared by the Japanese firms. Beauty secrets include making connections between eating wisely and the idea of enhancing both health and beauty. Another aspect is that of following the wisdom of age-old beauty secrets, regardless of technological advancements. Thus, there is a need to integrate meditative practices into their stressed and harried lifestyles to balance body, mind, and spirit for total, radiant beauty (*Asian Beauty Secrets: Ancient and Modern Tips from the Far East*, n.d.). Incorporating the beauty secrets within the CRM strategies and programs would only work to benefit beauty firms in the U.K.

In tandem with developments in the information technology landscape, customer retention strategies in the future are bound to employ the features made available by technology. For instance, big data presents an effective method through which businesses in the future are set to extract important knowledge to support business choices. Predictive analytics solutions will rely on big data in order to facilitate that important purpose and a combined solution that will profit from both the enormous amounts of data and advanced solutions in machine learning(Hofacker, Malthouse, & Sultan, 2016). The predictive analysis

based on big data, which is designed for marketing, is referred to as marketing analytics solutions, and their use in the future will increase.

Researchers have recently identified guidelines for conventional consumer relationship management solutions to use and benefit from big data explosion, especially in relation to social media (Amado, Cortez, Rita, & Moro, 2018; Hofacker et al., 2016). The recommendations include using marketing analytics tenets in human resources and predictive models with analytical competencies to take the most from CRM systems and solutions. Simultaneously, several studies have also highlighted the importance of combining analytics techniques in CRM encompassing widely understood marketing concepts like assessing the lifetime value of consumers. Future endeavours would comprise the use of Big Data to respond to consumers' needs in a much keener manner. Through Big Data analytics, interactive customer dashboards and reports can be generated for managers to make the right decisions and respond to the consumers (Amado et al., 2018).

Thus, Big Data technological solutions will provide the right tools to support marketing and organisations in retaining consumers. Of course, it is expected that with these technological tools, the analysis will be more accurate as compared to human solutions. As of 2012, research had already identified a huge gap in the future in terms of empowering marketing through Big Data. Recent research confirms that though some attempts were already made to fill the gap, the gap's size is still wide, considering the velocity of available Big Data (Amado et al., 2018). Therefore, the next years of research will provide an appropriate opportunity for research and the development of solutions for consumer relationship marketing that explore the information afforded by Big Data.

2.4.3 The function of CRM in Customer Loyalty and Retention

What makes organisations unique today in consumer demand-driven and highly competitive markets is their ability to meet consumers' priorities and preferences. With heightened competition, organisations realize the significance of loyal customers and consumer retention strategies (Foss et al., 2008). Customer relationship management (CRM) systems' main function is to increase consumers' chances of returning and protracting their length of stay as clients. According to studies, the protracted stay of consumers and profitability are significantly associated. An increase in profitability has been reported by firms that can increase consumer retention rates. For instance, a particular study has shown that as little increase in retention as 5% can lead to significant profit margins ranging from 35% to 95% (San-Martín, Jiménez, & López-Catalán, 2016).

Extant literature in CRM has assessed the various angles of the consumer relationship. While some researchers are focussed on formulating methods to model the retention of consumers, others are

concerned with studying the factors that underlie consumer satisfaction and retention (Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012; San-Martín et al., 2016). These studies assist us in understanding CRM's functions and the most relevant factors to consumer management and retention. In business to business transactions, the transactions' characteristics tend to work in conjunction with each other in a repeated manner over time. Therefore, it is critical to capture the features of both the current businesses as well as the previous ones. Studies highlight that consumers recognize the efforts of firms. Still, they only appreciate the effort when they get to see that they will get their desired outcomes from the organisation (S. R. Kumar, 2009). Organisations are thus seen as a significant part of developing and managing relationships with consumers, with some having a more direct contact than others, hence contributing to the provision of satisfaction and service quality and consequently to overall customer retention (Hosseini, Maleki and Gholamian, 2010). For instance, in providing satisfaction and service quality in the beauty industry, if consumers are not serviced in a friendly and efficient manner, the consumers will most likely not lead to loyalty or retention.

Employees of an organisation also serve a critical role in communicating the organisation's values to the general public and consumers by managing the times and points before purchasing to when a consumer makes a purchase and feels satisfied. Strategies of relationship marketing are more applicable to industries where consumers' opinions and preferences are very significant, and the beauty industry is among them industries (Vesel and Zabkar, 2009). According to researchers, providing rewards and offering products by being sensitive to the consumers' demands and desires is imperative (Shaon and Rahman, 2015). Therefore, firms are now attempting to be more innovative regarding their CRM strategies, including rewarding consumers loyal to them and their products. This will promote the growth of their business.

From a conceptual perspective, it can be contended that the effective implementation of a CRM system should enhance CRM processes and their influence on any new products' performance. CRM systems enhance the process of mining the information that has been accumulated from consumers. CRM technologies facilitate relaying information between the consumer and the organisation (Angamuthu, 2015). Furthermore, improved correspondence of information between an organisation and its consumers inevitably results in more information regarding key target consumers, enabling organisations to effectively target their consumers and find ways to manage customer information effectively. Furthermore, CRM technologies enable organisations to effectively and efficiently assess large amounts of consumer-specific information and make it available to key decision-makers within an organisation (Nam et al., 2017). In short, CRM technologies support organisations in enabling them to assess and

examine specific segments of their target customers. This is particularly relevant to the beauty industry in the UK.

CRM directly impacts consumers' loyalty, as literature demonstrates that developing and sustaining relationships with consumers is pivotal in encouraging repeat purchase behaviour over time (Hillebrand et al., 2011). Once a firm develops a base of loyal consumers, it can devote its time and resources to other critical business matters. Consumers do demonstrate their loyalty to a firm in various ways. They can choose to continue using a certain product, remain with a particular beauty firm, or both. Although some researchers, such as Dick and Basu (2004), differentiate between brand loyalty, product loyalty, salespeople's loyalty, and so on.

From an individual perspective, CRM has many benefits and can be looked at as a vehicle that enhances consumers' loyalty in the beauty industry to one specific brand. It induces greater resistance among consumers regarding offers from other brands, decreases the sensitivity to price amongst consumers, dampens the desire to look to other beauty brands, encourages marketing through endorsements and word of mouth, and attracts numerous consumers. For example, Bolton et al. (2010) found that members recruited into a loyalty program through CRM were less sensitive to customer care offered while purchasing different products, as opposed to those who were not in any loyalty program.

As per this focus, myriad consultants' rhetoric proposes that CRM's ultimate focus is to create a bigger cohort of loyal consumers in any given organisation. However, consumer loyalty assessment shows that this is both unachievable and undesirable by consumers (Bolton et al. 2010). Indeed, if consumers are already loyal to one brand, the scheme will only effectively create sales if it can attract people to purchase more products from the same brand. This is not easy to attain when so many consumers within the beauty industry are still light users of such products. Therefore, in these circumstances, they have to be persuaded to purchase more of a particular brand and more products in various categories of beauty products. This can be quite challenging if consumers are not motivated explicitly by a species program, brand, or category.

2.4.4 Empirical Studies on the Impact of CRM on Customer Loyalty and Retention

Customer relationships have been studied greatly over the ages in the academic discourse. An intense curiosity in consumer relationships is also evidenced in various marketing practices and is most conspicuous in the significant expend in an organisation's consumer relationship systems (Chen & Popovich, 2003; Foss et al., 2008; Hillebrand et al., 2011). Consumer share and customer retention rates are critical parameters in CRM. Consumer share refers to the number of purchases by consumers of a specific category of services and products from a specific supplier in relation to the total purchases in

that category. To maximize these parameters, organisations employ relationship marketing instruments such as direct mailing and loyalty related programs (S. R. Kumar, 2009). Organisations also develop close associations with consumers to bolster consumers' relationship perceptions.

Several studies have been done on consumer relationship management's impact on either the share or retention of consumers (Foss et al., 2008; Hillebrand et al., 2011; Lipiäinen, 2015). A few studies have considered the impact of relationship management infrastructure on consumer retention. On the other hand, the impact of the RMI on consumer share has not received sufficient interest. Furthermore, most studies focus on consumer share in a specific category of products such as Narayandas and Bowman (Long, Khalafinezhad, Ismail, & Rasid, 2013). Huge sales of the same brand and products can improve this share; however, organisations that sell various products and services attain greater share increments by cross-selling their brands. In addition, few studies have been conducted on the impact of CRP and RMIs on consumers' share and retention.

Previous studies have employed cross-sectional and self-reported data that describe both CRMs and consumer share (Verhoef, 2003). The application of such data may have prompted the overestimation of the considered relationships due to the methodological issues such as backfire and carryover and common variance of methods. Such data may not establish a causal association; indeed, an assertion could be made that causality works the other direction. Longitudinal data, as opposed to cross-sectional data, should be employed to examine the causality between consumer share and consumer share antecedents. Sofi and Hakim (2014) conducted a study that explored the relationship between customer relationship management (CRM) and customer loyalty in a sample of 100 retail Indian banks (both public and private). The specific objectives of the research were: (1) to assess CRM practices; (2) to examine the impact of implementing CRM; and (3) to highlight the vital CRM factors that have an impact on customer loyalty. The findings revealed that CRM practices such as customer prospecting, CRM technology incorporation, management of knowledge, the organisation of CRM, and key customer focus indicate the level to which the customers are willing to be loyal to banks they are subscribed to. Also, private retailing banks were found to implement CRM more effectively than their public counterparts. Hence, the former is more innovative in understanding customers and building good relationships with them. Additionally, customers had a significant level of fulfilment needs and, therefore, CRM should aim to provide higher-level services and value offerings. In a nutshell, CRM practices lead to customer loyalty.

Malik (2015) evaluated CRM's impact on winning customer loyalty and retention in the automobile sector. Two specific objectives were pursued: (1) to analyse the effectiveness of CRM on customer satisfaction; and (2) to investigate the impact of CRM on customer retention. The results revealed that 94% of customers are satisfied with CRM practices such as service delivery time and the trust,

promptness with which handling of repair work is done, friendly helpfulness, the arrangement of replacements, and the obligation to fulfil customer needs. Satisfied customers remain loyal to the organisation and are retained.

Angamuthu (2015) analysed the relationship between CRM practices and customer satisfaction levels in the hotel sector. According to the findings, there is a direct link between CRM practices and customer satisfaction in the hotel sector. The CRM elements used in this study included upgrading customer relationships, customer orientation strategies, customer value, customer management interaction practices, CRM-based technology, and customer contact programs. These practices lead to customer satisfaction in the selected hotels under study. Satisfied customers would then be loyal and retained in the hotels as the services provided meet their tastes and preferences.

Azzam (2014) focuses on the impact of CRM on customer satisfaction in Jordan's banking industry. In achieving this aim, the research aimed to meet the following objectives: (1) to determine the role-played CRM in the achievement of customer satisfaction in Jordan's banking industry, (2) to examine CRM practices used by Jordan's banking industry, and (3) to investigate the relationship between customer satisfaction and CRM in Jordan's banking industry. The findings revealed a close relation between CRM practices used in the banking industry and satisfaction. In the banking industry, CRM practices like service quality, employee behaviour, keeping a customer database, providing solutions to customer problems, customers' physical environment, and interaction on the social network are key in ensuring customer satisfaction.

Finally, Tauni, Khan, Durrani, & Aslam (2014) examined the relationship between customer relationship management and customer retention within the telecom industry. The study's findings revealed that CRM plays a crucial role in customer retention, and it contributes to over 68% of customer retention. This is possible through the development of an effective relationship with customers by providing excellent services to them. Therefore, this study's CRM element is the provision of excellent services, which make customers loyal.

Yaghoubiet al. (2017) assess the impact of CRM on customers' productivity, satisfaction, and trust. The researchers show that among the impacts, CRM's greatest impacts are on trust and customer loyalty. On the flip side, programs such as patient complaint management in healthcare settings have been reported as one of the main drivers of customer satisfaction. Studies also show that among CRM functions, diversification of services brings one of the greatest impacts. The existence of novel services and consulting services endeavour to provide services based on expectations and needs proving further that CRM bears a great and important impact on the loyalty and retention of consumers. Some researchers consider CRM as a business strategy that is designed to respond and react to the needs and demands of

consumers so that organisations can more effectively communicate with their consumers and hence gain by securing the trust of consumers.

Customer interaction, another important CRM function, has also been linked with positive outcomes for organisations. Long (2013) introduces consumer interaction and consumer strategies as important CRM areas that are consistent with other results on the impact of CRM on retention and loyalty of consumers. Training of workers on how to deal with customers and consequently lead to the satisfaction that ensures the business maintains its customers. Also, being able to identify and prioritize different customers has been shown to have a high impact on the relationship and retention of consumers. Scholars have shown that properly identifying consumers leads to business profitability as well as reduction of costs. In the consumer satisfaction dimension, the existence of CRM allows measurement of satisfaction of consumers. Sayedi et al. (2009) have assessed the association between CRM function and loyalty among consumers, which the consumer satisfaction dimensions, including channels for complaining and feedback, have also been found to have a profound impact.

Among the elements of consumer trust and loyalty, consumers referring potential clients to other firms if better conditions are available, there has been shown to have the lowest impact (Sayedi et al. 2009). This implies that if the conditions in other firms are better, clients still feel the need to loyal and there is trust between the client and the business, among the elements of loyalty and trust, the problems and issues of clients, such as financial issues, have been pointed out to have a significant effect. One of the impacts of CRM in studies is productivity. Jones and Keith present a list of advantages that are expected from CRM. The researchers finally conclude a list of seven benefits such as effectiveness and efficiency that is consistent with the concept that CRM leads to higher productivity in an organisation, and that includes retention and satisfaction of consumers. Additionally, in Ko et al. (2008) article, the CRM adoption and the characteristics of organisations, it has been pointed out that CRM leads to consumer loyalty, enhanced productivity, and efficiency. Customer relationship stands as a strategic imperative for all entities as its proper implementation can lead to higher consumer satisfaction, consumer loyalty, and attraction of customers and therefore leading to more repeat purchases and general sales.

2.5 Consumer Culture

Culture is an abstract and intricate construct that comprises of myriad implicit as well as explicit elements that render it hard for academicians across disciplines to settle on a single definition. More than two hundred descriptions of culture exist; however, on the broad context, Taylor's definition is highly esteemed. According to Taylor, culture refers to an intricate. At the same time, that subsumes beliefs, knowledge, morals, customs, and law, as well as any other habits and capabilities acquired by members

of the society. Moreover, Hofstede et al. (2010) define culture as the aggregate mental programming of people. The author employs the term “programming” to minds based on the notion that computers are programmed through the use of the software. Software varies from one environment to another.

As such, Hofstede et al. (2010) intend to point out that cultures are to communities as personalities are to people. Consequently, some of the commonplace aspects of the phrase culture found among the definitions include the learning aspect of culture through social relations, the non-genetic characteristic of culture, the mutuality aspect of culture, and that cultural aspect are transmitted from one generation to another. The consumer society concept has gained precedence in the recent past (Hirst & Reekie, 2013). This field is attracting scholars from various disciplines, including marketing and sociology. A good understanding of the components and drivers of consumer culture all around the world is important to understanding various aspects regarding consumer behaviour, important organisational aspects, societal dynamics, and uncovering what makes consumers respond in various ways to the forces that drive their consumption. Thus, the implicit interrelationship between consumption concepts, consumer society, and consumer culture merit in-depth investigation.

In the most basic sense, consumption is a term used to signify satisfying needs. A need appears compulsory for human existence owing to the fact that it pleasures satisfying (S. R. Kumar, 2009). Consumption bears both economic and social connotations also linked to space and time, depending on desires, wants, and value necessary for ensuring demands are fulfilled. According to Williams (1991), the outmoded implication for consumption is to spend, destroy, or waste. The non-self-sufficient individual has a myriad of social, psychological, and cultural needs. All actions towards meeting any of these could be referred to as consumption. Apart from this meaning, it is also possible to employ the concept to mean some other values that are spent even without an actual or real need (Williams, 1991). Consequently, consumption could be looked at as spending both tangible as well as intangible values that are ventured to attain certain demand, whether an actual one or a feigned one.

According to another school of thought, consumption, which comes about through the decision of a consumer to buy, is a process that aggregates behaviours to utilize economic goods. To define the consumption concept enough, the ultimate aim of economic activities, Ritzer (2003) assumes the description by Marx that classifies consumption goods as either luxury or subsistence. According to Ritzer, consumption enables people to get goods as well as services and also exploits individuals by holding them under control (Ritzer, 2003). In other terms, consumption implies the ability to have a service or a good or to own either, to use or dispose the same in order to gratify specific needs.

In today's era, the concept of consumption is perceived from both a positive as well as a negative angle. The notion is founded on a richer life as a result of more production and higher consumption, and it is

regarded as a factor that limits the freedoms of people and makes them dependent on others or alienates them (Ritzer, 2003). Contrary to the perceptions of researchers in the field of economics who see consumption as an action that is meant to meet the needs and to benefit, Baudrillard considers consumption as a desire for any product to remove the importance and refers to it as a system for indication and not one that meets the needs (Mendoza, 2010). Consumption is a process of interpretation and communication for individuals to position themselves.

The consumption of products made in the market and the desire that is invoked by marketing symbols is core to consumer culture. Yet, the reproduction and continuum of this system largely rely on the exercise of individual free will in the private scope of daily life (Bose, 2015). Consumer culture refers to interlinked systems of commercially developed texts, images, and objects that groups employ through the development of conflicting and even overlapping identities, practices, and implications to make general sense of the contexts and to orient the consumers in specific relationships and roles (Childs & Jin, 2016). Further, consumer culture is used to describe a network that comprises dense extensions and global connections through which the global and transnational capital highly interpenetrates local cultures.

Maybe most critically, consumer culture embodies culture as the very fabric of meaning, experience, and action. Due to its fragmented and internal intricacy, consumer culture does not lead to action as a causal force (Weber & Villebonne, 2002). Just like a game where players improvise within the limits of the rules, consumer culture and the entire marketplace ideology perpetuate and expand the horizons of consumers of conceivable feeling, action, and thought to make particular patterns of behaviour and interpretations more possible than others. The distributed understanding of cultural meaning accentuates the dynamics of plurality, fragmentation, fluidity, and intermingling of traditions of consumption and consumer lifestyle (Bose, 2015; Giannakis, Bompilis & Boutsouki, 2014). While distributive perceptions of culture are not the invention of Consumer Cultural Theory (CCT), the views have been developed to a significant extent through empirical studies that assess how specific manifestations of consumer culture are devised, sustained, changed, and moulded by broader forces such as ideologies and narratives and grounded in particular marketplace systems and socioeconomic systems (Gilovich, Kumar, & Jampol, 2015).

Cultural influences on the behaviour of consumers and purchasing can be summed up in inclination to change, buying behaviour, reasons for purchasing, particular products that consumers purchase, the structure of consuming, communication, and the process of individual decision making, acquisition of products, the behaviour of consuming the product, the compliments that consumers give regarding products, the adoption or diffusion of innovations, and the characteristics of consumption (Durmaz, 2014). Cultural factors, such as communication and systems of language, belief systems, values, symbols, artefacts, and rituals, influence the decisions that people make (Manrai & Manrai, 2010).

In this manner, it is conceivable that culture bears a huge impact on the manner in which consumers consume (Manrai & Manrai, 2010). For example, Americans are known for their preference for convenience and big vehicles, while Japanese are popular for their love for small, fuel-efficient vehicles. McDonald's' adoption of a famous menu in France owing to the unique appetite, there is also another good example. Featherstone names three aspects of consumer culture: the first one emphasizes the expansion of capitalist goods production, leading to the deployment of consumption of leisure activities and other products from contemporary western societies.

This scenario is welcomed as empowering individual equality and freedom by some, while others look down on it as a way of increasing manipulation ideologically. The second school of thought underlines the gratification that emanates from goods associated with their culturally construed meanings. The third aspect looks at consumption as a source of pleasure and fantasy, "celebrated in specific consumption places and cultural imagery such as shopping malls that generate aesthetic pleasure and direct physical excitement (Podrug, 2011). Cultures are changing with time, and consumer culture in the future ought to consider changes in differentiation, distribution, price changes, and other key changes.

Jones and Richards (2008) contend that the organisation focus on CRM organisation is likely to influence the marketing decisions in the future, such as price, brand differentiation, and distribution. In this case, it has also been noted that many cosmetics firms, flexible and cleverly price their fashion products, according to data collected from customers (Richards and Jones, 2008). Customer orientation and knowledge of the customers is vital when implementing any form of CRM strategy as a whole. What's more, it is important to account for the fact that when collecting data about customers, it enables organisations to gain a clearer picture of their current target market and they are in turn able to develop strategies to establish and develop relationships that are beneficial to them as a business.

Interestingly, Halmajan and Dutu (2011) are of the opinion that the implementation of a CRM strategy would be a total failure if the information technology is not well utilized. Therefore, the suitable application of technology in CRM and marketing as a whole is one of the most significant opportunities that are currently available to the beauty industry. Since it is critical to get the right information from consumers, at the appropriate time, so that the correct decisions can be made and the right products and services rendered. In support of that assertion, Kasim and Minai (2009) reported that CRM technology is profoundly embedded, to enhance the performance of the cosmetic industry, because beauty and cosmetics firms need information technology to enhance their performance.

According to Mishra and Mishra (2009), some perceive CRM as a technology tool while others view technology as a critical element critical in its implementation. They continue by stating that technology contributes greatly to the success of CRM. At the same time, Bose (2015) reiterates that CRM comprises

of business processes and technologies that are adopted to ensure that the needs of consumers are met in any business to consumer interaction. Further, technology has been considered to be a vital component that assists firms to achieve business excellence by inviting the participation of consumers in the manufacturing process (Izvercian&Potra, 2014). In extensions of CRM such as Prosumer-oriented Relationship Management, it is noted that prosumers serve as creative consumers, and they allow their innovative potential to be utilized through technological-based processes and tools.

With this in mind, new technologies are being regarded as the core drivers for change within the beauty industry. Furthermore, several studies (Bose, 2015; Mohammed & Bin Rashid, 2012a; Sulaiman et al., 2014a) that have been undertaken with regards to the influence of information technology, on the performance of firms have reported similar results, regarding the positive position of information technology when considering CRM strategy. In other words, these studies demonstrate that many customer-centric strategies are not able to attain their goals and be successful if they are not supported by information technology.

Another aspect of culture is the geographic characteristics associated with culture. Conventionally, culture has been defined by geographic parameters. However, in the recent past, global flows have made the territorial boundaries to be blurred. Consequently, consumer behaviour, along with cultural patterns, are no longer bound to particular territories, but instead, they are interconnected across wide geographical regions. Douglas and Craig identified five different outcomes: contamination in culture, deterritorialization, interpenetration, hybridization, and pluralism, which emanate from global flows (Samuel Craig & Douglas, 2006). For instance, if a huge group of immigrants from Turkey moved to Netherlands and Germany while still retaining their ethnic identification, there will be a significant demand for the products they esteem in their ethnicity. As a result, the globalization phenomenon, though it creates a global culture, it also leads to the formation of myriad subcultures. Global consumers are familiar with various global brand names today in various industries such as Hugo Boss, Ikea, Nike, McDonald's, and so on. However, every consumer depicts behaviour that is different from another owing to the different levels of acculturation pertaining to each subculture (Manrai & Manrai, 2010). In the global consumer culture, acculturation refers to how individual consumers acquire skills, knowledge, and behaviours that are characteristic of emergent and borderless global consumer culture.

2.6 Consumption Styles

The concepts of labour at work and production are of key significance in the initial stages of industrialization. Eventually, the consumption concepts, consumer society, consumer, and leisure time have taken over. The social structure in which work, and production are built around have been taken

over by a novel capitalist social system that is based on leisure time and consumption. In the past, leisure time meant naturalism, freedom, and optional choice strengthens choice. However, following the transformations that have been seen in the landscape over the years, the term started to imply living an approved and consecrated life of capitalism, such as artificial excitement and consumerism. Leisure time sectors have become highly significant as an actor in capitalism through marketing the significance of itself and in the meantime agitating the depressive trauma in the community(Firat, Kutucuo, Saltik, & Tuncel, 2013).

For instance, shopping malls, solariums, sports clubs, and fitness centres, among others do not have permanent meaning although consumers participate or take part in events in them. Since these have been organised by commercial and fictional logic, they cannot create a sense of gratification. Even the industry of leisure time appears to serve various alternatives, and they have various senses, accentuating that good life implies good consumption. Every consumer ascribes a different meaning to different products and services(Hofstede, Hofstede, & Minkov, 2010). The same applies to the beauty industry, where there can be five different styles of consumptions ascribed to products.

2.6.1 Conspicuous consumption

People gratify their basic security as well as physiological needs by consuming different products and a variety of services. However, in any community, some would wish to impress others by splashing out and excessive consumption. At times, the priority of excessive consumption may be more than that of basic consumption. This form of consumption is referred to as conspicuous consumption. The conspicuous consumption concept became eminent at the close of the 19th century through a study dubbed “The Theory of Leisure Class.” Veblen (1992) notes that people in the first generation gained wealth through industrialization but continued with a modest life as opposed to those in the second as well as a third-generation where consumption started to be more, competing with production(Van Holm, 2014). The most critical issue in consumerism, though, is power, class, and status, which at times is aimed at making others jealous. People endeavour to compensate for variations in status through performing consumption styles that ideally belong to people with higher status (Veblen, 1992). People are also keen to keep on consuming conspicuously to be at the front stage of their status group. Research also shows that the behaviour exhibited by consumers is basically to intimidate others that wealth prescribes honour(Witt & Bishop, 2009).

2.6.2 Symbolic consumption

The unique characteristic that humans have different from other species is the basic needs that invoke their ambitious and objective fantasies, awareness of the value, and absurd thrills, all of which are ideally unattached from the biological basis. Symbolization requirements and the function of creation of symbols exists among basic human habits, such as looking, feeding, mobility. Symbolic consumption subsumes evaluation of products based on their purchase, value, and consumption. Consumers love to be particular regarding the characteristics of their desires and needs or to communicate through consumption.

These product aspects are symbolic and are referred to as symbolic or extensive self-completion (ref). Consumption has a symbolic aspect, and consumers would love to communicate some regarding themselves through gaining from the symbolic characteristics of consumption (Firat et al., 2013). Products and services serve as objects that can represent what a consumer can become and what a consumer cannot become.

2.6.3 Addictive consumption

This classification refers to the forms of consumption that are associated with addictive products or services such as drugs. Although addiction normally associated with illegal substances, it subsumes any form of service or product that can be consumers to overcome issues or gratify a need that is attached to an extreme value(Firat et al., 2013). Another significant issue in this field is increasingly prevalent internet addiction. Since some of those who are addicted because of the internet tend to consider the virtual world and life to be more important and of greater value than the real-life, this form of addiction is highly harmful.

2.6.4 Compulsive consumption

Some of the consumers feel obligated to shop as though they were born to do that. Compulsive consumption highlights a form of over-consumption and repeating that takes place due to anxiety, boredom, or sometimes depression of consumers. Shopaholics, as they are at times referred, lean on overconsumption in the same manner that alcohol addicts do. For instance, a lady with an over-consumption issue may purchase more than 2000 hairgrips but fail ever to use them(Firat et al., 2013). Reports show that more women depict this disorder as opposed to men. While men tend to lean towards products such as vehicles, guns, electronic equipment, women show a preference for clothing and cosmetic products that will enhance their interpersonal relations. Both men and women may not have proper control when they are over-consuming, just like in any situation of addiction. Products that are

mostly related to over-consumption include cigarettes, alcohol, diet coke, and chocolate(van Doorn, 2016). In over-consumption, the behaviour is mostly not by choice, pleasure occurs because of shortness of the duration of the behaviour, and people exhibit a sense of guilt or regret shortly after the habit of consumption.

2.6.5 Shared consumption

Generally, the activities of consumption seem to create dual opposition such as good and evil. One of the critical dual opposing characteristics in the activities of consumers is sacred and non-sacred forms of consumption. The unique feature in sacred consumption is that it comprises products as well as services that are served with some level of great awe and respect. The consumption may be associated with religious connotations or not, but most of the time, people tend to respect the fact that holy elements are involved. The consumption has amalgamated with the consumer experience.

Sacred people, events, and people are created from the not so holy regions but filled with sanctity. For instance, theme parks serve as a new form of producing fantasies that include sanctity in many respects. Consumers from all parts of the world consider Disneyland as a pilgrimage. Some many products and services are presented with a sanctity spirit to sanctify consumption(Firat et al., 2013). Therefore, it serves to normalize the habit of spending money and assists to complete the consecration process.

2.6.6 Experiential consumption

To live in the current age that is full of new advancements and various products has been equated to living in a consumerist society. Although the initial industrialization factors have led to an unprecedented abundance of material, researchers still hold that these advantages have come at a high cost. A significant point of concern, then, is how these costs, actual and psychological, can be reduced. The fields of experiential purchasing, as well as experiential consumption, have gained the attention of researchers over the recent past as businesses seek to understand what provides optimum happiness and satisfaction to consumers (Gilovich, Kumar, & Jampol, 2015; Ulusoy, 2016; Walker, Kumar, & Gilovich, 2016).

There is now mounting evidence from research that there are myriad forms of consumption beyond the preferences of brands and consumption behaviour(Ulusoy, 2016). Such evidence better mirrors the fact that the phrase “to consume” can be elucidated in myriad ways: to spend, to use up, to spend wastefully, to devour, to absorb emotional faculties, to incorporate, or even to process in entirety. These variations give a taste for the diverse nature of consumption and conjointly point to the importance of assessing the

dimensions of experiential consumption: the experience of consumers when they use, consume or possess offerings from the market.

Studies founded on the notions implicit in the experiential domain have focussed on aesthetic products and the emotional processing that emanates from a desire for these products (Chang, Stansbie, & Rood, 2014). Prior research has identified eight major forms of human experience, some of which are associated with market offerings (Lofman, 1991). In addition to that, some scholars have ventured into an exercise to contrast two main emotion typologies (Gilovich et al., 2015). As such, some have looked at experiences that spur strong emotions and feelings. There is still a need for more research to gain a better understanding of the distinctions in experiential consumptions in various settings and different market offerings.

The hedonic or instrumental differentiation in the behaviour of consumers in literature is founded on psychological theories, especially those from the humanistic school of thought hypothesize a dichotomy in sensational perceptual states (Firat et al., 2013). As initially theorized, the behaviour may be motivated by either extrinsic or intrinsic factor (Reiss, 2012). Whereas external motivation spurs consumption as a way for achieving the end, intrinsic factors underlie consumption at the very end itself or what is referred to as hedonic consumption.

Various forms of perception have been contrasted by past and current researchers. In secondary auto-centricity, scholars note that the perceive objects in the form of uses or needs, thus engaging in approach-avoidance and problem-solving traits. On the other hand, allocentric perception involves the complete absorption of the perceiver in a particular object. Maslow's analysis compares two forms of cognitive activities: the first is cognition, followed by b-cognition. Cognition entails contrasting, making judgements, and evaluation (Reiss, 2012). On the other hand, b-cognition entails experiencing the object in its entirety, save for its specific purpose. Maslow's theory on being-psychology is based on ends and not means, for instance, end-experiences.

In a review of the literature on psychology, Tellegen suggested principal variations between what he called experiential and instrumental sets. The latter refers to states of readiness to engage in planning activities that are active, voluntary, and realistic to realize certain goals (Jamieson & Loi, 2014). On the other hand, experiential set refers to a receptivity state allowing a consumer to go through various experiential events, sensory that may take place, with a tendency to rely on what the experiences, as well as objects, represented by themselves.

In the 80s, researchers started to query the premise of rational consumer and theorize that consumers engage in both emotional as well as cognitive processing (Drolet & Wood, 2017). Scholars have differentiated between utilitarian based behaviour and pleasure-seeking consumer behaviour that

depends on hedonic values. In addition, researchers have concentrated on the hedonic form of consumption as a unique field of study (Drolet & Wood, 2017; Firat et al., 2013). An experiential perspective for customer behaviour has been proposed as an alternative to the purchase making or an information processing approach. Consequently, researchers have developed a framework that subsumes value, emotion, cognition and holistic-intuitive states of mind in experiential consumption.

The thought emotion, and activity value model comprises of all consumption forms, even the implicit ones proposed by the cognition and affect behaviour satisfaction model. Every construct in the thought, emotion, and activity value framework – there are four of them – is a protracted conceptualisation of the various constructs in the cognitive and affect-based approach. In these approaches, thoughts subsume dreams, daydreams, and imaginations. Emotion comprises of the various forms of expressive traits, feelings, or physiological reactions (Drolet & Wood, 2017). The activity comprises both mental as well as physical events that relate to both actions as well as reaction. The value comprises the evaluative judgments in consumer consumption.

These models present the experiences of consumption as intricate processes and interdependencies among the constructs is proposes hence non-linearity. In essence, scholars endeavour to paint two contrary scenarios of consumer behaviour, though not necessarily opposing ones. One side of scholarly work – instrumentally based – presumes a rational solver processing information by following the decision-making method that gratifies a unique need. The second aspect is a hedonic orientation where consumers are experiential beings who purchase or rather consume products for the very reason to enjoy (Firat et al., 2013). Collectively, theoretical and empirical research shows that the consumer is both hedonically and instrumentally motivated, implying that experiential consumption may fall under the classifications of majorly hedonic, majorly instrumental, or a blend of the two sides.

The assignment of brand references within the conventional beauty industry is a rapidly dynamic marketing communication area in its sophistication and scale (Bigné, Mattila, & Andreu, 2008). A lot of past studies in the area had conceptualized beauty industry marketing as promotion and directed on assessing the attitudes, brand recall, and purchase intentions of consumers in response to brand exposure (Bigné et al., 2008; Gilovich et al., 2015; Srinivasan & Srivastava, 2010). As such, the experiential approach is considered to be the next rational stage in the demands of consumers, beyond goods, commodities, or services (Srinivasan & Srivastava, 2010). The experiences offered to consumers may be the same as those offered by other consumers. However, integration is highly personal. For instance, one consumer may desire to use a luxury beauty product to lift his social reception, yet another may purchase the same product because of passion for the product.

Experiential marketing leads to the accumulation of memorable accounts. The consumer dotingly remembers the memorable accounts, and even shares these memories with their family members and peers. In turn, this generates an increase in sales through the power of consumer loyalty and word of mouth. In turn, this leads to the generation of more sales for the business while a deepening of the experiences for the consumers with each interaction (Hackley, Tiwsakul, Birmingham, & Chulalongkorn, 2006). Experiential customer relation necessarily involves the participation of consumers and addressing the needs of consumers as per consumption categories, considering the socio-cultural context. Therefore, experiential consumption involves more than needs and wants, but it also involves social goals, self-image, values, dormant emotions, and desires among consumers that are deeply ingrained.

The specific nature of consumer experience, which is unique for every customer, at a specific location and time, and limited to specific events, limits the managerial significance of planning as well as control purposes. Many organisations treat customer experience management as an alternative to customer relationship management. However, this succession is not left without integration challenges. When putting luxury brands or products from the beauty industry into considerations, trying to give an elucidation based on traditional marketing alone is insufficient. A detailed assessment that subsumes experiential marketing is needed. On the foundation of this concept, researchers and myriad forms of businesses have conducted studies for brands such as Hermes, Shoyeido, Toraya, and Louis Vuitton. There was also another research on CHANEL, a luxury brand, that points out the perceptions of consumer experiences (Hawkins & Mothersbaugh, 2010; Peter & Olson, 2009). These and other studies show common features in the luxury and beauty industry.

In a review of customer experience studies in the luxury and beauty industry, it emerges that the representation of luxury through the design of products, that is logo and package, that a brand adopts can assist consumers in identifying the brand. Brand image is important as it assists consumers in induce specific feelings as expressed by the consumer (Han, Nunes, & Drèze, 2010). Innovation is paired with the functionality of the product based on the story of the brand, and changes in the behaviours of a consumer are involved as they originate in the luxury brand. A specific sense of camaraderie and connection among consumers who associate themselves with the philosophy of beauty or luxury brands leads to the development of a special social group (Hennigs, Wiedmann, Behrens, & Klarmann, 2013). These are mutual factors in the beauty and luxury brands. There are specific factors that characterize luxury brands, and when they are all there, the status of the brand may be achieved.

Common factors in beauty brand representation include sense, feeling, thinking, action, and relationship. Sense involves identification of luxury brand as per its logo, package, and any other design aspect. Feeling involves the inducement of specific feelings through the image of the beauty brand. Thinking

comprises the pairing of innovation with the function of the brand based on the story of the beauty brand. Act entails changing the behaviour styles of consumers that originate in the beauty brand (Fionda & Moore, 2009; Song, Hur, & Kim, 2012). Relating, on the other hand, involves the formation of a social group based on the special sense of connection and the strong camaraderie existing among users who associate themselves with the beauty or luxury brand philosophy.

Further assessment of consumer experience shows that consumers can take part in the creation of experience in two main ways, namely active participation and passive participation. In the active participation, consumers are part of the experience that is created (Potts et al., 2008). This can be illustrated in a theatrical production where the audience is asked to provide their views on what should happen in the next episode or performance. After that, the responses of the audience chart the way forward for the next episode. In passive participation, the director determines the end of a continuum for an episode (Potts et al., 2008). The connection with the experience can also be used to characterize this dimension. Two critical sides of the connection include the absorbent and the immersive.

2.7 Conclusion

Despite the lack of information on customer relationship management with regards to the U.K. beauty industry, this literature review brings out critical information with regards to theories, practices, and trends within the sector in the U.K. and elsewhere. With projections showing that the U.K. beauty industry is bound to grow, by leaps and bounds. Consideration of best practices with regards to CRM will ensure that beauty firms can emerge successfully, having differentiated themselves in the highly competitive and concentrated market.

From the literature review, it is understood that in the beauty industry, customer retention depends upon two factors, customer satisfaction and loyalty and the effort made by the staff. It can be seen that the staff plays a crucial role in ensuring the satisfaction of customers and thus keeping them loyal to the organization. Customer satisfaction and loyalty depend on various factors like quality of service, offers and discounts, unique products and services, pricing, offers and discounts along with friendly behaviour of staff who are skilful in their work. The factors ensuring customer retention can be listed as below.

Figure 1: Factors ensuring customer retention

Source: (Author, 2020)

The impact of CRM strategies has also been discussed in great detail, with the emphasis being laid on the fact that CRM strategies lead to consumer retention and loyalty. Different models of consumer loyalty exist to elucidate the intricate relationship, with propositions for firms to devise loyalty programs, which are differentiated well enough to influence the behaviour of consumers. Importantly, the literature review compares practices in the beauty industry in the U.K. with trends in the beauty industry in countries such as Japan, China, America, and other markets, citing examples that are critical to the success of firms in the U.K. market.

3 Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The methodology is key to any research as it provides the blueprint for data collection and subsequent analysis. More specifically, research methodology refers to the specific techniques or procedures useful in identifying, selecting, processing, and analysing data concerning a certain topic (University of Witwatersrand, 2018). In actual research, the methodology part makes it easy for the reader to evaluate the overall reliability and validity of the study. Research methodology section provides answers to two major questions, namely: How was the data collection done? How was the data analysed? On this basis, this section of research outlines and justifies the methodology used in the study.

The methodology was decided in light of past studies with empirical findings justifying the methods used. Notably, Hajikhani et al. (2016) served as a guide for this study since they conducted similar researches where workers, as well as consumers of a service, were involved as participants in assessing the impact of customer relationship management on the loyalty of consumers. While there are slight methodological differences between this study and the studies used as a reference, the underlying structure and principle bear numerous similarities as elucidated in the sections below.

Before delving into the research methodology in detail, certain research questions need to be answered. Research, by definition, refers to a systemic inquiry to describe, explain, predicting, and controlling the phenomenon to be observed as informed by the study topic (Bryman, 2012). There are four main forms of research, each having a specific purpose: basic research, applied research, evaluation research, and action research. The study has adopted basic research, a descriptive research design in understanding and explaining a phenomenon (Isaac & Michael, 1971) which could help gain better knowledge on the contributions made by CRM to small and medium enterprises in UK beauty industry. Basic research helps in the development of knowledge or theory, and this case about the connection between customer relationship management and customer retention in the beauty industry. The method is best suited to understand factors that are not of immediate use or directly applicable (Edmonds and Kennedy, 2016), as in the case of the impact of customer relationship management on business growth to the industry. This research method will help the current study to increase the knowledge base of small and medium enterprises in the UK's beauty industry concerning the contributions made by CRM towards customer loyalty and retention.

3.2 Research Philosophy – Positivism

Research philosophy is very important as far as a research methodology is concerned. More specifically, research methodology can be classified based on three schools such as ontology, epistemology, realism, positivism, interpretivism, and axiology (Saunders and Loudoun, 2020). Research philosophy is significant in the sense that it consists of assumptions, which aid the researcher's view of the world. These assumptions subsequently assist in determining the research strategy

Of these, positivism is the philosophical method that best suits for studies that include observable social entities involving data collection (Al-Ababneh, 2020). The research on the contribution made by CRM to UK beauty industry will be largely based on observation of social entities and collection of primary data. Positivism enables a researcher to pursue a structured methodology to facilitate hypothesis testing. Further, positivism operates as a guide for quantifiable observations, which is then used for statistical analysis. The methodology followed while adopting positivist philosophy will be highly structured to facilitate analysis of hypothesis (Al-Ababneh, 2020). In this case, the researcher aims to test the hypothesis that CRM activities are largely helpful in retaining customer loyalty, which is crucial to the UK's beauty industry.

The method is also best suited for the present study as it will prevent any kind of manipulation during data collection as the data has an independent existence beyond the research subject. For example, in current study researcher will study literature on CRM, customer loyalty, customer retention, methods of CRM practised by the beauty industry, the importance of customer loyalty and retention in beauty industry etc. The researcher is conducting a case study of Panache beauty while the data collected applies to the industry as a whole and not solely about Panache. The data is further tested to check the hypothesis and to derive a theory about the industry as a whole. Further, positivist studies also espouse a deductive approach and concentrate on facts. Despite positivism being factual, there are certain disadvantages associated with the epistemological aspect of research philosophy. First, positivism depends on experience as a valid knowledge source.

Nonetheless, an array of important and basic concepts like cause, space, and time are not pegged on experience (Saunders et al., 2019). Second, adoption of positivism in business and other related studies is worth criticising for depending on the status quo: the finding of positivist studies is descriptive and lack in-depth analysis. It can be seen that the current study is solely based on the data collected from customers and employees of Panache beauty during a specific time frame. The data collected from another branch of Panache on another date and time might be different from the one used for the study.

This study has employed positivism research philosophy because the study at hand observes various phenomena in cosmetic CRM without altering anything about the phenomena. In line with the tenets of this philosophy, this research adheres to factual data that is obtainable through measurement and observation. In this research philosophy, the role of the principal investigator is limited to the collection of data and its interpretation (Burrell & Morgan, 1979), and that is what will be the case in this research. The study on the CRM impact on the loyalty of consumers of Panache depends on factual data obtained from primary data collection. The data collected is measurable and quantifiable, which further leads to statistical assessment. As such, the philosophy is key and conforms to the empiricist view that notes that knowledge stems from the experiences that people have (Crowther & Lancaster, 2009). In the present study, the relationship between CRM and customer retention in the beauty industry is largely dependent on the experience of customers and employees of the organisation. Positivism philosophy also bears an ontological, atomistic view that the world comprises of observable, discrete events and elements that interact in a regular, observable, and determined manner. It can be seen that the current study is based on the same principle, where the relationship between CRM and customer satisfaction and retention are elements that are discrete yet observable in nature. These factors interact regularly and can be observed and appropriately determined. It is also possible to document and quantify such observations which serve as the primary data for analyzing to conclude.

Furthermore, in studies that assume the positivist approach, there are few provisions for human interests when it comes to data collection. According to Pandey(2019), the most important rule in positivist research is the deductive approach as opposed to an inductive approach that is common to phenomenology philosophy. The current study has adopted the deductive approach, where the hypothesis of a positive relationship between CRM and customer retention in the beauty industry is tested. Also, positivism relates to the notion that scholars need to focus on factual information, while phenomenology focuses on the implications and has room for the interests of people (Crowther & Lancaster, 2009). It can be seen that the current study relies largely on factual information gained from customers and employees of Panache beauty. It is key to note that in this research, the researcher maintains independence from the research and that the findings of the study are ultimately objective. This implies that there is minimum interaction between the researcher and the research participants to ensure that the participants give factual information that can be considered objective.

In a study that assessed customer relationship management among businesses and marketing firms, the positivist approach was used (Hajikhani et al., 2016). Here the approach was considered as one that contends with the participants in different settings requiring interactional involvement of the investigator to comprehend the subjective implication of the phenomenon. The use of a positivist approach in the

CRM study allows social researchers to play a vital role in the data collection process. In other instances, though, the interpretivist approach has been employed with the principal investigators contending that it serves as the best approach to interact with the study participants (Wallet al., 2016). With this method, the researcher was able to interact with both the participants, the customers and employees, whose opinion is crucial to the research. The researcher plays a vital role in explaining the purpose and importance of the study to participants. This will help to make sure that the participants understand the questions properly and will be able to provide a proper answer for the same. Accurate information is critical for getting a genuine result from a study.

3.3 Research Design- Descriptive

The research design is the overall strategy chosen by a researcher to integrate different study components logically and coherently, thereby assuring effective address to the research problem. Accordingly, Sekaran and Bougie (2016) define research design as a set-up useful in deciding on data collection, analysis and interpretation with the final aim of providing a solution to the research problem. On this basis, there are various research designs with different settings such as action research, causal design, case study, cross-sectional, cohort design, descriptive design, experimental design, exploratory design, historical design, longitudinal design, meta-analysis, mixed-method design, observational design, intelligent design, sequential design, exploratory, explanatory design, and systematic review (Leavy, 2017). Despite such a plethora of research designs, this study is only interested in three designs, namely: descriptive, exploratory, and explanatory research designs. The reason behind narrowing on these is because they are the most applied in consumer relationship studies.

The exploratory research design is most suited to address a research problem, of which no earlier studies or few ones are available. The focus of exploratory research is to gain familiarity with and insights for future investigation or addressing research problem during the preliminary stages of an investigation (Cuthill, 2002).

Explanatory research is carried out in solving a problem, which is not researched well; thus, demanding priorities to generate operational definitions and provide a better research model. Explanatory research design focuses on explaining the study aspects of the details. The researcher begins on a general standpoint and uses the research tool to identify subjects to be investigated in the incoming future (Saunders et al., 2019).

Descriptive research design helps in providing answers to questions of how, where, what, when, and who in association with a certain research problem. As such, descriptive studies do no answer questions related to why. This is because descriptive research applies to obtaining information regarding the current status

through the description as guided by study variables (Anastas, 1999). In descriptive studies, the subject under investigation or observations is in the natural environment and, thus, they are considered true experiments with the data analysis being not adversely affected since the behaviours of the subject is not tampered with (Rahi, 2017). The research design is most suited for present research as the subjects observed are customers and employees of Panache beauty, and their opinions are true experiments. The data collected is related to their experience with Panache beauty which is not likely to have tampered, which in turn will not have any adverse effect on data analysis.

Additionally, descriptive research is a precursor to other quantitative research designs in providing valuable pointers to variables to be tested. The descriptive research design is more useful in conducting a focused study. It will hence help to gain valuable insights into the connection between customer relationship and the performance of the organisation. Using descriptive design for research aids in yielding rich data, this can be used to make important recommendations in improving studies or for practice in various disciplines (Given, 2007). The result gained from current research can also be used for developing ideas to conduct further studies in the area of customer relationship management in the beauty industry. Unlike exploratory and explanatory research designs, descriptive studies enable the collection of a large amount of data for facilitating analysis into details. However, results generated from descriptive studies cannot be applied to approve or disapprove research hypothesis. Since descriptive studies often make use of observational methods for collecting data, it is very difficult to replicate the results in similar research conducted (Rahi, 2017). This is because data collected for descriptive research is relative to other environments like, the respondents chose, time of research, market situation and other conditions under which research was carried out. There is no guarantee that another research conducted on the same method will be able to gain the same data as in the first study. For example, the present study has chosen both customers and employees of Panache beauty for data collection. While carrying out another research, the researcher might not be able to approach the same customers or employees for data collection, and this will certainly affect the results. Finally, the descriptive meaning of research highly depends on instrumentation to observe and measure (Leavy, 2017). Thus, analytical methods used for data analysis plays a crucial role in results obtained and when another research is carried out on the same topic using a different set of analytical tools is likely to generate a different result.

Within the context of current research, the descriptive study design is used to show the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable. Several studies assessing the effect of CRM on the loyalty of consumers have employed a descriptive study design (Sorayaei et al., 2014; Wali et al., 2016). Descriptive studies, which involve the gathering of data to describe situations and events, can elucidate the relationship between CRM strategies and the retention of consumers, and in the present

study the relationship between CRM and customer retention in the beauty industry. Often descriptive studies are also cross-sectional, implying that data is collected at a specific point of time. Data is usually collected using data collection methods like survey tools, such as questionnaires and responses, Likert scale questions, interviews etc. the results of which can be analysed to show the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The current study employs survey method using questionnaires and interviews. Some of the questions have used a Likert scale which allows measuring the attitude of respondents towards certain aspects.

Tiemo (2013) presents a descriptive study on CRM, its root and perceived sameness to relational marketing through extensive literature on marketing. The researcher has tried to provide a contrasting elucidation between relational marketing and customer relationship marketing with the hope of determining whether or not the two concepts are similar. The study notes some significant differences between two marketing concepts by exploring major theoretical underpinnings founded on the intellectual developments in marketing, and effective CRM processes were also highlighted as conceptualized from literature reviews. The various ways through which organisations and their consumers look at value was critically assessed through descriptive design. The study has been helpful to understand the methods in which customers and organisations are perceiving value, and this was helpful in data collection for current research. The questions, of both survey and interview, were developed keeping these methods in mind, and this was helpful to understand various perspectives on the importance of customer relationship management in the performance of an organisation.

Khan et al. (2014) have also employed a descriptive study design to assess the implementation of CRM in the service industry. Customer relationship in the service industry has grown to become a core issue for attaining competitiveness. Organisations prefer to invest in customer relationship management technology. In the study, researchers aim at assessing whether the implementation of CRM systems do spur success with or without consequent CRM factors. The study offers a descriptive analysis of the implementation of CRM and two significant factors: customization and consumer knowledge. Thus, through the descriptive approach, the researchers can attain their aim, which is to assess the level to which service firms can employ CRM technology, store knowledge regarding their consumers, and customise services. The results are useful in increasing organisational performance. The study was helpful to understand the importance of customization of customer relationship management and customer knowledge about the same. It also helped to identify the level to which Panache beauty has been able to employ CRM, their perception of customers and customer service provided. This was helpful in data collection to the extent that the researcher was able to generate data that can be analysed and

evaluated to reach a conclusion that could be used for providing recommendations helpful in increasing the performance of the organisation.

An assessment of descriptive design further justifies as to its inclusion in this study. Knupfer and McLellan (1996) note that descriptive statistics play a key role in educational studies, and hence, applicable in this scenario. Although descriptive studies do not fit neatly into the definition of either qualitative or quantitative methodology, they can be used at the same time in the same study. In essence, the descriptive nature of the research depends on the research questions or objectives, research design, and analysis applicable to a specific research topic. Descriptive statistics can provide complementary information for inferential statistics. Thus, it was based on research questions, objectives and research design that the current research chose descriptive method.

Some scholars are quick to dismiss descriptive studies or studies that have employed descriptive designs regardless of the novelty of the observations that are reported. However, in justifying the use of a descriptive approach, this study identifies descriptive studies as being valid and present results that are better than some other mechanistic studies lacking validity proofs of their experimental models. As such, non-descriptive studies are often given the benefit of the doubt based on rationalizations presented in opening statements. Observational study design, which is closely related to descriptive studies, is also critical because of its unbiased nature (Given, 2007). Sometimes, an important solution is missed owing to the fact that proper observation is not done. Disrespect for observational study design, just like for descriptive study design, is a recurring theme in scientific discourse (Anastas, 1997). But in thinking about new hypotheses and theories, observation methods should be used first. Direct observation is also important when testing new systems such as novel approaches in CRM or other modern tools that have come with the advent of modern technologies (Morgan et al., 2017). The researcher chose to use observation to ensure unbiased data collection and also after considering matters like novel approaches adopted by Panache beauty in their CRM practices.

Inferential statistics have been used in other studies assessing the relationship between variables where customer relationship management is the independent variable. In a study on the effect of customer relationship management and the attainment of competitive advantage in a tractor manufacturing firm, the researchers employed single sample t-test, correlation analysis, and multivariable regression to prove their hypothesis and arrive at their conclusions. Factor analysis, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were also utilized in assessing the perception of loyalty programs and the purchasing habits of consumers. Loyalty programs are embedded in CRM programmes. Chi et al. (2010) report their use of both descriptive and inferential statistics in assessing the relationship between CRM and loyalty of consumers in the banking sector. The specific techniques that the researchers use include factorial

analysis, structural equations modelling, and path analysis, which were availed by SPSS and (Chi et al., 2010). The data analysis tools for current research have been chosen after considering the nature of data obtained.

In an in-depth review of structural equation modelling, the literature shows that the method of analysis comprises a measurement and a path model (Popper, 2004). The path analysis or path model quantifies particular cause and effect associations between the variables observed. On the other hand, the measurement model quantifies connections between the hypothetical constructs that are linked to the known but the unobservable elements and the observable variables that stand for the actual hypothetical construct in a linear combination form (Lam & Maguire, 2012). For instance, in this study, the CRM variables and customer loyalty and retention variables can be included, CRM presumed to be the cause of loyalty and retention. These associations are considered to be based on evidence from other studies or theoretical underpinnings. However, there are specific conditions that have to be met for a research variable to be ascribed as a cause while another one is considered as the effect.

This is decided based on certain criteria like a functional relationship, time precedence, and non-spuriousness. First, for an element to be named as a cause variable, the variable has to proceed in terms of time. Thus time precedence means an asymmetric association between two variables. Secondly, the functional relationship should be present for there to have a cause and effect association. Third, if the association is spurious for any reason, mostly for a common cause, the relationship will disappear when the common cause is represented in the larger model (Lam & Maguire, 2012). A further review of the path analysis, though, shows that there is a need to shift from the conventional statistical analysis to a causal one.

A review of the significance of inferential statistics further justifies the use of inferential analysis techniques in this study to ascertain the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Studies note that descriptive and inferential analysis remains the most popular and essential methods of analysis in the assessment of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variables. Intricate methods such as time analysis, Cox regression and Cox regression with frailty are used in various studies and scenarios (Liu et al., 2010).

According to researchers, statistical methods may range from planning and collection of data to the methods used in interpreting as well as reporting findings in research. The statistical methods used in studies give meaning to the data and numbers, thus breathing life into data that would otherwise be meaningless. The findings and inferences are specific only if appropriate statistical methods are used (Ali & Bhaskar, 2016). Acquaintance with basic statistical tools and proper inclusion in a study enables the

researcher to understand the relationship between variables and find the place for qualitative data in MMR designs.

3.4 Type of Research: Mixed Methods

There exist two main approaches to dealing with a research problem: qualitative and quantitative research method. The quantitative research method is used in examining the correlation between study variables to analyse and represent the relationship mathematically via statistical analysis (Bryman, 2012). This research approach is mostly used to address scientific research issues. Quantitative studies provide data in a descriptive form enabling one to have a snapshot of the population. However, sometimes interpretations prove difficult.

Interestingly, it would be hectic to interpret the findings in the absence of statistically analysed data. Through sample size increment, the statistical significance or power becomes more meaningful. The limitation of quantitative studies is that they need a specialist to interpret quantitative statistics (Creswell, 2013).

On the other hand, the qualitative research method is employed when the researcher aims to engage in the examination, understanding, and description of a phenomenon (Creswell, 2012). To this end, qualitative research does not involve numerical analysis and representation in the form of statistics. This method is commonly used in social research in addressing various research problems coupled with studying ideas, human behaviours, beliefs, and research questions. Still, in this case, the relationship between the study, variables are not put into consideration. Whereas quantitative research method needs data collection standardization for easier statistical comparison, there is flexibility in the qualitative research method allowing the researcher to be responsive to user data based on emergence. Hence, qualitative research is naturalistic in observations using techniques like structured interviews or ethnography as opposed to statistical analysis in quantitative research; qualitative research only observes data trends (Creswell and Creswell 2017). However, it is quite involving as the person carrying the inquiry has to employ keen observation of identical statements, for instance, similarity across various research participants, in an attempt to identify trends.

The rule is the thumb valid: an anecdote is whereby the researcher collects data from one participant; a coincidence involves two respondents; and a trend is developed from three study participants (Creswell, 2007). The researcher is at liberty to either choose a qualitative or quantitative one based on the research problem and research questions (nature of the study). Alternatively, the researcher may opt to use both is a research study. This study will use mixed-method (the usage of both qualitative and quantitative

methods) since it combines the strengths of both two, leading to statistical analysis and interpretation of the represented data.

The researcher believes that, for this study, both quantitative and qualitative research is important in accomplishing the objectives and aims of a research endeavour. The quantitative study refers to data collection techniques and analytical forms that yield statistical/numerical data. For the current research, statistical data is collected by employing primary data collection methods like survey and interview. Qualitative research form, on the other hand, places its focus on the collection of data from individuals often related to the application of non-numerical response parameters. For this purpose, the researcher depends on interview method where questions on the research topic, that require details response, are asked to respondents. Creswell (2012), states that researchers normally use both quantitative as well as qualitative research methods to gain better chances of reaching their research objectives. In examining the impact of CRM in the beauty industry, the study uses a mixed-methods approach that subsumes both quantitative as well as a qualitative form of data.

The difference between quantitative and qualitative research is nevertheless abstract, quite general, and its significance is normally considered for granted (Allwood, 2012). Various arguments are considered in this methodology section regarding quantitative and qualitative research designs, including the heterogeneity of the various standpoints regarding the significant issues among researchers. Furthermore, the presence of significant overlap between the various features of quantitative and qualitative research designs is assessed to understand the distinguishing line. While being keen on assuming the overlap of features, quantitative research may be noted as research that can be analysed directly bringing out its findings in terms of numbers (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

In this form of study, participants provide their response to numbers or responses that can be coded as numbers. Researchers perceive quantitative research as the best research design that can get real data for purposes of business and marketing (Yilmaz, 2013). It has also been lauded as the easiest way to assess trends, discovering, monitor success, and validate ideas. In the present study, the researcher has used a Likert scale to generate quantitative data. Qualitative research, on the other hand, involves behaviour and exploration of thoughts (Barnham, 2015). It is mostly employed when researchers are looking to get a specific answer. Respondents usually have provision for giving their thoughts. While it is possible to transform the responses into quantitative data, the process is normally inaccurate and daunting; hence not a good option.

Mixed methods research has been shown to have made great advances in recent years. As a result of the efforts of researchers and methodologists, there is great comprehension of myriad issues, such as the myriad ways in which qualitative and quantitative research can be combined. However, at the same time,

the compound issue of the level to which mixed methods researchers genuinely integrate their findings has not been assessed to a significant degree. In other terms, the extent to which mixed methods researchers conduct their analysis, interpret their results and write their report in such a manner that the qualitative and quantitative aspects are evident is still questioned. This is what researchers mean when they use the phrase “genuinely integrate” (Creswell and Clark, 2018).

According to Brannen (2005), the various methods in which researchers conduct their studies lead to ambiguities, tensions, and, at times, dissonance. However, the essence of mixed methods research comes in as Brannen (2005) argues that mixed methods research illuminates the contradictions and complexities and hence researchers should not view the ambiguities, tensions, and dissonance as issues.

Adopting mixed methods research has also been justified by Browne et al. (2013) as they contend that mixing quantitative and qualitative data assists in refocusing inquiry from participants and offering intricate descriptions of phenomena under research. A discourse implying a further innovative direction for mixed methods research offered by Botha (2011) contends that mixed methods research may comprise a vehicle for engaging with contemporary research enabling reflection of the unique epistemology and its knowledge axes. Thompson (2004) provides another contribution noting that mixed methods research bears benefits that can be maximized by qualitative and longitudinal studies as the quantitative aspect brings meaning to the findings by the former types of studies. In combining qualitative and quantitative research, mixed methods research strategy indicates that there might be a need to develop mutual practices throughout a process of research.

Various CRM studies have employed mixed methods in assessing the impact and contribution of customer relationship marketing. In one study, mixed methods design comprising of qualitative and quantitative methods was used to assess the contributions of marketing by small businesses, regarding the adoption of technology in consumer information management and consumer communication (Browne et al., 2013). In another study, the application of mixed-method research design in the field of marketing was assessed. In the methodology of the study, a total of 34 mixed-methods studies, where data collection methods were implemented sequentially, were used and the findings were expected to provide researchers with guidance in identifying the right types of design (Harrison & Reilly, 2011).

Previous studies have shown that mixed methods offer an excellent approach to collect data for research through scholars need to address a few issues including priority and timing ascribed to each form of data and integration of the two forms of data. Some scholars argue that methodological issues brought about by mixing of study designs can be sorted out through Layder’s adaptive theory (Yogesh, 2009). According to Hewege and Perera (2013), these issues include design dilemmas emanating from the mixed methods approach and imbalance between structure and agency or what is often to as imbalance between

social structure and individual subjectivity. An assessment of the research methods used in customer relationship marketing shows that quantitative techniques are still in dominance. Still, a mixed-method research design is gaining precedence due to the addition of qualitative aspects of phenomena or research events.

Barnat et al. (2017) also offer a solution for the methodological issues highlighted in the methodological discourse by presenting rules that can be followed to get the most from MMR studies. The rules include offering potential benefits and limitations beforehand and elucidating the entirety of the study through conceptual frameworks that are backed by theory. Also, researchers are required to investigate and integrate the guiding role of theories in their studies (Barnat et al., 2017). As such, through the use of strict rules, while designing mixed methods studies and following what is referred to as the Layder's theory, studies can be designed to provide results that do not include any errors arising from methodological issues (Hewege & Perera, 2013). Some argue that a mixed-method research design still has myriad issues. Still, the use of the design in a judicious manner can always lead to a depreciation of limitation while ensuring that the studies can make the most from the benefits of mixed methods research design.

This research deals with primary data collected directly from the respondents as opposed to secondary data that comprises data collected from literature review or other sources of data that are not primary. Primary data are required for a specific research problem that is at hand and employs procedures that fit the question at hand best (Cheng & Phillips, 2014). Primary data may be employed for describing the historical and contemporary attributes, comparing research on replication of the original study, reanalysis, making a methodological advance, and learning or teaching (Hox & Boeije, 2005). On the other hand, secondary data is important when researchers need to assess a particular theoretical issue and compare the issue with existing information. Official statistics, records, and other accounts that are well documented may be employed as secondary data, but they are not void of characteristic problems such as locating and retrieval issues.

3.5 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Sampling methods provide a variety of techniques that allow a researcher to minimize the amount of data needed for a study by considering the needed data from a subset instead of all elements of a population. Although in the normal sense, the population is normally not used in sampling, this was not the case in this study as the research deals with both workers and customers. Thus, the research has made use of chosen elements of the target population who are relevant for the study. The target population has been identified as the customers and employees of Panache beauty.

A representative population is required to establish the effect of consumer relationship marketing on the loyalty and retention of consumers (Creswell, 2007). Properly selected sample enables the development of correct inferences in a study. Research methodologists refer to this as selecting an appropriate target population (Oluka et al., 2014).

Statistically, a correct population would be an entire cluster that can provide information that can be ascertained. In statistics, the population does not need to consist solely of people. Still, there can be a population of events, weights, or outcomes so long as the study defines the population clearly within inclusion as well as exclusion criteria. In choosing a population for research, the research needs to select a purpose and research question (Creswell, 2007). The population needs to be well defined to include or exclude the population of the study. For instance, if a study population comprises of consumers in a firm, it should be stated whether the consumers are repeat consumers or walk-in consumers (Ponto, 2015). As such, the use of the term population in scientific and social studies does not always correspond to the demographic description of the entire group of individuals living within a specific political or geographical boundary.

In this study, the population comprises of employees, managers, and consumers of Panache – the target firm. Thus, for this research, the population can be divided as those people who manage customer relationship at Panache beauty and customers who are affected or benefits from the same. It can also be said that, for this study, those who do not fall within the ambit of customer relationship management at Panache beauty, either as beneficiaries or as managers or those involved in the execution of the same, are excluded from the criteria of population.

The method of sampling is chief in enabling the attainment of needed response rate for the study. The sample population was decided based on probability sampling methods. Saunders et al. (2019) note that there are two forms of sampling: probability sampling and non-probability sampling. The probability sampling method is where the researcher chooses some members of the population based on certain criteria or randomly. This selection parameter ensures equal opportunity for the chosen population to be a part of the sample decided based on specific criteria. In this method, the sample population is usually selected from the larger population. In non-probability sampling, the chances of every case being selected from the larger population are not clear enough. Hence, it will be difficult for such a sample to answer every research question. This study uses both probability and non-probability sampling method for selecting a sample population. The probability sampling method used for the study is stratified sampling, where the target population is divided into subgroups that share similar characteristics. For the current research, the researcher divided the sample population into two main groups, the customers and employees of Panache beauty. The employees were further divided into two subgroups, managers and

employees who have direct contact with the customer. This method was chosen as it will facilitate representation from various subgroups related to customer relationship management at Panache beauty. To understand the impact of customer relationship management at Panache beauty it was necessary to get the feedback from customers and employees, and that too both managerial level and those who served the customers, of the organisation, which cannot be divided into equal sample size groups. Thus, the nature of the study required the stratified sampling method. The method is also effective to reduce sampling bias and thereby to improve the representativeness and accuracy of results.

Meanwhile, the non-probability researcher used a convenience sampling method for selecting a sample population from customers where the sample population is chosen based on proximity rather than representativeness. This form of sampling is defined by accessibility as far as inclusion of subjects is concerned (Saunders et al., 2012). This research is interested in the impact of customer relationship marketing for which convenience sampling is most suited as with this method researcher can easily reach out to sample population. The method is also effective as the researcher intends to collect primary data by handing over questionnaires to both workers and customers of Panache beauty firm. A total of 246 participants are included comprising six managers, 60 employees, and 180 consumers, which have been sampled in a proportion of not more than 30% as compared to the total population of the firm representatives and consumers of Panache. The study uses a 95% confidence interval and a sampling error of 3%. According to Nulty (2008), the expected responses from the study will be 82% of the participants enrolled in the study. This study importantly considers the number of participants it enrolls as studies state that if that is not considered, sample bias and sample errors are likely to occur. This implies that results obtained from sample population are not likely to indicate the case or situation of a population since the participants may differ from those who did not participate in a systematic manner (Nulty, 2008). With this representative population, this study can assess the development and implementation of the CRM strategy and the impact on consumer retention and loyalty. The data sources are as illustrated below:

Table 1: Sample population chosen for the research

Data Source	Sample size
Employees	60
Consumers	180
Managers	6
TOTAL	246

Source: (Author, 2020)

Various CRM studies have used different numbers of respondents in their assessment justifiable by the wider population they are dealing with. For instance, a study assessing the impact of CRM on the retention of consumers used a sample size of 350, comprising solely of consumers (Alipour & Mohammadi, 2011). In another study, information was collected from 180 participants serving as employees of a firm where the effect of CRM on the satisfaction of consumers was being assessed (Hassan et al., 2015). In a study assessing the use of social media for CRM, participants included members of the marketing team. The members of the marketing team were experts in public relations, communications, and studio management. The public relations team selected were able to provide the needed information to elucidate the impact of CRM (Julian, 2012). In all these studies it is evident that the researchers carefully sample research participants and apply inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure that the information that they report is a representative and actual representation of the impact of CRM. The same method is used in the current study, where some customers were chosen randomly. In contrast, others were selected based on the frequency of visits, distance from the facility, their likeness towards Panache, the number of beauty treatments they perform etc. The employees were chosen based on their understanding of customer relationship and its effect on customers.

The sample has been defined as a finite subset of respondents drawn from a larger population (Bryman, 2012). In turn, the selected population corresponds to the selected team and the needs or interests of research. Based on the findings received from a sample, investigators can draw their conclusions regarding the target population with a specific confidence level, following a method referred to as statistical inference. Even when the sample population comprises fewer of respondents than the minimum number recommended the study will be able to maintain its representativeness and the statistical inference will also remain accurate in terms of precision and the power to detect correlation or any association that may still prevail. On the other hand, studies with samples that are not representative may not be able to serve as a reliable source to make inferences and conclusions regarding the reference population. Thus, statistical inference may not be possible or accurate (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Lack of representativeness can come as a result of sampling bias or when the probability of denial or non-participation in the research is linked to the non-response bias. The strength of the sample population in this study is limited to 246 respondents. The respondents include 60 employees of Panache beauty, six managers and 180 customers who agreed to take part in the data collection process. One of the factors considered while choosing respondents was their ability to understand research purpose and answer accordingly. Those who were not able to understand the concept of customer relationship management

at Panache beauty were not included in the data collection process. All the employees of the organisation took part in the data collection process.

Further literature shows that it would be advisable to conduct a census-based survey, but various reasons including budgetary limitations, ethical issues, logistics, time restrictions and unknown target population size prevent studies from doing so (Banerjee & Chaudhury, 2010; Draugalis & Plaza, 2009) and the same was the case with the present case study as well and of this time restrictions and unknown target population size limited the number of respondents these reasons explain why samples are mostly used rather than carrying our survey on entire populations.

However, studies caution that there is a need to ensure that the results are not affected by sampling error or random error. This study has made all efforts to make sure that the sample is representative and to ensure that it will not lead to sampling error (Santin-Janin et al., 2014). The sample selected in this study may not be similar to the sample in other studies. Still, the numbers are well within range, and the literature supports them on sampling as the scholar's state that the sample depends on the larger population. The research is also convinced, based on the above literature, that selecting samples from every cadre – employees, managers, and customers – serves well as the perceptions and information of all the categories are to be represented. Finally, the representative population is to be keenly considered with an appropriate sampling procedure. During the collection of data, it is also expected that the response rate must be adequate to meet the required threshold and hence ensure that the inferences made are correct.

3.6 Data Collection

There are different ways to collect data while carrying out a research inquiry. They subsume, but are certainly not limited to, use of questionnaires, key informant guides, focus group discussion guides, observation checklists, recording devices, and photographing devices, among others. Data collection methods are developed based on their appropriateness and applicability in achieving the objectives and aims of a study (Püsküllüoğlu et al., 2014). Thus, careful selection of data collection methods is called for to ensure that the quality of data is maintained. Data quality has to be maintained before, during, and after the collection process. It is, therefore, necessary to have robust plans for data collection in place. Data collection methods are of great importance because how information is collected a huge influence on the explanations that the information can generate.

The various methods of collecting data have their advantages as well as limitations. Questions in the format of questionnaires or surveys are important as they can obtain both quantitative as well as qualitative data through close and open-ended question formats. Open-ended questionnaires are important for documenting attitudes, perceptions, beliefs, or knowledge within a vivid, predetermined

sample population, in the present case, the customers and employees of Panache beauty. Qualitative questions should be clear enough to yield coherent responses across study participants, yet broad in a manner that can invite a spectrum of responses (Paradis et al., 2016). The use of questionnaires in research is advantageous as it facilitates the collection of a large amount of data at a relatively low cost over a short period (Ackroyd, 1981). Also, any researcher can use questionnaires, hence, not limiting based on education level. In addition to the above benefits present study chose to use questionnaires for data collection as the results obtained can be easily and quickly quantified. Nonetheless, the use of questionnaires is limited to the level that the feedback obtained will be very short in the case of online questionnaires (Popper, 2004). Moreover, the respondent will not be able to convey emotions and feelings in addition to some questions being difficult for an appropriate response.

Interviews are important in collecting information from single individuals in a one on one session, through the use of a pre-made set of questions or areas of interest (Popper, 2004) and for present research interview questions were asked to six customers, who also took part in the survey. The customers were asked about certain aspects like quality of service, offers and discounts, the expertise of staff etc. that needed details answers. Six customers, who were frequent visitor the facility was chosen for an interview to know about their experience at Panache beauty. The interviews were transcribed or recorded after seeking permission from respondents. The interviews were structured and followed a strict script, a set of ten questions (Appendix B) that prod interviewees to express themselves in a free manner. Interviews are important when employed to document the accounts, stories, or even perceptions of participants and in present research interviews helped to understand the perception of long-term customers about the service given by Panache beauty. This was very crucial in understanding the customer relationship aspects and its connection to customer retention at the facility. Interview data was further employed to generate theories as ten study questions used in surveys were employed in the interview. Interviews were conducted to generate responses that are richer and more in-depth as compared to surveys (Paradis et al., 2016). Further, interviews are flexible and allow face-to-face communication between the researcher and respondent, and there is sufficient availability of information. However, the negative aspects of conducting one-on-one interviews are that they are time-consuming, costly, and the interviewer may be biased (Ackroyd, 1981). The researcher was able to overcome these issues by conducting interviews over the phone directly with the customers.

Observations gather data in situations through the use of basic senses, including vision, touch, hearing, and smell. Observations allow researchers to investigate as well as document the behaviours of respondents and attempt to understand why they engage in such habits rather than focus on the recollections and perceptions. Observations are important when employed to documenting,

understanding and exploring the phenomena as they occur (Paradis et al., 2016). The number of observations needed depends on research questions and methodologies of study. The present study has made use of observations to understand the behaviour of employees towards customers and the response of customers towards CRM practices of Panache beauty.

Content analysis and textual analysis are ideal when researchers use them to investigate the changes in organisational perceptions on particular topics or to document the context of specific practices. Researchers can use textual analysis as their main method in a study or as a method to contextualize the findings from other methods. The number and choice of documents depend on research questions, but they can also subsume documents such as government reports, research articles, protocols, organisation policies, and meeting notes among others (Paradis et al., 2016). In the present study, research questions acted as a guide for the development of a scheme or codes grid for content analysis. The questionnaires for interview and survey were developed based on textual analysis conducted as part of the research. However, textual analysis is not considered as the main analytical method as it is not sufficient to answer the research question.

3.6.1 Primary data Collection: Questionnaire and Interview

In this study, questionnaires and interview schedules are used to gather information from the sample population identified for the study. A standard survey tool, including demographic information and Likert scale questions, was designed. The scale was derived widely from the literature review on CRM in the beauty industry, followed by a pilot analysis. Researchers have also used questionnaires in examining the effects of customer relationship management on the performance of marketing teams (Oluka et al., 2014). Through the use of questionnaires, the study revealed that CRM does influence marketing performance (Namjoyan et al., 2013).

The literature on research instruments credit questionnaires as being one of the most common tools used the other being interviews. Questionnaires can be issued in various forms, mostly as self-administered or researcher administered (Sorayaei et al., 2014). In this case, the questionnaires were self-administered. Various types of questions were included in the questionnaire, including the questions on demography, Likert scale questions, and other questions that represent the variables of the study. The reader must understand the contents of the questionnaire to provide relevant responses. The significance of assessing the consistency and accuracy of study instruments, particularly questionnaires referred to as reliability and validity, respectively, have been published in various studies. However, the measure may not be popular in some regions. In this study, though, after the pilot study, the validity and consistency of the study were undertaken.

Questionnaires can be issued in printed form or digital format that can be issued through email or other electronic avenues. Internet-based applications such as Survey Monkey or Google Forms or a combination could be employed, offering participants the choice of the preferred method. The more advanced mobile data collection method has also been employed for CRM studies. Open Data Kit is cited as an on-shelf application that previously required individuals with programming skills. However, today, there are myriad open data kits available with off-shelf digital technologies that can be easily utilized in various environments. This study has made use of open data kit application to issue the questionnaire to respondents.

For the interview, six customers, who have been associating with Panache beauty for the longest span, were chosen. They were asked about various aspects of customer service to understand why they remain loyal to the salon. For a question on the uniqueness of services provided by the beauty salon, one of the respondents said that the beauty treatment provided by Panache beauty does “wonders to her skin” and that she has been able to maintain her skin healthy through these treatments. Responding to a question on the expertise of the staff at Panache, one of the respondents said that “the staff recommends treatments based on the need of customer while considering their skin type.” She also said that their recommendations are so good and she never had any issue with the treatments prescribed by the staff. It was also understood that Panache offered a great discount to customers and intimated them through various social media handles. All the questions asked in an interview aimed at measuring the loyalty of customers.

Six theoretical constructs were considered in measuring the loyalty of the consumers: efforts of acquisition by the consumers, commitment, trust, consumer attitudes, the loyalty of the consumers (Segoro, 2013). On the other hand, the staff will be assessed based on CRM elements that they implement and the strategies they employ at Panache beauty. This will help to find out whether such methods employed have a positive impact on consumers. The constructs have been selected as per the review of literature on the topic of consumer loyalty and retention. The constructs, as well as their constituents, are considered sufficient to assess the impact of customer relationship management strategy on the retention of consumers in the beauty industry with panache being the case organisation. Of particular importance is that previous studies have used these constructs, thereby increasing the validity of measuring tools for this study (Punniyamorthy et al., 2011; Segoro, 2013). Thus, the measuring tools and constructs have been tried and tested in other areas and are now adapted for use in the current study.

Constructs are used in CRM studies, as evidenced by the literature. Constructs are used to build on the variables and dimensions of CRM. The constructs serve the purpose of developing hypotheses that are assessed for a relationship through CRM models (Bhat & Darzi, 2016). The data collected from

participants in CRM studies are thus assessed using statistical analytical methods like ANOVA to ascertain the relationship between various constructs used through models that define the application of each of the construct.

As such, the use of constructs is well documented in the literature, and the selection of the appropriate variables and constructs in this study is geared towards making the entire analysis process clear and verifiable. Further, through the use of constructs, this study aims to employ a common language through which the results of this study can be compared with the results of other studies. This study delineates constructs from concepts and models, as practised in other studies (Arthur & Villado, 2008). It can be seen that the use of constructs in assessing the role of consumer relationship management in the beauty industry is well backed by research.

3.6.2 Secondary data collection

As the name suggests, secondary sources are important in carrying out a literature review as well as documenting important parts of a study. The sources are referred to as secondary owing to the nature of the information. Secondary sources like books, articles, journals, and others are used for assessing the impact of customer relationship marketing in the beauty industry. Depending on various sources for secondary data collection was helpful in gaining critical information on the topic. Secondary sources will also augment the data collected from primary sources (Cheng & Phillips, 2014). Madsen et al. (2016) note that in studying fashionable management ideas and concepts, interpretative approaches that triangulate the general picture while employing secondary sources such as case studies and other surveys have been used. Secondary sources of data have their advantages and limitations. The most apparent advantage concerns the cost incurred towards conducting the secondary analysis. While there is a cost that is at times attached to gaining access to some datasets, these costs cannot be compared to what researchers may have to spend on conducting an actual field study. Also, the data that is availed online has normally undergone professional cleaning by those who usually provide detailed documentation regarding the collection of data as well as cleaning processes (Cheng & Phillips, 2014). This is a great approach to conduct rich studies, especially for individual researchers who may not have ready funding for conducting their studies. Thus, this research relies on reliable data published in various mediums like books, journals, articles, previous studies etc. regarding the relationship between customer relationship management and customer behaviour and retention. The study has made use of secondary data while preparing questions for primary data collection. Several secondary data sources were accessed online from online libraries, scholarly articles available online, Google books, online journals etc. The method also helped the researcher to save cost and time to a large extent and to have an in-depth idea on the

impact of customer relationship management practices on customer behaviour and performance of organisations in general.

Scholars who would rather spend time testing study hypotheses and deliberating various research approaches instead of collecting first-hand data from field or study sites can benefit from the plethora of data online (Cheng & Phillips, 2014; Hox & Boeje, 2005). The increasing access to online data encourages cross-connection and creative application of information from various data sources. For instance, research experts in hierarchical frameworks can integrate data from single surveys with aggregate data from various levels of administration in a community setup. The availability of such sets of data also offers statisticians with actual data to test novel models in statistics (Betini, Volpato, Anastácio, de Faria, & El Dib, 2014). Such analyses can also enable the identification of potential new interventions to current issues that can subsequently be subjected to tests in prospective studies. Intrinsic to the nature of secondary data analysis, the data in such scenarios are not meant to address specific research issues or test specific hypotheses. It is not unusual that some third critical variables were presented for the assessment.

Similarly, the data from secondary sources may not be from all the target population of interest or the locations of interest in the current study (Cheng & Phillips, 2014; Hox & Boeje, 2005), an issue faced by the current study as well. Another issue is that to secure the confidentiality of research respondents. Datasets that are available publicly lack some variables regarding the respondents. These variables may be critical in the purposed analysis, such as the area codes, race, sampling units, and specific ages of the participants (Betini et al., 2014). This can lead to residual confounding when the variables that are omitted are significant covariates to control for in the secondary based assessment. Measures have been taken to avoid such issues and to make sure that the confidentiality of respondents is secured and to choose participants considering variables that are critical to the research study.

Another significant drawback of the analysis of currently published data is that the researchers who are assessing the data are usually different from those involved in the process for collecting data. Thus, they are probably not aware of the study-specific glitches and important nuances in the process of collecting data. Sometimes, the volume of documentation is daunting, especially for large-scale, complex studies were done by government agencies, so researchers using the data miss critical details unless they are prominently laid out in the documents. Compendious documentation of critical information regarding the validity of secondary data by the provider of the data and capricious assessment of all relevant documentation by the researcher can prevent this issue. The researcher has used secondary data as a base to collect primary data to make sure that the study won't face such issues.

3.6.3 Material

One standard semi-structured questionnaire consists of both closed and open-ended questions, and the same format is followed in this research as well. The questionnaire is further automated and converted to suit open data kit format or XML format (Bandopadhyay, 2007). To ascertain the validity of the questions in the questionnaire, the researcher has sought expert guidance in the evaluation of the questions considered relevant to achieve the objective of the study. Furthermore, a pilot study consisting of 30 respondents was conducted, to test the data-gathering instruments, and data analysis frameworks. Insights from the pilot study were used to sharpen the research instrument and data analysis framework. XML questionnaires, just like the standard questionnaires, include a predetermined set of inquiries employed for collecting data. There are various formats of the questionnaire, such as social status, clinical data questionnaire, and occupational group questionnaire. The questionnaires are used to record information regarding and on specific issues and are aligned with the objectives of the study. The questionnaires are unstructured as they combine both quantifiable and qualitative data. In this context, the XML questionnaire comprised of both quantifiable as well as qualitative data.

In the context of social or commerce-based studies, questionnaires may be used in myriad survey contexts such as electronic, postal, face-to-face, and over the telephone. In situations where the questionnaire is sent through postal methods or electronic formats, they are referred to as self-completion questionnaires. Questionnaires that are employed by interviewers in this manner are at times referred to as interview questionnaires or interview schedules. They could be used from the research context that has already tested them, or they could be developed as novel data collection tools (Paradis et al., 2016).

These conditions thus warrant the need to conduct validity and reliability tests for the questionnaires. The application of ODK for the collection of research data is well documented. In one survey, open data kit was deployed by researchers, Coker et al. (2002), to conduct research among 300 farmers. The researchers randomly selected the farmers through stratified, proportional, and cluster sampling methods. In collecting data, the researchers employed HTC G1 Android-based smartphones equipped with the ODK application; a software that readily digitizes data in readiness for analysis, allows remote monitoring of the data collection in real-time, facilitates the data collection process and most importantly reduces the need for using paper-based questionnaires and hence reduces survey time and cost significantly.

The method has the potential for a significant impact on the process of gathering data in the future where study locations may be remote, and research budgets may be tight. ODK is part of the software suite made by researchers from the University of Washington who were exploring the application of

technology to enhance lives in developing nations. The questionnaires have to be written in XML format for them to be seen in the smartphones. XML questionnaire development can either be manual or automatic through the use of online interfaces. The software comprises of various programs including ODK aggregate and ODK collect. ODK Collect is installed in the data collection smartphones where the questionnaires can be downloaded to SD memory cards, hence enabling the technology to work even in the absence of connectivity.

The researcher chose ODK to collect as it allows users to develop questionnaires that are not only in a linear manner but also with a predefined logic system, also known as if-then, depending on the answers for the continuity of the questions. The program also supports the integration of GPS points, pictures, videos, sound bites, and barcodes as attachments to a data collection process as the foundation of the responses of the questionnaires. Then the data collected through the smartphone can then be sent through an ODK Aggregate tool hosted on a server through either Wireless internet or mobile internet. The other ODK tools in the suite include Validate, Manage, and Voice, but they will not be employed in this study. Literature records comparative technologies, including FrontlineSMS, RapidSMS, and GeoODK. The first two are web-based platforms that can be deployed for data collection through SMS messaging. However, the interface for these SMS-based platforms is more limited. The two methods, FrontlineSMS and RapidSMS, can be employed through mobile phones without requiring the installation of special software in the phones. For this reason, they need low hardware overhead and hence ideal for studies that need short forms with the provision of free questions across many research enumerators (Braun, Catalani, Wimbush, & Israelski, 2013). Studies that need longer answers to numerous questions and few enumerators together with a myriad of data forms, e.g. photos and GPS can benefit from the more adaptive ODK and EpiSurveyor. Advanced methods of collecting data such as ODK and EpiSurveyor employ the features availed through smartphones for more intricate question forms. They can easily manage a great volume of information that emanates from the data collection process (Bishop, 2017). While other features of data collection cannot be availed through the free version of the ODK application, only the free version was considered.

Once the questionnaires were developed and loaded on the ODK platform, the reliability of the questionnaires has been assessed using the Cronbach's alpha test. To achieve reliability, a pilot test was conducted on a homogeneous population of 30 participants conveniently selected. Finally, after completing the piloting phase, the questionnaires were computed for the assessment of reliability. Consistent with previous studies (Reynaldo & Santos, 1999; Taber, 2017), the baseline for the reliability test will be 0.7. On assessment, the data from the pilot study gave a green light on the appropriateness of the questionnaire.

Several scientific papers record subjecting questionnaires into a reliability analysis to ensure internal consistency. The use of Cronbach's alpha coefficient is, therefore, widely applied with results that range between 0.60 and 0.84 being considered reliable (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Validity is important as it assists in expressing the degree to which research measurements are able actually to measure what they purport or propose to measure. There are several varieties of this, including construct validity, face validity, criterion validity, and content validity. The validity can also be classified as predictive or concurrent validity. These tests for validity are further grouped into two: internal as well as external validities. In internal validity, researchers refer to the accuracy in the methods of measuring obtained from the study.

On the other hand, external validity refers to the accuracy of the measurement in obtaining from the sample of the study described as the reference population from which the research sample was derived (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Reliability, on the other hand, refers to the level to which the findings obtained in a study through a method of measurement and methodology can be replicated. Through this method of reliability testing, researchers contribute and prove the validity of their data collection tools. It is nonetheless insufficient to test for reliability (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Lack of sufficient reliability may arise from the divergence of instruments or the participants such as instability of the questionnaire or the attributes being subjected to measurement, which will consequently and invariably impact the validity of the data collection tool. There are three major forms of reliability: stability, equivalence, and internal or homogenous consistency (Oladimeji et al., 2015). It is critical to comprehend the difference between these three angles as it serves as a guide to the researcher on the adequate examination of the reliability of the data collection tool. Meanwhile, both Type I and type II errors were employed to measure external validity, and explanations will be provided in the results section (Banerjee, Chitnis, Jadhav, Bhawalkar, & Chaudhury, 2009). These are statistical errors that may emanate during the rejection of the null hypotheses when essentially the hypotheses should be accepted or accepting the null hypothesis when essentially the hypothesis should be rejected and ignored.

3.7 Procedure

Those included in this study will be referred to as participants owing to the fact that they will take an active role in responding to the set questions. Having purposely selected the management team and using non-probability sampling techniques to select consumers visiting Panache for their beauty treatment services, the research assistants will follow the due process of research to collect data. The research assistants, as well as guides who will be included in the research, will be expected to have the cognitive

capacity and an understanding of the topography of the case organisation. The participants will then be issued a self-administered questionnaire, preloaded into the ODK enabled devices that they will go through and, if they offer their consent, they will proceed to complete the questionnaire. The research assistants will be there to guide participants, on any technical aspect of the questionnaire, especially regarding the selection of options in the drop-down menu and flipping to the next page on the devices. The participants will also be assured of anonymity and explained the intended use of the data that will be collected. Proposed Analysis

The research data will be analysed through SPSS package version 22, for both descriptive and inferential statistics. In contrast, Likert scale data will be analysed using graphs to cross-check the accurateness of result. Frequencies, as well as standard deviations of data obtained from the staff and consumers of Panache beauty, will be generated. A correlation coefficient analysis will also be conducted in order to ascertain the relationship between the independent variable, customer relationship management, and the dependent variable, loyalty and retention in the beauty industry. Further, multiple regression analysis will be conducted to assess the effects of the independent variable on the loyalty of consumers and the dependent variable, in the beauty industry, through data from the case organisation.

Before the commencement of data analysis in SPSS, data will be classified according to the various quantitative or categorical variables. The measuring data scales are numerical, and they are classified as quantitative variables. Interval data is considered as scale variable, but nominal and ordinal data is considered as categorical variables.

The use of SPSS and other related software in the analysis of data in CRM studies is well documented. In one study involving 200 respondents, data were analysed through SPSS in order to bring out the relationship between customer relationship management; total survives quality and the loyalty of consumers in KFC fast food restaurant. Significant effects were shown through inferential statistics done through the software (P & Panjaitan, 2014). Data on the relationship between customer relationship management and organisational productivity, customer satisfaction, and customer trust has also been assessed through the use of SPSS where the researchers used SPSS version to apply the structural equation model (Yaghoubi, Asgari, & Javadi, 2017).

The actual analysis has also been elucidated in methodology sections of some papers, for instance, a study that assessed CRM and the loyalty of patients used SPSS version 20 to conduct cross-sectional as well as descriptive analysis hence showing that the relationship's significance according to the alpha level of 0.05 (Hajikhani, Tabibi, & Riahi, 2016). In sum, the use of SPSS in assessing CRM's effect on various dependent variables is common. In the same vein, this study finds justification in the abundance of literature on the use of SPSS for analysing the relationship in its methodology.

In the inferential analysis, the relationship between different variables and the subgroups of certain variables are compared with the dependent variable. Other studies have also used inferential statistics to examine and prove hypotheses that are set in the studies. Structural equation modelling, a form of multivariate analysis technique that is broadly general and robust from the families of multivariate regression owing to its precision, has also been used.

3.8 Hypothesis

Hypothesis refers to a testable position regarding the association between two or more concepts or events. There are two broad statements in a hypothesis: the null statement stated as H_0 , and the alternative statement denoted as H_a . The null hypothesis is mostly the one that researchers want to reject while the alternative one is the one that researchers would like to keep. The decision to accept or reject statements of hypotheses of the research are normally based on a 95% confidence interval or 5% level of significance ($P\text{-value} = 0.05$). The reasons for doing this is to avoid errors as much as possible. Qualitative data will be analysed thematically. Thematic analysis is the most common form of analysis used for qualitative data. Generally, the form of analysis is used to analyse data from interviews as well as other forms of collecting qualitative data such as the open-ended questions in the questionnaires in this study.

According to scholars, thematic analysis is important in identifying, analysing, and reporting themes or patterns that can offer meaningful insight that provides answers to specific research questions (Sutton & Austin, 2015). Additionally, this method facilitates research questions through offering an investigation of the interview data through two major points of view: the first point of view is the data drive perspective and a perspective that is based on coding in an inductive manner; the second way is from the research questions point of view to check if the data collected were consistent with the questions in the research and offered relevant and sufficient information.

3.9 Practical Issues

Practical issues during the research process will include understanding the data collection process and developing research instruments that will measure the identified variables accurately. Another practical issue is the training and practical use of SPSS analysis. The research shall assume a mobile data collection method in collecting quantitative data from the research participants. The proposed data collection method, which will make use of the Open Data Kit (ODK) system, which is designed and made available for researchers as open-source software, will require basic training on how to automate a conventional questionnaire into an XML questionnaire that can be then used to collect data through mobile devices (Jeffrey-Coker et al.,2010). Once again, SPSS training will be required to ease the task of entering data

and running both descriptive and inferential analysis. Specifically, training will be required on the type of variables that can allow multiple regression analysis and the interpretation of findings from multiple regression analysis.

While the ODK system is open-source and hence free for use, there are cost implications for training and acquisition of tablets that will enable the collection of data from staff and consumers visiting the Panache beauty shops in the U.K. (Heunis et al., 2014). In addition to that, the SPSS training will also cost money, with a statistician being preferred for the training that will equip the researcher with the necessary competencies to undertake the analysis process. There will be financial implications for the training.

However, suppose financing will not be forthcoming. In that case, the researcher will bear the costs of training for the two technical areas that require the acquisition of the right competencies, prior to undertaking the data collection and analysis endeavour. The problem of uncompleted questionnaires also presents a practical challenge to researchers. It is always advisable to see the best methods to sort out this problem before the process of collecting data starts. To sort this problem, research ought to consider the attrition rate. After the data is collected, every questionnaire should be scrutinized to exclude questionnaires that are not duly filed or completed.

3.10 Ethical Concerns

For the success of the research, the surveying team will issue an introductory letter to Panache beauty in the U.K. The letter intends to seek consent from the organisation and the participants. Every participant recruited into the study will be issued with a consent letter or read before any data collection work commences. The consent of participants will be obtained in writing, where possible, and verbally. Participants will be given guarantees of anonymity and confidentiality. Thus, participants will take part through their own volition, implying that they can opt-out of the study at any point without victimization. The participants' anonymity will be assured, and the findings of the study will be made available in the university library and through publication. Any identifying information will be deleted to maintain the participants' anonymity in any research outputs that arise from the study. The research will only be conducted once the consent letter is approved. Any consumer who is recruited into the study must consent to offer information, which will only be relevant for academic purposes. Data collected will be kept in a safe and lockable place and stored securely in accordance with the principles set out in the Data Protection Act, 1998.

The data will be used for the study's purpose and give management and industry experts some useful insights that emerge from the data. A number of studies cite to have used and followed the United Kingdom Data Protection Act. The act has reported a significant impact on studies, although that was

not its initial and primary purpose (Iversen, Liddell, Fear, Hotopf, & Wessely, 2006). It serves as a wide-ranging legislation piece that protects participants' fundamental right to privacy when personal data processing is taking place. Laws (Iversen et al., 2006) also require that the purpose of research be expressly stated to ensure that the respondents do not provide information that may be used for defamation or illegally in violation of their privacy and individual rights.

4 Chapter Four: Data Analysis

4.1 Introduction

The chapter presents the overall results of the analysis performed upon the data collected according to the methodology detailed in the above chapter. The data has been analysed in SPSS using different statistical analysis techniques and presented under various sub-sections. Furthermore, the study's findings have also been discussed in the chapter about past literature and other similar research studies conducted by different organisations.

4.2 Demographics and General Information of Study Participants

Demographic information has been added as part of the questionnaire to understand the characteristics of Panache Beauty's target population and target market. These characteristics include age, gender, race, ethnicity, occupation, marital status, education, profession, etc. (Stiles et al., 2008). It has been reported that people's buying habits and beauty treatment-related preferences vary according to their demographic characteristics (MDG Marketing, 2018).

In this regard, gender and age have been used to gather the study participants' demographic information to have accurate insight and understanding of the sample's characteristics under study. Further, general information is comprised of respondents' status of employment, whether they are a student, employed, unemployed, or self-employed. Similarly, other questions on general information comprise their distance from Panache Beauty, their duration of the relationship, and the frequency of visit to Panache Beauty to analyse and relate their behaviour with the beauty salon.

A total of 246 individuals participated in the research survey. Out of these 246 survey respondents, 190 respondents, making almost 77% of the total sample, were female, whereas only 56 respondents making almost 23% of the total sample, were male. This depicts that female participants were a lot more in number than the male participants. The proportion of male and female participants in the study sample shows that females are more beauty conscious and interested in salons and skincare in comparison to males (Table 01). This is in line with recent research conducted by Mintel, which shows that 72% of the total women in the survey visit beauty parlours or salon for professional care services while only 52% of men use such services. However, the research also showed that men also have a growing interest in such services (Mintel Press Office, 2012), which is quite observable with male participants in the study sample. The frequency distribution of gender is as follows:

Table 02:Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	56	22.8	22.8	22.8
	Female	190	77.2	77.2	100.0
	Total	246	100.0	100.0	

The survey participants' age distribution shows that most of them were young adults as 37.4% as they belonged to the age bracket of 26 – 25 years. Whereas, 21.1% of respondents fell between the age brackets of 18 – 25 years; 16.7% of them fell between the age bracket of 46 – 55 years, 14.2% of the fit between the age bracket of 36 – 45 years and only 10.6% of them were more than 55 years old. The respondents' age distribution suggests that most young adults, mostly visit beauty parlour or beauty salons because they tend to be more beauty conscious. These research results are similar to the research results of Jayesh & Pradip (2014), who showed from their research of Indian women that most of the females who go to parlours are young adults (Jayesh & Pradip, 2014; The Nielsen Company LLC, 2018). The frequency distribution of the age groups is as follows:

Table 03:Age Groups

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 to 25 Years	52	21.1	21.1	21.1
	26 to 35 Years	92	37.4	37.4	58.5
	36 to 45 Years	35	14.2	14.2	72.8
	46 to 55 Years	41	16.7	16.7	89.4
	More Than 55 Years	26	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	246	100.0	100.0	

When the respondents were probed regarding their employment status, most of them responded that they are employed as 119 participants out of 246 of total survey participants that are 48.4% were employed. Also, a major proportion of that 35.8% was self-employed, while only 39 individuals with 15.9%, were students. The research results imply that mostly employed women tend to visit beauty salons because they want to look good and presentable while at their work. The frequency distribution of the responses to the questions is given in Table 05 below:

Table 04:Status of Employment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	39	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Employed	119	48.4	48.4	64.2
	Self-Employed	88	35.8	35.8	100.0
	Total	246	100.0	100.0	

When asked about the distance of Panache Beauty from individuals' residence, most of them responded that it is between 2 – 10 miles of distance from their residence. Out of the total of 246 participants, 43.9% (108 individuals) responded that the distance is 2 – 10 miles between Panache Beauty and their residence, 35.4% (87 individuals) responded that this distance is more than 10 miles for them. Only 20.7% (51 individuals) answered that this distance is less than 2 miles for them. These results imply that distance was not the major factor that influences customer loyalty and customer retention because most of them have their residential places at some distance from Panache Beauty. The frequency distribution of the responses to the questions is given in Table 06 below:

Table 05:How far is Panache Beauty from your residence?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 2 Miles	51	20.7	20.7	20.7
	Between 2 - 10 Miles	108	43.9	43.9	64.6
	More than 10 Miles	87	35.4	35.4	100.0
	Total	246	100.0	100.0	

When asked about their duration of the relationship with Panache Beauty, most of the respondents that are 35%, seemed to have been associated with Panache Beauty for 1 to 6 months, and 26.4% seemed to have their relationship with Panache Beauty for more than one year. While 20.7% of total respondents have been a customer of Panache Beauty for less than one month, 17.9% of total respondents have been customers of the salon for 7 to 12 months. This shows that Panache Beauty has retained 65 of its customers for more than a year and 86 of its customers for 1 to 6 months providing high-quality services. The frequency distribution of the responses to the questions is given in Table 07 below:

Table 06:How long have you been a customer of Panache Beauty?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less Than 1 Month	51	20.7	20.7	20.7
	1 to 6 Month	86	35.0	35.0	55.7
	7 to 12 Months	44	17.9	17.9	73.6
	More than 12 Months	65	26.4	26.4	100.0
	Total	246	100.0	100.0	

Out of a total of 246 respondents, 43.5% (107 individuals) responded that they visit Panache Beauty on a fortnightly basis, whereas 37.0% (91 individuals) responded that they visit Panache Beauty very occasionally. Only 14.2% (35 individuals) visit Panache Beauty every week while 5.3% (19 individuals) visit Panache Beauty on a daily basis. The findings suggest that most of the individuals used to and liked to visit Panache Beauty on a fortnightly basis. In contrast, very a smaller number of people used to visit Panache Beauty either on a daily or weekly basis. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 08 below:

Table 07:How frequently you visit Panache Beauty?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
On a Daily Basis	13	5.3	5.3	5.3
On a Weekly Basis	35	14.2	14.2	19.5
On Fortnightly Basis	107	43.5	43.5	63.0
Very Occasionally	91	37.0	37.0	100.0
Total	246	100.0	100.0	

4.3 Customer Relationship Management of Panache Beauty (Independent Variable)

This section involves questions related to the different aspects of customer relationship management of Panache Beauty, that is how Panache Beauty has been striving to maintain a relationship with their customers, which is an independent study variable. The respondents were asked to record their responses upon a scale of one to five, where one shows strongly disagree, and five shows their strong agreement to the statement asked. The aspects of customer relationship management include staff behaviour and experience, quality of services, discount deals and offers for customer engagement, pricing of services and value for money, and suitability of services provided for the skin type of customers, which is

considered one of the most important aspects of customer engagement and customer relationship management in the beauty industry.

Vesel and Zabkar (2009) explained the importance of staff/ employees in an organisation, stating that employees hold a critical position in communicating and collaborating the organisation's values to customers and the general public. Therefore, it is necessary to communicate effectively and pleasantly with the customers in order to draw their attention and retain customer loyalty. In the case of Panache Beauty, the response to the question regarding sincerity and friendliness of the staff was positive. Most of the respondents (almost 30.1%) strongly agreed that staff at Panache is very sincere and friendly, and almost 17.1% agreed that the staff at panache is very sincere and friendly. Out of 246 participants, 24.4% of respondents answered that they are neutral, while 16.3% strongly disagreed, and 12.2% disagreed with the same. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 09 below:

Table 08: The Staff at Panache Is Very Sincere and Friendly

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	40	16.3
Disagree	30	12.2
Neutral	60	24.4
Agree	42	17.1
Strongly Agree	74	30.1
Total	246	100.0

Figure 2: Staff at Panache Is Very Sincere and Friendly

The customers interviewed were also happy about the behaviour of staff at Panache Beauty. All of them found the staff as friendly and caring. One of the respondents said that “some of the staff, especially seniors, is so good that they even remember customer preferences.” Another respondent said that the most favourable aspect of Panache Beauty is the friendly staff behaviour you cannot expect in several other rival organisations. Quality of service is the next most important factor while assessing customer relationships. By using three attributes, Zeithaml (1981) indicated from their research that the evaluation processes of different consumer goods and services differ. The goods and services are allocated high in search qualities, high in experience qualities, and high credibility qualities along with a continuum of evaluation ranging from the easy evaluation to difficult evaluation. According to his classification, the beauty services industry falls high in the experience qualities category, which means the experience of the staff providing services at the beauty salons is one of the most important factors in order to understand the needs of the customers in an effective manner and provide them with the services exactly according to their needs and maintain the relationship with their customers.

When asked about the experience and understanding of the customers’ needs of the staff of Panache Beauty, a major proportion of the survey respondents (around 47.1%) either agreed or strongly agreed that the staff was experienced and understood their needs and preferences very well. In comparison, 25.6% were neutral on the same. On the other hand, 27.3% either disagreed or strongly disagreed that the staff

at Panache Beauty is experienced in their jobs and understand their needs and preferences very well. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 10 below:

Table 09: The Staff at Panache Is Experienced in Their Jobs and Understand My Needs and Preferences Very Well

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	27	11.0
Disagree	40	16.3
Neutral	63	25.6
Agree	40	16.3
Strongly Agree	76	30.9
Total	246	100.0

Figure 3: Staff at Panache Is Experienced

All six customers who were interviewed believe that the staff are professionals with expertise in their field of operation. One of the customers said that the “staff always explains the pros and cons of each treatment so that customers can choose the best, which is not a common practice in other beauty salons.” Such attitudes show the professionalism and expertise of the staff at Panache Beauty.

Furthermore, another important aspect of customer relationship management in beauty salons is understanding the skin type of the customers and assessing their skins before using any type of product on their skin to avoid any negative reaction. A number of beauty experts have argued that skin type analysis is a vital part of providing professional facial or other treatments where their skin can be affected for which understanding of how to identify the skin type for the face, neck and décolleté and identify additional skin conditions and characteristics. It is considered part of a professional facial treatment where the therapist studies and assesses their clients' skin to determine the skin type and identify any conditions that might influence recommendations for immediate and future treatment. The interview participants were of the opinion that at Panache beauty staff is professionals when it comes to recommending treatments. One of the customers said that the “staff are so efficient that they can recommend beauty treatments by assessing the skin types of the customers.” Another one found it fascinating that the staff make recommendations based on skin conditions and the occasion for which a customer avails treatment. The survey respondents were also asked whether the staff at Panache Beauty assesses their skin before providing or recommending them any treatment and using any kind of a product (The Times of India, 2018). Among the total survey respondents, 43.6% have either agreed or strongly agreed that staff at Panache Beauty assesses their skin before providing or recommending them any treatment and using any kind of a product; while 21.5% were neutral on this and only 23.6% of the total either disagreed or strongly disagreed to the same. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 11 below:

Table 010: The Staff at Panache First Assesses My Skin Before Applying or Using any Product to Avoid Negative Reaction

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	25	10.2
Disagree	33	13.4
Neutral	56	22.8
Agree	53	21.5
Strongly Agree	79	32.1
Total	246	100.0

Figure 4: Staff at Panache has expert knowledge

The service sector, which was ignored during the traditional marketing era, was a key concern in the realm of customer retention, and it has been recognized that it is more critical in the business environment of today as customers demand quality services for them to be retained (Chase, 2013). In this sense, every organisational employee must present quality service and be endowed with the appropriate skills to respond to customer needs efficiently and effectively (Valmohammadi&Beladpas 2014; Tauni et al., 2014; Tu & Olsen, 2016). This is the reason that the quality of services is considered a very important aspect of customer relationship management, especially in the service sector.

Those interviewed were satisfied with the quality of services offered to them. However, two of the respondents said that considering staff expertise; Panache Beauty could increase the quality of services though it is better than all other competitors. One of the respondents said that of all the services, skincare treatments have the highest quality though she has never faced any issues due to low quality in any other segment like hair care.

In this regard, when asked about the quality of services provided at Panache Beauty, a significantly major proportion of the total survey participants (52.4% or 129 respondents) have either agreed or strongly agreed that the quality of services provided at Panache Beauty is excellent. On the other hand, 26.4% of the survey respondents were neutral about the quality of services provided at Panache Beauty. Whereas only a small proportion of survey respondents (21.4%) have either disagreed or strongly disagreed with

the statements that the quality of services provided at Panache Beauty is excellent. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 12 below:

Table 11: The Quality of Services Provided at Panache Beauty is Excellent

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	24	9.8
Disagree	28	11.4
Neutral	65	26.4
Agree	53	21.5
Strongly Agree	76	30.9
Total	246	100.0

Figure 5: Quality of Service is Excellent

Furthermore, an additional and one of the most important aspects of the quality of services provided at beauty salons is the suitability of the services for the clients' skin type. In addition, laws related to occupational safety also become relevant because of using different types of products with a diverse range of chemicals in it (Apostolico et al., 2015). Therefore, the clients of Panache Beauty were asked about the suitability of the services provided for their skin type. All the respondents, who took part in the interview, believed that Panache provided the best skincare treatment, and none of them has ever

experienced any issue related to the usage of low-quality products for treatment. One of the respondents said that the staff at Panache Beauty would never do service just because the client insists on the same. On the contrary, they would educate the client as to why he/she should go for another treatment and not the one she has asked for. This is one aspect that shows that the quality of service offered at Panache is exceptional and professional.

In response to the question, a significantly major proportion of the survey respondents (54.5% or 134 respondents) have either agreed (25.2%) or strongly agreed (29.3%) that the services provided at Panache Beauty suit their skin very well. On the other hand, 21.5% of the survey respondents were neutral about the suitability of services provided at Panache Beauty for their skin type. Whereas only a small proportion of survey respondents (23.9%) have either disagreed (14.6%) or strongly disagreed (9.3%) with the statement that services provided at Panache Beauty suit their skin. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 13 below:

Table 12: Services Provided at Panache Suits My Skin Very Well

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	23	9.3
Disagree	36	14.6
Neutral	53	21.5
Agree	62	25.2
Strongly Agree	72	29.3
Total	246	100.0

Figure 6: Services Provided at Panache Suits My Skin

In addition, the overall environment and atmosphere of Beauty Salons also matter a lot. It has been revealed in a study that a lot of females do not just visit beauty salons in order to get beauty services/ treatments of therapies. They also used to visit to relax and relieve their aches and pains via massage, promote a sense of well-being or simply as ‘time for oneself’ or ‘time-out’ from their daily routines. Therefore, they expect the overall environment to be very good, relaxing and free from any stress (Paulson, 2008).

In the case of beauty salons, it has also become a very important aspect of customer relationship management because females who find the overall atmosphere of beauty salon relaxing tend to visit it again to gain relaxation from their daily and hectic routines. This is the reason respondents were asked about the overall environment and atmosphere of Panache Beauty.

Those interviewed were of the opinion that they consider Panache Beauty as a gathering point, where they could get the beauty treatment done while relaxing and meeting with friends. Some of them come to the salon with friends at regular intervals and spends hours. For them, Panache beauty is more than a salon, and the reason behind this is the environment and overall atmosphere of the salon.

In response, a significantly major proportion of the survey respondents (54.9% or 135 respondents) have either agreed (22.4%) or strongly agreed (32.5%) that the overall environment and atmosphere of Panache Beauty is very good and relaxing. On the other hand, 26.4% of the survey respondents were neutral about Panache Beauty's overall environment and atmosphere.

Whereas only a small proportion of survey respondents (18.7%) have either disagreed (8.5%) or strongly disagreed (10.2%) with the statement that the overall environment and atmosphere of Panache Beauty is very good and relaxing. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 14 below:

Table 13: The Overall Environment and Atmosphere of Panache is Very Good and Relaxing

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	25	10.2
Disagree	21	8.5
Neutral	65	26.4
Agree	55	22.4
Strongly Agree	80	32.5
Total	246	100.0

Figure 7: Overall Environment and Atmosphere of Panache is Very Good and Relaxing

After the quality of services, service pricing is also another important aspect of customer relations management. Leventha (2006) has given a concept of price loyalty, according to which that a business organisation charges the lowest price, enjoys a significant market share of the client base (Leventha, 2006). However, the organisation that operates on relatively a higher-end and provides premium quality

services charges premium prices from their customer and only targets a specific customer base. However, in such cases, customers must feel that the services they are paying for such prices are worthy of high spending. In this way, customers tend to remain loyal to such brands for their whole life, in which a customer decides to be faithful to a brand for his/ her entire lifetime.

This form of commitment occurs when consumers decide to remain loyal to the products or services irrespective of other competitors' presence and substitute products (Bowen & Chen, 2011). Thus, the customers were asked about their opinion, whether they that the services they are getting are rightly priced according to their quality.

The majority of interview participants agreed that the services are rightly priced considering the expertise, professionalism and facilities offered by Panache Beauty. One of the participants said that the salon gives offers and discounts occasionally but could do this more often for regular customers. However, none of them was of the opinion that the services provided by Panache Beauty are overpriced.

In this regard, a significant proportion of the total survey respondents of 56.9% either agreed (23.6%) or strongly agreed (33.3%) that the services of Panache Beauty are rightly priced according to the quality. While only 22% of the total survey respondents were neutral about the services' pricing according to their quality. On the other hand, only 21.2% of total survey respondents either disagreed (11.0%) or strongly disagreed (10.2%) with the statement that the services of Panache Beauty are rightly priced according to the quality. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 15 below:

Table 14: The Services of Panache Beauty Are Rightly Priced According to The Quality

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	25	10.2
Disagree	27	11.0
Neutral	54	22.0
Agree	58	23.6
Strongly Agree	82	33.3
Total	246	100.0

Figure 8: Services Are Rightly Priced

In order to build a relationship with the customers and bring customer loyalty, offering them service packages and discounts is an excellent way. Offering service packages and the discount is also considered a very important aspect of customer relationship management. This is the reason that customers were asked the offering of service packages and discount offers at Panache Beauty.

In this regard, a significant proportion of the total survey respondents of 52.9% either agreed (16.7%) or strongly agreed (36.2%) that the services of Panache Beauty offer good packages, and discounts are also available. While only 23.2% of the total survey respondents were neutral about Panache Beauty offers good packages and discounts are also available. On the other hand, only 24.0% of total survey respondents either disagreed (11.4%) or strongly disagreed (12.6%) with the statement that Panache Beauty offers good packages and discounts are also available. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 16 below:

Table 15: Panache Offers Good Packages and Discount Offers

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	31	12.6
Disagree	28	11.4
Neutral	57	23.2
Agree	41	16.7
Strongly Agree	89	36.2
Total	246	100.0

Figure 9: Offers Good Packages and Discount Offers

Gutjahr (2011) has argued that customer relationship management is about managing a relationship with the clients and interacting with them (Gutjahr, 2011). There are many ways in which the brands can interact with their clients and customers. A method to interact with the clients and keep them loyal is to offer distinct services or discounts to the customers returning to the brand. This helps the brands to keep their customers loyal by developing a feeling of being valued and acknowledged by the brands, and they tend to return (Aihie & Bennani, 2012; Beltman, 2013).

Customer loyalty and relationships have been studied greatly over the ages in the academic discourse. An intense curiosity in consumer relationships is also evidenced in marketing practice and is most

conspicuous in organisations' significant expend in consumer relationship systems (Chen & Popovich, 2003; Foss et al., 2008; Hillebrand et al., 2011).

Consumer share and customer retention rates are critical parameters in CRM. Consumer share refers to the number of purchases by consumers of a specific category of services and products from a specific supplier in relation to the total purchases in that category. To maximize these parameters, organisations employ relationship marketing instruments such as direct mailing and loyalty related programs (Kumar, 2009). Organisations also develop close associations with consumers to bolster consumers' relationship perceptions. Therefore, we asked whether Panache Beauty offers distinct and good packages and discounts to its existing customers.

One of the participants in the interview said that the salon could offer better discounts to regular customers. However, she did not deny the fact that Panache gives offers and discounts on certain occasions. Another customer agreed that the special packages offered by Panache Beauty to its regular customers are better than the ones offered by competitors. She also agreed that other than quality services, the offers and discounts are factors that forced her to keep visiting the salon.

A significant proportion of the total survey respondents of 55.2% either agreed (21.5%) or strongly agreed (33.7%) to this. While only 24.0% of the total survey respondents were neutral whether Panache Beauty offers distinct and good packages and discounts to its existing customers. On the other hand, only 20.8% of total survey respondents either disagreed (11.0%) or strongly disagreed (9.8%) with the statement that Panache Beauty offers distinct good packages and discounts to its existing customers. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 17 below:

Table 16:Panache Offers also Offers Very Good and Different Packages, and Discount Offers to Its Regular Customers

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	27	11.0
Disagree	24	9.8
Neutral	59	24.0
Agree	53	21.5
Strongly Agree	83	33.7
Total	246	100.0

Figure 10: Panache Offers Discount to Its Regular Customers

4.4 Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention (Dependent Variable)

In the current study, customer loyalty and retention have been taken as a dependent variable, which has been tested in terms of likelihood of visiting the salon again, preferring Panache Beauty over the other salons and recommending Panache Beauty to the family and friends.

Therefore, when asked about the likelihood of their visiting Panache Beauty again, all the respondents said that they visit the parlour very often. One of them visits Panache Beauty once a month while the duration of visits by other respondents ranges from once in two months to three months. One of them said that she loves visiting Panache Beauty to get the treatments and meet friends. Another one said that she visits the parlour whenever one of her friends needs treatment and not at regular intervals.

A very major proportion of the total survey respondents of 65.5% replied that it is either likely (21.5%) or very likely (33.7%) that they will visit Panache Beauty again. While only 12.6% of the total survey respondents were unsure about the likeliness of their next visit to Panache Beauty. On the other hand, only 22.0% of total survey respondents replied that it is either unlikely (11.8%) or very unlikely (10.2%) that they will visit Panache Beauty again. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 18 below:

Table 17: How Likely You Are Expected to Visit Panache Beauty Again?

	Frequency	Percent	
Very Unlikely	29	11.8	
Unlikely	25	10.2	
Unsure	31	12.6	
Likely	75	30.5	
Very Likely	86	35.0	
Total	246	100.0	100.0

Figure 11: How Likely You Are Expected to Visit Panache Beauty Again

In addition, when asked about the likelihood of preferring Panache Beauty over the other similar salons, a very major proportion of the total survey respondents of 67.4% replied that it is either likely (40.2%) or very likely (27.2%) that they will prefer Panache Beauty over the other similar salons. While only 18.3% of the total survey respondents were unsure about preferring Panache Beauty over the other similar salons. On the other hand, only 14.2% of total survey respondents replied that it is either unlikely (8.1%) or very unlikely (6.1%) that they will prefer Panache Beauty over the other similar salons. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 19 below:

Table 18: How Likely You Are Expected to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Other Salons?

	Frequency	Percent
Very Unlikely	20	8.1
Unlikely	15	6.1
Unsure	45	18.3
Likely	99	40.2
Very Likely	67	27.2
Total	246	100.0

Figure 12: How Likely You Are Expected to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Other Salons

Lastly, the respondents were asked about the likelihood of referring Panache Beauty to their family or friends. In response to this, all the interviewed customers said that they would recommend Panache Beauty to their friends and family. Some of them have already done this, and Panache has gained several new customers through such recommendation.

A major proportion of the total survey respondents of 51.6% replied that it is either likely (25.2%) or very likely (26.4%) that they will refer Panache Beauty to their family and friends. While only 19.1% of the total survey respondents were unsure whether they would refer Panache Beauty to their family and friends or not. On the other hand, only 19.3% of total survey respondents replied that it is either unlikely

(18.3%) or very unlikely (11.0%). They are going to refer Panache Beauty to their family and friends. The frequency distribution of the responses to the question is given in Table 20 below:

Table 19:How Likely You Are Expected to Refer Panache Beauty to Others?

	Frequency	Percent
Very Unlikely	27	11.0
Unlikely	45	18.3
Unsure	47	19.1
Likely	62	25.2
Very Likely	65	26.4
Total	246	100.0

Figure 13: How Likely You Are Expected to Refer Panache Beauty to Others

4.5 Correlation of Each Independent Variable with Dependent Variable

Customer loyalty is a condition in which customers become faithful to an organisational brand (Liang & Wang, 2014). As such, customers associated with an individual brand will continue to visit the business organisation, in which it is produced or offered, even if the item is not available. However, this is a consumer loyalty process, whereby consumers relate their previous experiences in informing their purchasing decisions. If the experience is positive, customers will repeatedly be visiting the brand or organisation, hence the lifetime loyalty. Consequently, upon understanding customer buying behaviour, an organisation can then deliver the desired client needs and desires to perfection with regards to buying

history and in turn, creating an attraction on behalf of the business, in the eyes of consumers (Vesel & Zabkar, 2009; Liang & Wang, 2014). Thus, this section presents a correlation analysis of each of the study's independent variables with each of the dependent variables. This correlation analysis helps establish how each particular independent variable (e.g. quality of services, the price of services, the suitability of services, etc.) is related or associated with the dependent variable (customer loyalty or retention) impacts the dependent variable.

First, a correlation analysis of the frequency of visiting Panache Beauty with the salon's distance from the residence of the customers has been conducted. The analysis showed a very weak or nearly no correlation between both variables (Table 16). This implies that clients' frequency of visiting the salon is not dependent upon their residence and salon distance. This also shows the willingness of clients to travel miles to get beauty care services.

Table 20: Correlation of Distance from Residence and Frequency of Visiting the Saloon

		How far is Panache Beauty from your residence?	How frequently you visit Panache Beauty?
How far is Panache Beauty from your residence?	Correlation	1	.014
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.822
	N	246	246
How frequently you visit Panache Beauty?	Correlation	.014	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.822	
	N	246	246

After this, the correlation between staff sincerity and friendliness with the customer loyalty and retention has been tested by analysing their likeliness to visit Panache Beauty again, prefer Panache Beauty over other salons, and recommend it to others. The correlation analysis depicts that staff's sincerity and friendliness have a very weak positive correlation with customers' likeliness to visit Panache Beauty again, and it is also not significant. Similarly, the staff's sincerity and friendliness are weakly positively correlated with customers' likeliness to prefer Panache Beauty over other beauty Salons. However, there is a slightly higher positive correlation between the staff's sincerity and friendliness and customers' likeliness to recommend Panache Beauty to others. Although all of the loyalty and retention indicators are positively correlated with staff's sincerity and friendliness, this correlation is not significant.

The findings imply that the staff's friendliness and sincerity somewhat positively influence customer loyalty and retention but do not significantly influence it. The research findings are in line with the Nam et al. (2017) that suggest that service quality, communication, brand image, price perception, and value offered lead to increased customer loyalty and, in turn, customer retention. Similarly, Morgan and Hunt (1994) implied through the commitment-trust theory that commitment, effective communication, trust development, and conflict resolution are the factors that influence and measure the level of customer loyalty. Hillebrand et al. (2011) defined customer brand loyalty as the repeated buying behaviour that reflects the positive decisions to pay for the similar product and service offered; however, customers' positive attitude towards the product and service should remain intact to repeated buying behaviour to continue. This implies that customers would come to visit Panache Beauty again if they get quality services and the staff's same positive attitude.

Furthermore, the CRM practices and strategies to maintain customer relationships depict staff's sincerity and friendliness to the customers, increasing their loyalty and ensuring retention. According to Yang et al. (2012), the cosmetics industry firms try to attract customers by improving the perceived quality of products, brand image, and effective communication through CRM strategies, which in turn helps them gain customer loyalty and improve customer retention. All of these research studies are in line with the findings of this research regarding the correlation of friendliness and sincerity of staff with customer loyalty and retention.

Table 21: Correlation of Staff Sincerity and Friendliness with Customer Loyalty and Retention

		Sincere and Friendly Staff	Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likelihood to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Sincere and Friendly Staff	Correlation	1	.384**	.277**	.529**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.384**	1	.344**	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
	Correlation	.277**	.344**	1	.402**

Likelihood to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Correlation	.529**	.582**	.402**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation between experience and understanding of staff regarding customers' needs and customer loyalty and retention has been tested with the same loyalty and retention indicators. The experience of staff and their understanding of customer's needs has a weak positive correlation with customers' likelihood to visit Panache Beauty again, prefer the Salon over others, and recommend it to others. This implies that experienced staff and customers' satisfaction regarding their needs positively influences their loyalty and, ultimately, retention. As suggested by Kumar (2009), customers recognise and appreciate firms' efforts only when they realise them by getting their needs fulfilled and their desired results.

Hosseini et al. (2010), in this context, have stated that the struggles of the organisation to develop and manage relationships with customers through direct contact increase customer satisfaction, quality of services and ultimately contribute to retention. The study's findings combined with other studies imply that if the customers are dealt with efficiency and friendliness and their needs are catered effectively in the beauty industry, it will increase customer loyalty contributing to customer retention.

In line with these findings, Vesel and Zabkar (2009) have stated that employees and staff of an organisation has a crucial role in the communication of values to customers and giving them a sense of satisfaction and fulfilment of their needs and wants by managing times and points before purchase, during purchase, and after purchase. Effective relationship marketing strategies are also crucial for industries where consumers' opinions and preferences have considerable importance, including the beauty industry (Vesel and Zabkar, 2009). Shaon and Rehman (2015) also found that providing products and services by remaining sensitive to customers' desires and demands are imperative to customer loyalty. The innovations and development in the CRM strategies, including offering high-quality products, rewarding customers, communicating effectively, and understanding customers' needs, increase customer loyalty towards the brand and the services offered (Malik, 2015; Shaon and Rehman, 2015). This implies the significance and importance of catering to customer needs with experienced and skilled staff for Panache Beauty to increase customer loyalty and retention.

Table 22: Correlation of Staff Experience and Understanding to Customers' Needs with Customer Loyalty and Retention

		Experience Staff	Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likelihood to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Experienced Staff	Correlation	1	.393**	.242**	.515**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.393**	1	.344**	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Correlation	.242**	.344**	1	.402**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Correlation	.515**	.582**	.402**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation between staff professionalism (independent variable) with customer loyalty and retention has been tested. The correlation analysis depicts that the staff's professionalism which takes care of customers' skin has a positive correlation with the likelihood of customers to visit Panache Beauty again. Similarly, the correlation of staff professionalism with customers' likelihood to prefer Panache Beauty over other salons is also positive but not significant.

The professionalism of the staff is also positively correlated with customers' likelihood to recommend the salon to others. This implies that staff professionalism in dealing with the customers is positively linked with customers' likelihood to visit the salon, prefer it over others, and recommend it to others, which ultimately shows their loyalty towards the brand. These findings are consistent with the study of Malik

(2015). His research found that impact of CRM in terms of trust on employees, service delivery time, speed of the work done, friendliness of staff, an obligation of staff to fulfil the customer needs, and arrangement of the work increases the customer satisfaction by 94% which contributes to customer loyalty towards the brand. Similarly, a study conducted by Azzam (2014) suggested that CRM practices include employee behaviour, professionalism, quality of services, maintaining and updating customer database, offering solutions to customers' problems, the physical environment of the workplace, and interaction with the customers ensure customer satisfaction. Tauni et al. (2014) have also found that CRM significantly influences customer retention by retaining 68% of customers in the telecom industry through quality excellence in providing services. This implies that the development of a strong and effective relationship with the customers through professionalism, excellent services, friendliness and sincerity, effective communication, and catering to their needs would increase customer loyalty and ultimately contribute to retaining the customers in the beauty industry.

Table 23: Correlation of Staff Professionalism with Customer Loyalty and Retention

			Professional Staff	Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likeliness to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Professional Staff	Correlation	1	.421**	.208**	.513**	
and Takes Care of Customers' Skin	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.421**	1	.344**	.582**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Others	Correlation	.208**	.344**	1	.402**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	
Likeliness to Recommend Panache to Others	Correlation	.513**	.582**	.402**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
	N	246	246	246	246	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation of quality of services offered has been tested with customer loyalty and retention in the following table (Table 25). The excellence in the quality of services provided is positively correlated with the likeliness of customers to visit Panache Beauty again, to prefer Panache Beauty over other salons, and to recommend it to others. The highest positive correlation is with their likeliness to recommend the salon to others. This implies that excellence in the quality of services offered enhances customer loyalty towards the brand and retains customers. These findings are in line with the study of Azzam (2014) and Tauni et al. (2014) who found that CRM applications in terms of excellence in quality of services offered to enhance customer satisfaction contributing to customer loyalty. Similarly, Labus (2010) has shown that CRM activities, including customer services, billing, sales, and marketing, influence customer relationship and satisfaction with the brand.

Table 24: Correlation of Quality of Services Provided with Customer Loyalty and Retention of Suitability

			Excellent Quality of Services Provided	Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likeliness to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Excellent Quality of Services Provided	Correlation	1	.433**	.209**	.528**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.433**	1	.344**	.582**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Others	Correlation	.209**	.344**	1	.402**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	
Likeliness to Recommend Panache to Others	Correlation	.528**	.582**	.402**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The suitability of services offered to customers is an important factor in increasing customer experiences and loyalty. The study's findings depict that the suitability of services provided to customers is positively correlated with the likeliness of customers to visit Panache Beauty, prefer the salon over others, and recommend it to others. The correlation is weak between the suitability of services offered with customer loyalty and retention. However, the positive correlation implies the significance of the suitability of services provided to customer loyalty and retention.

The findings are in line with the study of Djumarno et al. (2017), who found that the quality and prices of the product significantly influence customer satisfaction that ultimately influences customer loyalty. Similarly, Al-Bostanji (2015) stated that the quality of services offered (empathy, tangibility, and quick responsiveness) strongly influences customer loyalty. On the contrary, the findings of Rimawan et al. (2017) show that the quality of services, product quality, and trust do not influence customer satisfaction. However, customer satisfaction influences customer loyalty. The study's findings, combined with other studies, suggest that suitability and quality of services influence customer loyalty and customer retention.

Table 25: Correlation of Services Provided for Customers' Skin with Customer Loyalty and Retention

		Services Provided Are Suitable for Customers	Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likelihood to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Services Provided Are Suitable for Customers	Correlation	1	.405**	.221**	.473**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.405**	1	.344**	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to refer Panache Beauty Over Others	Correlation	.221**	.344**	1	.402**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	246	246	246	246
	Correlation	.473**	.582**	.402**	1

Likelihood to Recommend Panache to Others	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In almost all of the industries, the stores' overall environment and atmosphere play a significant role in customer satisfaction that ultimately impacts customer loyalty. The correlation analysis of good and relaxing overall environment and atmosphere of Panache Beauty with customer loyalty and retention suggests a positive correlation. However, the correlation of a good and relaxing environment with the likelihood of customers to prefer Panache Beauty over others is weaker. It is higher with the likelihood of customers to visit the salon again and recommend it to the others. As in the fitness industry, the fitness centre atmosphere influences customer satisfaction and loyalty (Oztas et al., 2016). Similarly, the results of the study conducted by Emir (2016) are consistent with the findings of this research, proving that there is a statistically significant link between the external and internal components of hotel atmosphere and customer loyalty (Emir, 2016). The findings of this study combined with other studies imply that an overall good environment and atmosphere, whether it be beauty salons, fitness centres, and restaurants or hotels, shapes the customer perception that influences customer satisfaction and ultimately improves customer loyalty and retention.

Table 26: Correlation of Overall Environment and Atmosphere with Customer Loyalty and Retention

		Very Good and Relaxing Overall Environment	Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likelihood to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Very Good and Relaxing Overall Environment	Correlation	1	.457**	.234**	.537**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
	Correlation	.457**	1	.344**	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000

Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to refer Panache Beauty Over Others	Correlation	.234**	.344**	1	.402**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
Likelihood to Recommend Panache to Others	N	246	246	246	246
	Correlation	.537**	.582**	.402**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pricing products and services is a significant variable that can influence customer behaviour, loyalty, and retention. The correlation analysis of service pricing with customer loyalty depicts a weak positive correlation of the rightly priced services with customers' likelihood to visit Panache Beauty Again, prefer the salon over others, and recommend it to others. As mentioned above, the study of Nam et al. (2017) found that price perception, quality of services, the value offered, and brand image increases customer loyalty. Similarly, Djumarno et al. (2017) have stated that prices and quality of products offered greatly impact customer satisfaction that increases customer loyalty.

Another study conducted by Dawes (2009) found that when customers are associated with a brand from the long-time period, price increases will not affect customer retention. However, the number of customers is influenced adversely by the price increases reducing the retention rate. Hutagalung et al. (2015) found that pricing, promotion, and service quality has a significant impact on customer retention in Johnny Andrian, a beauty salon renowned for its hairdressing and other customers' needs.

Table 27: Correlation of Service Pricing with Customer Loyalty and Retention

Rightly Priced Services	Rightly Priced Services	Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likelihood to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Correlation	1	.450**	.167**	.485**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.009	.000

	N	246	246	246	246
Likeliness to Visit	Correlation	.450**	1	.344**	.582**
Panache Beauty	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Again	N	246	246	246	246
Likeliness to refer	Correlation	.167**	.344**	1	.402**
Panache Beauty	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.000		.000
Over Others	N	246	246	246	246
Likeliness to	Correlation	.485**	.582**	.402**	1
Recommend	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
Panache to Others	N	246	246	246	246

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The reward programs, good packages, and discount offer to the customer's influence customer satisfaction and loyalty. Correlation analysis of good packages and discount offers with customer loyalty and retention depicts a positive correlation. Good packages and discount offers are weakly positively correlated with customers' likeliness to visit Panache Beauty again, with the likeliness of customers to prefer Panache Beauty over other salons and recommend Panache Beauty to others. This implies that offering good packages and discount offers to the customers can increase customer loyalty and retention. As suggested by Magatef and Tomalieh (2015), loyalty programs include different packages like VIP benefits, point systems, and other rewards programs significantly influence customer retention. According to Ndubisi (2005), custom-made offers, packages, and discounts to clients can compel them to purchase the products and take the services. According to Alvarez and Cavanagh (2005), discounts are a strong, powerful method to draw new customers and retain the existing ones.

Table 28: Correlations of Provision of Good Packages and Discount Offers with Customer Loyalty and Retention

	Good Packages and Discount Offers	Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likeliness to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Correlation	1	.399**	.241**	.563**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000

Good Packages and Discount Offers	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.399**	1	.344**	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Likelihood to refer Panache Beauty Over Others	N	246	246	246	246
	Correlation	.242**	.344**	1	.402**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
Likelihood to Recommend Panache to Others	N	246	246	246	246
	Correlation	.563**	.582**	.402**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation analysis of the provision of special packages and discount offers to the regular customers with customer loyalty and retention depicts that special packages and discounts offered to regular customers are more significantly correlated with customer loyalty as compared to good packages and discounts offered to everyone. It is positively correlated with customers' likelihood to visit Panache Beauty again, prefer it over others, and recommend the salons to others. This implies that special packages and discount offers can significantly increase customer loyalty and retention. These findings are in line with other studies conducted by different authors on loyalty programs, and discounts offered to customers (Ndubisi, 2005; Magatef & Tomalieh, 2015).

Table 29: Correlations of Provision of Special Packages and Discount Offers for Regular Customers with Customer Loyalty and Retention

	Special Packages and Discount Offers for Customers	Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Likelihood to Prefer Panache Beauty Over Others	Likelihood to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others
Correlation	1	.408**	.220**	.566**

Special Packages and Offers for Regulars	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Correlation	.408**	1	.344**	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to refer Panache Beauty Over Other	Correlation	.220**	.344**	1	.402**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.000
	N	246	246	246	246
Likelihood to Recommend Panache to Others	Correlation	.566**	.582**	.402**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	246	246	246	246

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation analysis of independent variables including (quality of services offered, price of services, the suitability of services, overall environment and atmosphere, staff professionalism, staff's sincerity and friendliness, good packages, special packages, and discount offers) with the dependent variables (customer loyalty and retention indicated by their likelihood to visit again, preference, and recommendation to others) depicts that all of the independent variables are positively correlated with the dependent variables. However, in some cases, the correlation was quite significant, while it was insignificant in some cases. The overall analysis depicts that with the good quality of services, reasonable pricing, good and relaxing overall atmosphere and environment, professional, experienced, and friendly staff, and good packages offered to the customers. These customer loyalty increases ultimately contribute to customer retention.

4.6 ANOVA for Statistical Significance of the Relation between Study Variables

One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used to determine whether the differences between two or more variables are statistically significant or not. Therefore, one-way ANOVA has been performed upon the study variables to establish whether the difference in the mean value of the study's dependent variables is statically significantly different from the mean value of the independent variable.

The results of ANOVA are presented in the tables below.

ANOVA of staff sincerity and friendliness with customer loyalty and retention with all three dependent variables of the study (likelihood to visit panache beauty again, likelihood to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likelihood to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 31 below. The

significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [F (4,241) = 11.752, p = .000] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [F (4,241) = 6.736, p = .000] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [F (4,241) = 24.336, p = .000] for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 30:ANOVA of Staff Sincerity and Friendliness with Customer Loyalty and Retention

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	73.555	4	18.389	11.752	.000
	Within Groups	377.112	242	1.565		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Between Groups	33.508	4	8.377	6.736	.000
	Within Groups	299.695	242	1.244		
	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	126.545	4	31.636	24.336	.000
	Within Groups	313.297	242	1.300		
	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of staff experience and understanding of customers' needs with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 32 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [F (4,241) = 12.816, p = .000] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [F (4,241) = 8.801, p = .000] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [F (4,241) = 22.276, p = .000] for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 31:ANOVA of Staff Experience and Understanding to Customers' Needs

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	79.047	4	19.762	12.816	.000
	Within Groups	371.619	242	1.542		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Between Groups	42.469	4	10.617	8.801	.000
	Within Groups	290.735	242	1.206		
	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	118.724	4	29.681	22.276	.000
	Within Groups	321.117	242	1.332		
	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of staff professionalism with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 33 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [$F(4,241) = 16.109$, $p = .000$] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [$F(4,241) = 5.863$, $p = .000$] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [$F(4,241) = 22.019$, $p = .000$] for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 32:ANOVA of Staff Professionalism

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	95.073	4	23.768	16.109	.000
	Within Groups	355.594	242	1.475		
	Total	450.667	246			
	Between Groups	29.548	4	7.387	5.863	.000
	Within Groups	303.655	242	1.260		

Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	117.724	4	29.431	22.019	.000
	Within Groups	322.118	242	1.337		
	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of quality of services provided at the salon with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 34 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [F (4,241) = 17.351, p = .000] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [F (4,241) = 5.872, p = .000] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [F (4,241) = 24.237, p = .000] for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 33: ANOVA of Quality of Services Provided

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	100.765	4	25.191	17.351	.000
	Within Groups	349.901	242	1.452		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Between Groups	29.591	4	7.398	5.872	.000
	Within Groups	303.612	242	1.260		
	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	126.179	4	31.545	24.237	.000
	Within Groups	313.663	242	1.302		
	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of the suitability of services provided at the salon for customers' skin with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 35 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [F (4,241) = 16.145, p = .000] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [F (4,241) = 6.868, p = .000] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [F (4,241) = 18.479, p = .000] for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 34:ANOVA of Suitability of Services Provided for Customers' Skin

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	95.241	4	23.810	16.145	.000
	Within Groups	355.426	242	1.475		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Between Groups	34.098	4	8.524	6.868	.000
	Within Groups	299.106	242	1.242		
	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	103.240	4	25.810	18.479	.000
	Within Groups	336.601	242	1.397		
	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of the salon's overall environment and atmosphere with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 36 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [F (4,241) = 19.514, p = .000] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [F (4,241) = 6.305,

$p = .000$] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and $[F(4,241) = 25.876, p = .000]$ for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 35:ANOVA of Overall Environment and Atmosphere

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	110.252	4	27.563	19.514	.000
	Within Groups	340.414	242	1.413		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Between Groups	31.568	4	7.892	6.305	.000
	Within Groups	301.636	242	1.252		
	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	132.148	4	33.037	25.876	.000
	Within Groups	307.694	242	1.277		
	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of pricing of the services provided at the salon with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 37 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p -value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA $[F(4,241) = 18.321, p = .000]$ for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; $[F(4,241) = 3.733, p = .000]$ for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and $[F(4,241) = 19.137, p = .000]$ for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 36:ANOVA of Service Pricing

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	105.085	4	26.271	18.321	.000
	Within Groups	345.581	242	1.434		

	Total	450.667	246			
Likelihood to refer	Between Groups	19.441	4	4.860	3.733	.000
Panache Beauty Over	Within Groups	313.762	242	1.302		
Other Saloons	Total	333.203	246			
Likelihood to	Between Groups	106.027	4	26.507	19.137	.000
Recommend Panache	Within Groups	333.814	242	1.385		
Beauty to Others	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of the provision of good packages and discount offers with customer loyalty and retention with all three dependent variables of the study (likelihood to visit panache beauty again, likelihood to refer panache beauty over other saloons, likelihood to recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 38 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likelihood to visit panache beauty again/ likelihood to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likelihood to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [$F(4,241) = 16.206, p = .000$] for likelihood to visit panache beauty again; [$F(4,241) = 7.742, p = .000$] for likelihood to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [$F(4,241) = 29.756, p = .000$] for likelihood to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 37: ANOVA of Provision of Good Packages and Discount Offers with Customer Loyalty and Retention

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likelihood to Visit	Between Groups	95.528	4	23.882	16.206	.000
Panache Beauty Again	Within Groups	355.139	242	1.474		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likelihood to refer	Between Groups	37.941	4	9.485	7.742	.000
Panache Beauty Over	Within Groups	295.262	242	1.225		
Other Saloons	Total	333.203	246			
Likelihood to	Between Groups	145.411	4	36.353	29.756	.000
Recommend Panache	Within Groups	294.430	242	1.222		
Beauty to Others	Total	439.841	246			

ANOVA of the provision of special packages and discount offers for regular customers with all three dependent variables of the study (likeliness to visit panache beauty again, likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons, and recommend panache beauty to others) is presented in table 39 below. The significance value of the difference is 0.00 for all three dependent variables (i.e., p-value = 0.00), which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in likeliness to visit panache beauty again/ likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons/ likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others on average between different groups. The results are determined by one-way ANOVA [F (4,241) = 17.667, p = .000] for likeliness to visit panache beauty again; [F (4,241) = 5.826, p = .000] for likeliness to refer panache beauty over other saloons; and [F (4,241) = 28.385, p = .000] for likeliness to recommend panache beauty to others.

Table 38:ANOVA of Special Packages and Discount Offers for Regular Customers

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Likeliness to Visit Panache Beauty Again	Between Groups	102.184	4	25.546	17.667	.000
	Within Groups	348.483	242	1.446		
	Total	450.667	246			
Likeliness to refer Panache Beauty Over Other Saloons	Between Groups	29.379	4	7.345	5.826	.000
	Within Groups	303.824	242	1.261		
	Total	333.203	246			
Likeliness to Recommend Panache Beauty to Others	Between Groups	140.858	4	35.215	28.385	.000
	Within Groups	298.983	242	1.241		
	Total	439.841	246			

5 Chapter Five: Discussion on Findings

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the research by examining the results of statistical analysis using SPSS. The survey questionnaire's various aspects and variables will be analysed under separate headings like demographics, dependent and independent variables. Finally, a correlation between dependent and independent variables was also established to determine how each variable affected customers' decisions and its effect on customer loyalty. A discussion on the findings will also be presented along with the linkages to current research and existing literature review to ascertain whether the data obtained during the survey supports information already in existence.

5.2 Demographics

This section examined the descriptive statistics of research participants like their age, gender, ethnicity, race, occupation, profession, marital status, etc. to analyse the consumer behaviour and beauty preferences of people. Analysing general information and demographics was also helpful in getting an accurate insight into the influence of such factors in the buying habits of the target market and target population of Panache Beauty. Factors like age and gender helped to understand the characteristic of research participants while their employment status and relationship status with Panache Beauty gave a detailed insight into their behaviour pattern.

5.3 Gender

The survey was held among 246 individuals, and the majority of participants, amounting to 77.2%, were women, while only 22.8% were men. This shows that women visit beauty parlours more frequently than men and that the former is more beauty conscious than their counterparts. The results also indicate that the target market of Panache Beauty is women rather than men though the number of male customers is not a negligible sum.

5.4 Age

It was found that young adults belonging to the age group of 26-35 years form the majority of customers of Panache Beauty. This shows that people belonging to this age group are more beauty conscious. The finding is similar to the finding of a study conducted among Indian women (Jayesh & Pradip, 2014), which found that females who visit beauty parlour are young adults.

The above table shows that 37.4% amounting to about two-fifths of the total number of research participants belonged to the age group between 26 to 35 years, while 21.1% or one-fifth of the total number of participants belonged to the age group of 18 to 25 years. The pattern also brings out an interesting factor that there is a slight increase in the number of people belonging to the age group of 46 to 55 years (16.7%) who visit beauty parlours in comparison to those between the age of 36 to 45 years (14.2%). This shows that research participants in the age group of 36 to 45 years were less beauty conscious than those belonging to the age group of 46 to 55 years. From the analysis, it is found that more than half the customer base, amounting to 58.5%, of Panache Group, are aged between 18 to 35 years while the next age group to be focused on those between 46 to 55 years.

5.5 Employment status

On analysing the employment status of respondents, it was found that about fifty percent of the customers of Panache Beauty is employed. Self-employed persons formed 35.8% of the customers, while the customers contained only 15.9% of students. This shows that employed people, especially women, are more likely to visit beauty parlour in comparison to students or unemployed persons. This also shows that those who go to the office and mingle with others are more conscious about their looks than those who are self-employed, and hence the main target of Panache Beauty should be employed women that fall within the age gap of 26 to 45 years.

5.6 Proximity

Proximity is another factor that influences the decision to visit a beauty parlour. The research points to the fact that women tend to visit beauty parlours close within their proximity, and the maximum distance acceptable is 2 to 10 miles. Simultaneously, it was also found that only 20% of women residing within 2 miles visited Panache Beauty, while 35.4% of customers resided at a distance of over 10 miles. These facts indicate that distance is not a hurdle for customer loyalty and hence need not be considered a factor while targeting the market. The research shows that women prefer to visit their favourite beauty parlour irrespective of the distance as their main concern is results.

5.7 Duration

A major factor discovered during the research is that only 26.4% of customers maintained a relationship with Panache Beauty for over a year, while the relationship of 20.7% lasted for less than a month. It was also found that only 35% of customers have remained customers of Panache Beauty for six months. This shows that Panache Beauty has retained over 44.3% of its customers for over six months. The data also

points to the fact that Panache Beauty needs to increase customer loyalty to maintain a long-term relationship with customers.

5.8 Frequency

Another important factor considered as part of the research was the frequency of visits by customers. It was found that 107 customers of the total 246 respondents used to visit the parlour on a fortnightly basis, while 14.2% visit the parlour once a week, and 5.3% give a daily visit. The result is very promising when it comes to customer loyalty, as it can be seen that 153 customers visit the parlour in two weeks. It was also found that 91 customers make very occasional visits. The research points to the fact that the majority of customers like to visit Panache Beauty during a smaller frequency, which is a positive aspect when it comes to customer loyalty.

5.9 Independent variables

The questions asked under these segments relate to various factors that are likely to affect customer relationships and loyalty. Quality of service, the behaviour of staff, services provided by Panache Beauty etc. are factors affecting customer relationships. These elements are of extreme importance as they are the factors that influence the decisions made by customers with regard to the services offered by Panache Beauty.

5.10 Customer relationship

The customer relationship of Panache was considered as an independent variable considering the fact that it is an important aspect that affects customer loyalty. Various aspects like customer engagement, pricing, quality and sustainability of service were considered as these factors are very important in customer relationship management and customer engagement. Communication and collaboration of employees play a major role in customer loyalty. Hence, it was also important to understand the behaviour of employees as to whether they were customer friendly and sincere. It was found that 30.1% of customers strongly agreed that the staff at Panache Beauty is very friendly and sincere, while 17.1% agreed. 24.4% maintained a neutral stand while 28.5% disagreed. This shows that the majority of customers, amounting to almost fifty percent, consider Panache staff as friendly and sincere, and another one-fourth consider them as neutral. Panache can do better when it comes to customer relationships and make their staff more customer-friendly, and this will help to turn the customers who are taking a neutral stand into an agreement. Improving customer relationships will also help to retain more customers and increase the frequency of visits. With better customer relationships, Panache Beauty can make sure to

retain customers for a longer period as well. Staggering customer relationships in a beauty parlour will earn praises and revenue alike as it will help gain and retain more customers for a longer period. The beauty industry falls high in terms of quality and customer relationships. Staff should be able to deal with individual customers according to their needs and should also be able to establish a good relationship with them.

5.11 Experience of staff

Another important factor that affects customer relationships is the experience of staff. Only an experienced staff will understand the needs of a customer and provide them with an effective and satisfactory service. The staff needs to understand the skin type of a customer and suggest the best options to suit their needs. The research found that 47.1% of customers agreed that the staff at Panache Beauty was experienced and capable of understanding their preferences and needs. At the same time, 25.6% maintained a neutral stance, while 27.3% gave negative remarks. Though the results are not disappointing, it is not that promising as well. Staff at Panache needs the training to understand the needs and preferences of customers. They should be able to create a better relationship with customers so as to understand their needs and preferences to provide a better suggestion.

It is also important for the employees to be aware of various processes carried out in the parlour in detail so that they can suggest the best for the customer. They should also be able to explain to the customer satisfactorily as to why that particular treatment was suggested. The employee should have knowledge about various aspects like skin and hair type, the result of each treatment on each skin type, the best suitable hairstyles for various face shapes etc. An experiment is an important factor that can help beauty parlour employees acquire such knowledge to a larger extent. Panache Beauty needs to make sure that their employees are skilled with the necessary attributes to ensure customer loyalty.

5.12 Analysing capacity

Skincare is one of the most important aspects to be taken care of in a beauty parlour. Massage for the face and body is a popular beauty treatment that offers benefits to the skin, including the application of beauty products. Hence, the staff needs to be aware of the benefits of various beauty products used in the parlour and its application according to skin type. It is also necessary for the staff to know which product should be used to meet the customer's requirement and expectation. The staff will have to identify the skin type, its conditions and characteristics to recommend proper skin treatment and product. Analysis of skin will also help staff to recommend any immediate or future skin treatment for the client.

When asked whether the staffs assess the skin type of the customer at Panache Beauty before suggesting treatment or using any product of the total participants, 43.6% agreed that the staff at Panache Beauty assess the skin type prior to recommending treatment or using any product. Meanwhile, 21.5% maintained a neutral stance, while 23.6% had a disagreement about this. As most customers gave a positive reply while one fourth maintained a neutral stance, it is likely that the staff at Panache are conducting skin assessment but might not be communicating it to the customer, which makes them unaware of the act.

It is important to inform the customer that the staff at Panache Beauty are recommending skin treatment or using the product after properly analysing the skin condition and inconsistency with the customer's requirement. This method will help increase awareness among customers regarding the staff's care and caution, which will further help increase customer loyalty.

5.13 Service quality

The beauty parlour industry belongs to the service sector, and hence, customer loyalty is the most important factor that affects customer retention. Customer demands a high quality of service when it comes to skincare along with quality products. It is also important for the employees to understand the requirements of each customer and respond accordingly. Staff must be capable enough to respond to customer demands effectively and efficiently. Hence, it was important to understand the quality of service to identify customer management at Panache Beauty. It was noted that service quality is one of the inquiries to which the largest number of participants gave a positive reply.

As many as 129 respondents agreed that the service quality at Panache is good, 26.4% maintained a neutral stance. Thus, it was found that 78.8% of participants were happy about the service quality at Panache Beauty, and only 21.4% disagreed with the statement of the quality of service. As cited above, one of the reasons behind this might be that the customers are not aware of the methods adopted by Panache Beauty to ensure the quality of service. Hence, communicating with them might be a good option to increase customers' perception in this regard. Creating awareness among customers on how each treatment and product is chosen for them will help increase satisfaction regarding the quality of service provided at Panache Beauty.

5.14 Suitability

A most important factor to be considered in the beauty industry is whether a product is suitable for your skin. Ensuring quality service and products are not enough, but the staff of beauty parlours must also make sure that the product used for treatments is suitable for the skin type of the customer. People have

different skin types, and the result of a single product will be different for each customer depending upon their skin type. At times, a customer might demand a particular product or treatment, which might not suit their skin type. Under such conditions, the staff must be able to identify that the product demanded by the customer is not suitable for the skin type. Instead, another one will be more suitable. The staff must also be able to convince the same to the customer, which is possible only in a friendly atmosphere. Such actions will help to retain customer loyalty. When asked about the suitability of products used for treatment at Panache Beauty, majority of respondents, amounting to over half of the total participants, agreed that the products used at Panache Beauty suit their skin type.

As many as 53 respondents, amounting to 21.5%, maintained a neutral stance while 23.9% disagreed. The results show that the majority of customers, who are aware of their skin type and effects of treatment, are satisfied with the product use at Panache Beauty, while about one-fifth of them does not have a negative opinion. About one-fourth of the customers disagreed with the suitability of products for their skin, and this is not a negligible amount. The issue can be resolved if the staff can have a conversation with the customers about their skin type and which product, they think will suit their skin type. If the staff has a different opinion, it can be communicated to the customer. This method will help develop a better understanding of the product use among customers of Panache Beauty.

5.15 Environment

As skincare and other beauty-related treatments need to be performed in a hygienic environment, customers will also check the overall atmosphere of the parlour while choosing one. Beauty parlours are also a place in which customers, especially women, use as a place for relaxation. Women visit parlours not only to get beauty treatments done but also to spend some time for themselves away from the daily chores and to get free of their stress. Hence, beauty parlours need to have a relaxing and comfortable environment that can attract customers. Places that can provide a friendly and relaxing atmosphere are more likely to get frequent customers. For an enquiry on the atmosphere of Panache Beauty, 135 participants gave a positive reply, indicating that 54.9% of respondents consider the environment and atmosphere of Panache Beauty as relaxing and comfortable.

It was also found that 26.4% of respondents gave a neutral opinion, pointing out that they do not feel uncomfortable while visiting the parlour. At the same time, it is also important to note that 18.7% of respondents disagreed that the atmosphere of Panache Beauty is good and relaxing. This shows that Panache Beauty can better customer relations better its atmosphere, which will attract more customers. Establishing a better relationship with customers is one method that will help them feel more relaxed and stress-free while in the parlour. Establishing good communication with customers is key to this, and this

is an important skill that employees in the service sector need to acquire. Such measures will help Panache Beauty to turn neutral customers into satisfied customers, which will further tempt customers to visit the parlour again.

5.16 Pricing

Pricing plays a crucial role in the service sector as customers give equal importance to pricing along with quality. Price loyalty can be achieved by providing services at a lower price (Leventha, 2006). However, it might not always be possible to provide the best available service in the industry at a lower price. A beauty parlour, providing premium quality service is likely to charge premium price from customers. Still, it is important to make sure that the customers feel that the service provided to them are worth the money they are paying. Another factor is that those providing premium services target specific customers who are ready to pay a premium price for the services. If the customers are satisfied with the service, they are likely to remain loyal to the brand for a long period irrespective of the presence of competitors in the market (Brown & Chen, 2011). Hence, it is important to know customers' opinion regarding the pricing at Panache Beauty as it will help to understand whether the participants consider the pricing as reasonable or not and whether they are satisfied with the service. As many as 56.9% of participants were of the opinion that the services provided by Panache Beauty are rightly priced, and of them, 33.3% strongly agreed to this, which is a positive factor.

Meanwhile, 22% of participants of the survey maintained a neutral stance, which shows that they do not have any complaints regarding the pricing at Panache Beauty. Only 21.2% were of the opinion that the service provided by Panache Beauty is not up to the mark, and this shows that only less than one-fourth of the customers feel that the parlour is highly priced. The survey points to the fact that those who agree with the pricing at Panache Beauty are more likely to remain loyal to the brand while those who maintained a neutral stance are likely to return to the parlour as they do not have any complaint with the pricing for service. These two sections should form the target market of Panache Beauty as they understand and value the parlour's quality of service.

5.17 Offers

Service packages and discounts are one of the most popular marketing techniques used to attract customers. The same method is also used for retaining customers. Loyal customers are offered special discounts and packages that they find to be an added advantage to remain loyal to a brand. Panache Beauty offers such packages to their customers, and when asked about discounts and other benefits, 52.9% agreed that the offers made by the parlour are good. At the same time, 23.2% gave a neutral opinion,

which points to the fact that these customers do not have complaints about the packages and discounts offered by Panache Beauty.

On the other hand, 24% of survey participants were not happy with the offers and disagreed that the packages and discounts are good. Customers' response shows that the majority of customers of the beauty parlour are happy with the offers provided to them while 23% do not have any complaints. Providing new offers or introducing new discount schemes is likely to attract those who maintain a neutral stand while ensuring satisfied customers' customer loyalty. Such a move is also likely to improve the satisfaction of those customers who are not happy with the current offers provided by Panache Beauty.

5.18 Relationship with regular customers

One of the major assets of a service industry is its loyal customers, and this is all the more important in the case of a beauty parlour segment. Those who visit the parlour frequently and are maintaining a long-term relationship are the ones who are satisfied with the services provided at the parlour. The best means to maintain customer relationships is to interact with the customers (Gutjahr, 2011). It is the best way to let the customer know about the services provided by the parlour. Good communication will ensure a strong relationship with the customer and prompt them to return to the brand. It will also help to develop a feel among the consumers that they are being valued and their priorities are being taken care of. Besides communication, providing special packages and discounts is another way to make the customer feel important.

In the service industry, it is important to acknowledge the needs of customers and provide the service accordingly. The majority of customers prefer to be in places where their needs get fulfilled in a satisfactory manner. Customer-specific and unique packages, rewards, discounts, etc. are among the best methods to make the customer feel important. Hence, it was asked whether Panache Beauty offers distinct packages and discounts to its customers. The question was of great importance as it was a major factor that helped retain regular customers and ensure their loyalty. It was found that 55.2% of customers agreed that Panache Beauty provides special packages and discounts for their existing customers, which shows that the majority customer is satisfied with the parlour's offers.

It also points to the fact that 55.2% of customers of Panache Beauty are loyal customers. The survey results also showed that 24% of customers maintained a neutral stand, which indicates that they do not have any complaints with the parlour's offers. Customers who maintain a neutral stand are likely to become loyal if provided with better offers that will satisfy them. Only 51 of the 246 customers maintained that the offers provided are not distinct.

5.19 Dependent variables

Decisions made by customers based on independent variables were considered under this section. Such decisions affect customer loyalty as well as acquiring new customers. Three factors, visiting the salon again, recommending for friends and family, preferring Panache Beauty over other salons, are considered dependent variables.

5.20 Revisit

Loyal customers will visit the parlour again, and it was important to understand this factor, which will help to understand customer retention and loyalty. When asked about the possibility of revisiting Panache Beauty, 65.5% replied that they are likely to visit the parlour again, which amounts to 161 of the 246 participants. Meanwhile, 31 participants were unsure whether they will return to the parlour, and this indicates that with better offers and customer service, these 12.6% participants are likely to become loyal to the brand since they have no complaints about Panache Beauty. Only 22% of customers replied that they are not likely to visit Panache Beauty again.

5.21 Preference over other parlours

Another factor amounting to customer loyalty is that loyal customers will prefer the brand over any other market brands irrespective of better offers or pricing. When asked about this, 67.4% replied that they prefer Panache Beauty over any other brand in the market, which shows that 166 participants intend to remain loyal to Panache Beauty. It was also found that 45 participants amounting to 18.3%, were unsure whether they will return to the parlour. Still, there is a probability for these people to come back if provided with better customer service and offers. Only 14.2% responded that they are not likely to return to the parlour.

5.22 Reference

The third important dependent derivative is referring the brand to family and friends as a personal reference is the most reliable means to get new customers who are also likely to remain loyal to the brand. For the question on the likeliness of referring Panache Beauty to others, 51.6% responded that they are likely to refer the brand to people they know. At the same time, 19.1% said that they were unsure about this, while 19.3% said they are not likely to refer the brand to others. It can be seen that those who were likely to refer are less in number when compared with those who were willing to return to the parlour. Panache Beauty can get more customer references from their loyal customer base with new offers and discounts, and this is one of the best ways to gain new customers.

5.23 Correlation between dependent and independent variables

Correlation analysis will help understand the relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable. This will help determine how this relationship can be improved in a positive way to improve customer satisfaction and, thereby, customer retention. This will help Panache Beauty to plan offers and discounts to meet the requirements of customers and make the business attractive for them (Liang & Wang, 2014).

5.24 Frequency of visit and distance from Salon

The analysis aimed to determine whether the distance to the parlour has any effect on customer visits. During the analysis of independent derivatives, it was found that the majority of participants were travelling up to 10 miles to visit Panache than those who were staying in the proximity of 2 miles. On analysing the relationship between the two, it was found that the frequency of visit is in no way connected to the distance from the parlour. Customers who are loyal to the brand are ready to travel miles to get the service done, and thus, it was found that proximity was not a factor affecting the business of Panache Beauty.

5.25 Friendliness of staff and preference over other brands

The atmosphere of a beauty parlour plays a major role in customer retention, and among them, the most important factor is staff behaviour. In order to understand the relationship between friendly behaviour of staff and its effect on customer preference of the brand over others, the likeliness of reference and revisit to the salon, a correlation analysis was conducted. Though these factors are normally considered to have a very strong relationship with each other, in the case of Panache Beauty, it was found that friendliness of the staff has a very weak role in the decision of customers to visit the parlour again or not.

However, it was found that customers are more likely to refer to a parlour if they found the staff as more sincere and friendly. This shows that mere friendliness of staff cannot attract customers, but the visitors should feel that they are sincere in their work and can give the best results for the money they are paying. Thus, it was found that though friendliness has a positive correlation to customer loyalty, it alone can-do wonders, but instead, they should also be sincere in their work.

5.26 Experience and understanding of staff

The third factor considered for checking the relationship between customer loyalty and service was the experience and understanding of staff about the customer's needs and preferences. The correlation analysis showed that the influence of staff experience and understanding on customer loyalty and the

possibility to refer it to others is very less. However, customers are likely to return to the parlour if they found that the staff are experienced and understanding, but these are not the only factors that influence customers' decision.

5.27 Professionalism

The next factor tested was the professionalism of staff and its relation to customer loyalty. It was found that the staff's professionalism has a positive correlation with the likeliness of customers to revisit the brand and refer it to others. This shows that customers are looking for the professionalism of staff above friendliness and understanding through all these factors together than increase customer retention rates to a larger extent.

5.28 Quality and suitability of service

Two factors tested against customer loyalty are quality and suitability of service, and both were found to be positively correlated to customer loyalty. It was found that the decision of customers to recommend a parlour to others is mainly influenced by the quality of service rather than the friendly attitude or professionalism of the staff. Simultaneously, it was also found that customers who find the service suitable for themselves were more likely to prefer the parlour over other brands and refer it to others. This indicates that service quality is one of the most important factors that determine customer loyalty, and along with that, it will also bring in new customers to the parlour.

5.29 Environment and pricing

The final factors tested to understand customer loyalty was the environment of the parlour and pricing of products. The friendly environment had a weak positive correlation with reference to the likeliness of preferring Panache Beauty over others while the customers are more likely to return to the parlour and recommend it to others. This shows that customers are not likely to remain loyal just due to the fact that Panache Beauty offers a relaxing and comfortable environment as it is not the sole factor that influences the decision to choose a beauty parlour. However, when it comes to pricing, it was seen that customers were more likely to prefer Panache Beauty over other brands, revisit the parlour and recommend it to others, considering the pricing offered. This shows that the customers of Panache Beauty are satisfied with the services offered for the pricing charged, and they don't think that the services are priced higher.

The result shows that Panache Beauty can increase its customer base by becoming more professional when assessing the skin type and offering service in a friendly and comfortable manner. The survey

results also indicate that professionalism, including quality of service, friendliness and experience of staff and comfortable atmosphere, is the key to customer loyalty more than any other factor in the beauty parlour segment. Pricing at Panache Beauty is not considered as higher by customers. Hence, new offers and discounts are likely to increase customer retention and, at the same time, attract new customers through recommendation.

6 Chapter Six: Conclusion

After analysing literature and primary data, it was found that marketing needs to primarily focus on customer retention rather than the increasing number of customers or profit. From the in-depth analysis, it became clear that emphasis should be given to establishing long-term customer relationships and creating strategic alliances with customers. Thus, marketing should change its nature to relationship marketing in a wide range of ways, including ensuring better service, improving the surroundings to facilitate relaxing environment, employing skilled labours and providing special offers, packages, and customized treatments to meet customers' requirements and expectations. This, for sure, this can be considered a paradigm shift from focusing on the transaction to the relationship, as put by Webster (1992). Customer value is of utmost importance in service sectors like, especially in the beauty business. Though products are of importance, the prime focus should be on creating and maintaining a long-term relationship through better customer service, and marketing should focus on enhancing the entire organisation's quality rather than on the profit side alone. Thus, various factors like attraction, enhancement, and customer relationship maintenance are the most important factors to be considered by Panache Salon. The beauty parlour already possesses a good customer base, and to ensure customer retention and loyalty, they will have to think beyond commercial interest to enhance the relationship with existing customers while equipping themselves with new methods to attract new customers. Panache beauty will have to improve its customer relationship management practices by providing better quality services than its rivals to create and maintain a long-term relationship.

Further, the demographics studied as part of the survey helped to understand that characteristics like age, gender, occupation, marital status, education, profession, etc. also play a key role in persons' beauty decisions. It was understood that demographic characters, especially gender very much influence beauty treatment-related habits. Women were found more interested in skincare and beauty related matters. However, a large number of men were also found seeking such services. Another factor noted was that adults aged between the age bracket of 26 to 35 years are the ones who are most interested in taking beauty treatment, while those between 18 to 25 years comes second. The survey also clarifies that Panache should introduce products focusing on customers aged between 18 to 55 years. The salon needs to focus mainly on customers aged between 18 to 35 years, and for that above, Panache can introduce specific products that can deal with issues that affect the skin.

The survey also revealed that the majority of people visiting the parlour are employed persons who want to be presentable at work. This adds to the possibility of including special packages for working persons,

which can enhance their personality than merely going for a beauty treatment. Providing treatments exclusively for working persons can be a unique service offered by Panache, which can attract more clients belonging to the specific target group. Offering different treatments and services for working women and students is likely to bring in more customers due to the salon's uniqueness. Providing a wide range of treatments and offers for the customers based on such differentiation will also add more loyal customers.

The survey also pointed out that customers were not much concerned about the distance they need to travel to reach the parlour. This made it clear that there is no need for Panache to open new salons as part of its customer retention efforts. It was also found that at the present majority of customers who took part in the survey and all the customers who attended interviews were remaining loyal to the brand for a period between one to six months while about a quarter of the survey participants have been customers of Panache for over a year. This pointed out that customers are either looking for long term treatments and services or a short term ranging from one to six years. Hence Panache will need to have various packages that could retain its customers for a longer period. Loyalty bonus, club cards, discount offers for long-term customers, free treatments for long-term customers, etc. are methods that can help retain customers for a longer period. People who are used to visiting the parlour for six or more months can be retained for a longer period with an effective customer retention method. Over 75% of survey participants and all the interview participants have been visiting the salon for more than a month. Such customers are the most probable customers when it comes to loyalty. Panache needs to focus on customers who visit the parlour more than once and introduce them to loyalty programs. There should be a wide range of services and treatments for customers to choose from. Panache can also make suggestions and offer discounts for those who show genuine interest in continuing with the brand. This should be given more focus considering the fact that some of the customers who took part in the interview said that the salon could provide better or special offers to long-term customers.

The survey also pointed out that almost 50% of respondents used to visit the parlour on a fortnightly basis, while 37% used to visit only occasionally. Of the rest, 5.3% happened to visit on a regular basis, while 14.2% used to visit parlour once a week. Panache needs to focus on those who visit the parlour more often than the occasional ones, as they are more likely to remain loyal. One method is to provide a better offer for those visiting the parlour on a weekly basis than the offers made to those who visit on a fortnightly basis. This method might be helpful for customers like the interview participant who visit the parlour every now and then even to meet their friends. Panache can also provide special services to such customers or loyalty, or membership cards will also be of great help. Thus, the demographic factors show that a wide range of products targeting various age groups and employment status is the most important

factor to be taken care of as part of a customer loyalty programme. On the other side, it is also important to introduce offers, discounts and loyalty programmes considering the frequency of visits and the time period for which the customer has been visiting the parlour.

As indicated in a literature review, customer retention and loyalty are also about various other aspects like staff behaviour, service quality, skill and experience of staff, discount deals and offers, value for money, the suitability of serviced provided and pricing. Vesel and Zabkar (2009) are of the opinion that staff plays a crucial role in communicating with the customers and collaborating the values of the organisation to the public. Effective and pleasant communication is also considered as a means to draw customer attention and retention. Hence, such factors tested in the survey and interview questions regarding friendliness and skill of staff have given fruitful insights into customer retention methods.

The friendliness of the staff was counted as a positive factor when it came to customer retention, and the survey showed that 47% of respondents were positive in this regard, while all the interview participants said that they find the staff friendly. Another 24.4% took a neutral stance when asked about the friendliness and sincerity of staff at Panache. The answers indicate that customers consider the behaviour of staff while visiting a parlour and friendly and sincere staff is an added advantage for the organisation. The beauty industry falls under the high experience quality category, as explained by Zeithaml (1981), where the behaviour and experience of the staff are of at most importance in maintaining customer relationships. When asked about the staff's experience at Panache Beauty and their capability to understand the needs and preferences of the customer, all the interview participants and over 47 of survey respondents answered positively. They either agreed or strongly agreed that the parlour staff are experienced enough to understand the preferences and needs of customers. As many as 63 respondents counting to 25%, remained neutral, indicating that they have no complaints about the staff. The result is a strong indication of the well-experienced staff of Panache Beauty, who can play a great role in retaining customers and ensuring customer loyalty.

Another factor that Panache beauty salon should take into consideration is the cost. Before fixing the price for each service, the beauty salon should make sure that it is affordable for prospective customers and that the service provided is worth the amount spent by the customer. It is important that the customers are satisfied with the results of the treatment they undergo at the parlour. They will also be expecting satisfactory service for beauty parlour is not only considered as a place to fix beauty-related issues but for some customers, it is a place to relax, forgetting all their daily chores, like the interview participant who visits the salon with friends even if she does not need treatment. Hence Panache salon must ensure a soothing and calm environment where customers can decide on the treatments and services without worrying about the time they need to spend there. Customers are also likely to opt for time-consuming

treatments or more services in a good environment and staff behaviour. This was evident from the fact that during the survey majority participants replied that they don't mind the distance to parlour from home but were concerned about the ambience and behaviour of staff.

One of the major factors that add to customer retention is customer loyalty, and this is an area Panache should work on. To ensure customer loyalty, Panache salons will have to instigate positive behaviour among the staff towards both existing and prospective customers and vendors and obtain stabilization. As put forward by Bruhn (2011), customer loyalty is achieved by satisfying their expectations. While dealing with customers, the staff needs to keep in mind that there is a tendency among customers to compare the services they have availed earlier, both at Panache as well as at rivals, with their recent experience. This was evident from the fact that the interview participants were repeatedly comparing Panache Beauty with competitors while answering questions on quality, staff expertise, pricing, offers and discounts etc. The description will attract new customers by those who recommended them, and it is important to meet their expectations. Such comparisons often increase enthusiasm among customers, which leads to appreciation and satisfaction. Hence, it is important for the service provided to meet customer expectations if not able to exceed it. What is to be kept in mind is that each customer has a different level to evaluate satisfaction, and hence, each one should be dealt with uniquely. Some customers might admire the ambience while another might be interested in service quality or pricing. There might be some who wish to get the service they intend to while another might be looking for suggestions. Thus, the staff needs to understand the requirement of each customer and behave accordingly. Thus, it can be said that customer retention and loyalty is part and parcel of a wide range of actions beginning from the reception accorded to the payment made by the customer.

The survey and interview analysis has made it clear that Panache salon will have to begin its efforts to ensure customer satisfaction from the treatment given to existing customers. The first step to be taken is to make sure that the ambience at the parlour is a relaxing and soothing one, which can invoke a desire among customers to spend more time there. The staff should be given pieces of training to improve their knowledge to analyse each skin type and make suggestions. They should also be equipped with the skill to manage customers by understanding their needs and expectations.

The better ambience and customer management are not enough to ensure customer satisfaction in a beauty parlour business. It is also dependent on the quality of products used as well as the price of services. It is very difficult to gain and retain customer loyalty in the beauty parlour business as it is a very competitive market. With a large number of products and competitors, customers are most likely to switch between brands. In order to retain customers, Panache will have to be well conversant with customer behaviour as well as needs. It should work towards achieving the emotional and physical

loyalty of customers. Leventhal (2006) states that loyalty can be explained as a state of mind achieved through a set of attitudes and desires. The staff of Panache salons should be able to understand the attitudes and desires of customers and provide services accordingly. Other than favourable ambience and good behaviour, there are some methods to retain the customer's interest. The focus must be one method to improve customer satisfaction and, thus, loyalty. Some clients may be attracted to service while others may look for products, incentives or price paid. As understood from the analysis of interview data, some customers consider all these factors while choosing a facility. In addition to this is the exchange of information, which helps to create a link with the customer. Thus, communication is one of the major factors in gaining loyalty. Besides offering better services and treatment to customers, the staff at Panache can also provide them with useful beauty tips that are often very much valued.

The literature review has made it clear that customer loyalty is mainly about the organisation's initiatives to capture customer's attention, and some of these methods include loyalty bonus, price commitment, special packages, etc. A loyalty bonus is a method in which select customers are rewarded in the form of discounts or gifts as a token of appreciation for their loyalty towards the company. This is one method that Panache beauty can try. The salon can offer special packages, price discounts and even free services for loyal customers. Such actions will help retain their loyalty and, at the same time, encourage them to refer new customers. As word of mouth is the most effective marketing method keeping customers loyal is also likely to help Panache Beauty with spreading good words about the services. Often, customers gained through reference tend to visit the salon with a positive prejudice. Such customers are also more likely to return to the salon seeking services, and the probability of them being loyal is more. However, it is also important to keep in mind that those visiting the salon through reference might be having high expectations, and it is important to keep up with their needs and requirements or else the salon is likely to lose one of its loyal customers as well. But, with quality services and treatment, Panache beauty can easily add more loyal customers through referrals.

The survey also points to the possibility of inertia loyalty, explained in the literature review. As pointed out by Leventha (2006), Panache salon can compel customers to remain loyal to its offerings. This is achieved by creating obstacles that will prevent the client from approaching competitors; for this, Panache will have to introduce specific terms and conditions in its loyalty card scheme whereby the customer will have to pay a specific amount while becoming a member of the scheme. Along with that, Panache can also include reward points to the card, which the customer can redeem towards payment for service. A specific limit can also be fixed for redeeming the point, like converting 100 reward points to \$10. Such schemes will force the customer to revisit the parlour, spend the amount paid towards the

membership fees, and get the points redeemed. This can be read in line with the fact that the majority of participants of the survey found schemes offered by the parlour as a major attraction.

As per the survey results and response to the interview, Panache's products and services were the most attractive factors that drew them to the parlour. Panache can make the most out of this by introducing unique products and creating a monopoly in the market. Such products must be ones which can suit the preferred tastes and preferences of customers. For example, suppose the majority of customers of the parlour are looking for facial treatments. In that case, the salon can offer a wide variety of facial treatment options from which the customer can choose from. Such treatments can be offered according to skin types, skin conditions, weather conditions, specific occasions etc. These facilities can be counted as convenience loyalty, as explained by Leventha (2006), a situation that forces a customer to remain loyal and make a deliberate decision not to look for an alternative product or service. With so many different products to choose from, the customer is more likely to remain loyal as there is no need to search for another organisation to try a new product.

Assessing skin types and suggesting appropriate treatment for the customers is another important factor that can ensure loyal customers. It is important that the staff is able to understand the expectations and needs of customers and, at the same time, assess their skin types to suggest the best suitable product for them not only to get the best results but also to avoid any negative reaction. A skilled staff should be able to assess the skin type and spot any differences in the face and neck skin. The staff should also be skilled in identifying the skin condition and its characteristics before giving suggestions. The matter was considered in the survey and interview and for the question on the capability of staff at Panache Beauty in assessing the skin condition above 43% of survey participants responded positively while all six participants of the interview were happy about it. The respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that the staff could make assessments about skin type before giving any recommendations or using products. The result points to the fact that Panache can positively influence customers and thus retain more of them if the staff are more equipped with such skills.

Quality of service and treatment is of great importance in a service sector like beauty care (Chase, 2013), and Panache can achieve this by ensuring that the staff has the skill and knowledge to respond to the needs and expectations of customers in an efficient manner. In this regard, all the interview participants and over 52% of survey respondents agreed or strongly agreed that Panache Beauty provides quality services. Increasing the quality further will help Panache keep on with its existing customers and gain a better impression from future customers and those who remained neutral.

Suitability of services and treatments provided to the skin of the client is another factor that comes together. The issue was also included in the list of questions for the interview and survey. It is a known

fact that a wide range of chemicals is used in beauty treatments, and there is a wide possibility for that to go wrong or have a negative effect on one's skin. Therefore, the staff must be capable of assessing the skin type and using the most suitable products that suit the skin of the client. Such assessments require a lot of skill and precision, some of which can be acquired from classes and others from experience. Panache Beauty needs to make sure that the staff are talented and equipped enough, with knowledge, experience and skill, to make correct assessments on the skin and the use of materials for a beauty treatment. When asked about the suitability of products used at Panache parlour, only 24% had a negative opinion, while over 54% agreed that the products used are well suited for their skin. However, another 25% of respondents chose to remain neutral in their opinion. Thus, it is clear that the majority of customers are happy and satisfied with the use of products at Panache Beauty, and this also points out that working out on this factor will help retain more customers. All these can be achieved by giving training to the staff, as mentioned in the recommendations.

Loyal customers are those who intend to visit the parlour again, and it is important to know what percentage of customers would choose Panache Beauty over competitor brands. This will help the management plan customer retention and loyalty programmes keeping in view its customers' mindset. The question was included in the survey and interview to assess what percentage of customers was willing to visit the parlour again. All the customers who took part in the interview were happy to visit the salon again. Over 65% of survey respondents seemed more than happy to visit the parlour again, while only 12% were not interested in the brand. Twenty-one respondents were not sure about the decision. This percentage that Panache Beauty should aim to attract while making efforts to ensure that the positive ones are retained. From the survey results, it can be assumed that various factors that influence customer satisfaction and, retention are in existence at Panache Beauty. Still, the salon can increase the rate by introducing more effective methods.

Customer preferences also play a crucial role in customer retention and loyalty. With the beauty business being a service sector is experiencing the toughest of competition, Panache Beauty must offer uniqueness in all factors that could add to customer loyalty. To the question of preference to Panache Beauty over competitors above, 67% responded positively, while 18% was unsure of their preference. Loyalty here can be referred to as convenience loyalty, where customers would remain loyal to a product and won't look for other brands to remain loyal to the brand alone. Panache can achieve this by providing customised and individual service and unique products as per the needs and expectations of each customer. The management needs to make sure that the customers are loyal to the products solely offered by Panache. As no other brand can offer the same service, those loyal to the product/service will remain loyal to the brand.

Other than methods to ensure customer retention and loyalty, Panache Beauty should also look for new customers. One of the most effective means to gain loyal customers is through a reference. Customers referred by other loyal customers are more likely to have an open mind to accept the facilities and services provided by Panache. At times such customers also tend to share the same interests and needs, which will be easy for the staff to find out. However, they are also likely to have high expectations from the brand, which the staff need to keep in mind while dealing with them. Though offering special discounts and special care are likely to impress such clients, it is also important to make sure that they are provided with the highest possible service quality. Such an action will help to meet their expectations easier. The probability of such customers remaining loyal is high, and hence giving special care and treatment will come for the benefit of the company.

On analysing the literature, interview and survey results, it can be concluded that Panache Beauty is one of the most preferred brands in the beauty industry. The majority of its clients are loyal. However, integrating more effective methods, including new products and improving staff's skill will help Panache Beauty increase its loyal customer base.

7 Chapter Seven: Recommendations

This study embraced four aspects in order to gain a more accurate perspective on matters affecting customer relationships at Panache Beauty. Various factors like gender, sex, age, proximity to parlour etc. were considered as primary factors while a deeper look was conducted by analysing dependent and independent factors and their correlation to each other. Primary results and literature review proved that mainly women tend to attend parlours rather than men. The research study also confirmed that women belonging to the age group of 18 to 55 years of age and the majority of them were working women. On analysing survey results, it was found that working women are more beauty conscious as they want to maintain their looks while mingling with the public, including their peers and clients. Various other factors like proximity to Panache Beauty, the environment at the parlour, and frequency of visits showed that distance and environment are not factors that influence customers' decision through a few numbers of customers are likely to consider these factors while deciding on visiting a salon. On a detailed analysis it was found that most independent variables like friendliness of staff, service quality and offers, which are otherwise considered very important in maintaining customer relationship, did not have a great positive correlation with dependent variables like the possibility to revisit the parlour, recommend it to others and preferring Panache Beauty over other brands.

Hence, this section will provide an outlook into various factors that matter most in the case of Panache Beauty when it comes to customer relationship and what factors the researcher thinks will help increase customer base and better customer retention. This will be done in concurrence with the findings obtained by analysing survey results. Recommendations will be given for each factor identified to influence the customer relationship of Panache Beauty and are expected to improve customer retention and loyalty. As in the analysis and findings, recommendations too will be given under three main categories – demographics, independent and dependent factors.

7.1 Demographics

The survey was conducted among 246 customers of Panache Beauty, and six factors like gender, age, employment status, proximity, duration of association with parlour and frequency of visits, which were considered important to identify the customer base, were included under this category. It was found 77% of the parlour customers were women, and of the participants, only 56 were men. The result points to the fact that the customer base of Panache Beauty largely constitutes women, and hence, the main target must be women, who are concerned about their looks.

Another factor considered under the demographic category is the age of participants. Survey results showed that women between the age of 18 and 55 are more conscious about their looks, and among them, it is mainly young women, between the ages group of 26 to 55, who are more concerned. This points to the fact that women tend to become more conscious about their looks mostly after they pass 25-years-of age, and this attitude continues till they get near to senior position, which is 55 years, just five years left to reach the status of a senior citizen. The age factor must be read along with employment status as it was another criterion considered in the survey. It was found that 84.2% of participants were employed, and 35.8% were self-employed. This points to the fact that women who are employed and capable of spending their own money are more likely to visit beauty parlour than financially dependent. Only 15.9% of the participants were students, and they might be spending the money from their parents/guardians. Another factor to be noted is that those employed, rather than running their self-employed entity, wanted to look good and be presentable.

Considering the age and employment status of participants, it is found that working women between the age of 25 to 55 are the most potential customers of Panache Beauty mainly because they are earning and are willing to spend money as they consider it important to maintain their looks while at work. Hence, introducing products and treatments, mainly aiming at issues faced by young and middle-aged women, will greatly benefit Panache Beauty. Main issues faced by women in their middle age include age spots, dry skin, wrinkles and sagging, grey hair as well as hair loss, thinning of eyelashes and brows etc. On the other side, women below 35 years would be asking for facials, haircuts and hair treatments, spa, waxing, pedicures and manicures etc. Hence, having expertise in beauty treatments and offering special treatments for women between 26 to 55 will be most beneficial as they should be the target customers of Panache Beauty.

The survey and interviews revealed that the pricing at Panache Beauty is acceptable to the customers. However, reducing pricing for regular customers or treatments that are most in-demand is another tactic that might help attract more customers or retain existing ones for a longer period. This is all the more beneficial to attract unemployed customers, including students, who cannot spend larger amounts on beauty treatments. Further, this is also likely to persuade customers to choose Panache over other brands in the market.

7.2 Independent factors

The first independent variable considered during the survey and interviews was the staff's sincerity and friendliness as these two factors are considered the most important elements valued by customers, especially in the service sector. Survey results pointed to the fact that almost half of the survey

participants consider the staff at Panache Beauty as friendly and sincere, while 24% gave a neutral opinion while all interview participants found Panache staff friendly. Communication with customers is the key to establishing a relationship with them. Communication is all the more important in the beauty segment as it is the only method to identify the customer's needs and expectations. The staff needs to understand the exact requirement of the customer before suggesting any treatment.

At times the customer might be demanding a particular beauty treatment. Still, if the staff can understand the purpose, they will be able to propose better treatments if needed, and this will help establish better customer relationships. Further, it is also important that the staff should have a clear knowledge of the purpose of each beauty treatment offered at the parlour. For this Panache, Beauty will have to provide training to their staff to increase their skill and knowledge. A staff who is experienced and equipped with the necessary skill and knowledge will be able to make a correct assessment for the customer and provide the best available treatment to meet their expectation. Such kind of services will always be valued, and customers are more likely to return to a parlour that they can rely on.

Along with friendliness, staff should also be equipped with the knowledge to identify each skin type and offer beauty treatments accordingly. The ability to assess skin type and offer treatments accordingly is an added advantage for the staff who is experienced. Though some of this skill can be acquired with experience, knowledge in such matters will be much more helpful, and this will be possible if Panache Beauty can equip their staff through classes and workshops. The management can arrange skill development classes or workshops for the staff, which will help them acquire knowledge of the latest technologies and other beauty treatments. Another method is to conduct combined workshops for staff and customers. This is a good method to create customer awareness, which will also make it easy for the staff to convince them of the benefits of each treatment and why they are referred to them. This will also help develop faith in customer minds about the quality of service offered by Panache Beauty and acquire better customer retention and loyalty.

Customer relationship is not only about communication, offers, good service and atmosphere, but it also involves planning services and products according to target customers. Customer valuations, information gained from them and knowledge play a crucial place in planning. Panache Salon will have to think about different products and services in addition to what is being offered. They should also think about the pricing that customers will be willing to pay and how the value of the service or result can be raised in the customer's eyes. Eco consultancy's marketing report states that it is easy to retain a customer than acquiring a new one. Hence, Panache Salon needs to derive measures to retain existing customers. Adopting measures to manage customer retention by improving the company's relationship will help in

business growth, and profitability and Panache Salon will have to adopt new methods to create continually, maintain, and develop the customer relationship.

Figure 14: Customer retention methods

(Author, 2020)

In order to retain existing customers and to increase their loyalty, Panache will have to understand their needs and requirements and refocus the company's strategy to develop plans to serve its customers better. Retain those customers who are neutral in their opinion with regard to dependent, and independent variables itself will bring in a huge difference in the customer base of the beauty salon. The company will have to adopt relationship marketing techniques to manage relationships with customers and unsatisfied customers. One method is to arrange service meetings where customers can open up about the issues they are facing at the parlour or how they want to improve the services as well as new treatments or services expected at the salon. This method will be of great help in customer relationship management as the company will get to know the customer's needs and introduce changes accordingly. Another method is arranging a facility where customers can write down their demands or a drop box where they can drop their paper slips requirements. Though both these will be very helpful, the second method will be highly helpful for Panache to improve their services because those customers who do not want to reveal their names will also get a chance to write down any complaints they might be hesitant to write down in the book. Another method is to keep software to update the requirements and treatment details of the regular customer by which the staff will be able to know the customer's requirements as soon as they visit the parlour. This will also help keep track of the requirements of regular customers and make improvements according to their expectations, which will increase customer loyalty and, thus, retention. Once Panache Salon can clearly identify the frequency of regular customer visits, they can give

special offers for them, like free hair treatment or facial during the sixth visit or a special discount on completion of six months, etc.

Establishing a good relationship with the customer is the sole of customer retention, and various techniques are used to achieve this. Various policies and measures that could establish a relationship, create a network and facilitate interaction with the customer are methods that can help. Any company needs to establish four social connections to ensure new customers and retention of existing ones. Services provided to each customer should be determined according to their relationship with the company. Methods used to establish a relationship with a satisfied and loyal customer should be different from an unsatisfied one or a new one. The methods adopted for establishing customer relationships should be capable of keeping the company and its products in the customer's minds. Various factors like price to quality of service must form such methods as these factors play a crucial role in maintaining long-term customer relationships (Bergström & Leppänen 2011, 452).

One method to achieve this is to offer targeted service to individual customers and for different segments. However, it is important to ensure that all techniques adopted by Panache Salon aiming for customer retention facilitate two-way communication, rather than a one-way method. Customers have a chance to express their needs and wishes. This is very important as happy and satisfied customers are more likely to return to the parlour and recommend it to their friends and relatives. This acts as a free advertisement and is more effective than paid ones. Panache Salon can make their customers do this by providing a product or service that stands out from its competitors. The company can decide on or develop such a product or service by understanding their customers' needs and wishes.

Panache Salon can conduct a survey among its customers to know their priorities and needs and customise their products accordingly. A survey will also help the company find out potential customer needs and develop products and services accordingly. However, it is important to retain existing packages and services as not all customers will be happy about new products. The majority of them might be visiting the parlour to get their regular treatments done. The survey is also a good method to understand the opinion of the customer on the products and services provided by the salon. This will help them improve their services and products to keep up with the expectations of customers. Another benefit is that a survey will help Panache Salon to understand new trends in the market, which are in demand and provide them. From the data collected in the survey, Panache Salon will also customize their services according to age group or frequency of visits. The company will also be able to provide training to their staff to gain knowledge and develop skills in more demand from the customer. For example, suppose the survey shows that customers are looking forward to getting better haircuts from Panache Salon. In that case, the company can recruit someone who is more experienced in doing haircuts or provide training to

existing staff to improve their skills in the area. Thus, the company will be able to improve its service and meet the expectation of the customer.

Ensuring customised services and treatments is another method to retain customer priority over other similar brands. This method will be more helpful in customer retention as the staff will be aware of the needs of existing customers and having a good relationship with them. Under such situations, it will be possible for the staff to ask the customer if they want any other treatment/service or if they prefer to try something different. The staff can also offer specialized service/treatment depending on the needs or priorities of the customer. For example, if the staff finds out that an existing customer has started developing wrinkles, they can suggest treatments for the same, which a satisfied customer is more likely to accept than a new one. Such considerations are mostly valued by existing customers who already have a good rapport with the staff and are confident about the service. In the case of a new customer, experienced staff will be able to give suggestions if the customer needs one, which might be an added value in some cases.

Another method that Panache Beauty can adopt is discounts and offers. Providing exclusive benefits to long term customers is an effective method to retain them for a longer period by ensuring loyalty. Panache Salon can introduce a loyalty card by which they can assess the number of visits by a customer and offer gifts according to service use. Another method is to provide a bonus point during each visit, which the customer can redeem for money after reaching a certain limit. Panache Salon can also offer customers a discount for treatments or products based on loyalty bonus points acquired. The loyalty card is a proven strategy for customer retention and offering discounts for newcomers is also likely to bring in new customers. However, the parlour should be careful while offering discounts to new customers as there is a chance for the new customers to be a single-time visitor. In this case, Panache Salon will suffer losses as they are offering existing services without compromising on quality, and the treatment/service will be under-priced. Existing customers will be happy to purchase products from the Salon at a discount price. It will be even more attractive to customers if Panache Salon sells the products they normally use for treatments at the salon. Hair styling and haircuts are needed for every customer, and a discount in this segment is also likely to attract customers. Special discounts can be given to exclusive customers who will get their hair done only from Panache Salon. Offering discounts for facials, manicures, pedicures, bridal makeup etc. are also likely to bring in more customers. Bridal makeup is something sought after by brides, family members, bridesmaids etc. A discount in this section is likely to bring in a greater number of customers, especially during the wedding season.

Loyalty cards are a very effective means to ensure customer retention. Providing special discounts and offers to members will encourage them to return to the salon and thus ensure retention. Panache Salon

can introduce membership cards to its customers and club it with other discounts and special offers. Other than common discounts and offer schemes, Panache can also introduce special discounts for members. Another method is to provide bonus points on every visit. Customers should be allowed to redeem bonus points for cash or some beauty treatments once the points reach a certain limit. Bonus points can be either fixed according to the customer's money, for example, one point for every £10. Bonus points can also be fixed according to services provided, like five points for a manicure. Various other schemes can also be brought under membership schemes like providing free service at frequent intervals.

For example, regular customers can be given a free eyebrow fixing once every three months or a free manicure to those spending a minimum amount for treatments. While introducing such offers, Panache Salon should always make sure that the offers and discounts provided to members should always be better than those without membership. The Salon should also make sure that the offers and discounts are on par with its competitors. It is important to communicate about the membership facility and its benefits to all the customers visiting the parlour. This can be done at the initial stage itself, instead of waiting until the customer has finished the treatments. This will give the customer enough time to think about membership options and inquire about details without spending more time in the salon. While introducing such schemes, Panache Salon must create awareness among its staff so that they can communicate about the offers to customers.

The staff should be clearly aware of the scheme's benefits, like redeeming points, special discounts and offers, etc. They should be given the training to speak convincingly to the customer. It is not necessary to introduce all the benefits in the initial stage itself. Special discounts or free offers can be either communicated to the members as a surprise, during their visit to the parlour or inform them as mail, message or through social media. Mail and other means of communication is a good method as it will tempt the customer to visit the parlour. In such a case, the customer is also likely to introduce a new customer during the visit. Providing a free treatment as a surprise is also beneficial as the customer is likely to return to the salon expecting similar surprises in future.

In the beauty industry, most service providers fail to retain their customers to competitors as they fail to understand the expectations of the customer and meet their needs and wants. This is mainly due to the similarity of services offered, and the staff of most parlours lack the skill to convince their customers on the unique selling point of their products and services. One of the reasons behind the failure of staff is lack of interest, and it is mainly because they don't gain anything from putting extra effort to acquire new skills or knowledge and to ensure customer loyalty by informing them about the uniqueness of the salon. Motivation plays a key role in active participation, and it is the most important ingredient behind every effort. Such attempts by staff are of utmost importance, and a positive result is possible only when

people are willing to do such things on their own, without any pressure from management. Other than training and workshops to improve the staff's skill and knowledge, Panache Salon can also introduce a scheme under which staff will benefit from customer retention. Panache Salon can offer remuneration for the staff, who are successful in persuading a customer to get new treatments done than the one they came asking for or for referring the parlour to others.

Reward programs are likely to increase enthusiasm among the staff to perform better, and they will put in more effort to ensure customers' satisfaction. This will also introduce a competitive spirit among the staff, which will help improve their productivity. However, it is important to make sure that such measures should not lead to too much competition among the staff or else it will destroy the company's reputation. Another method to motivate the staff is to offer them a share of the company's yearly profit or a hike in salary in accordance with the company's performance during the last financial year. Panache Salon can also offer incentives for staff on par with their performance. An incentive system can be introduced on a yearly basis, by the end of the financial year, or on a short-term basis. Short term incentive plans are likely to be more beneficial as employees will be able to assess their performance at frequent intervals and make necessary improvements.

Further, management will also understand the issues faced by employees and help them improve, which will further help increase customer retention and loyalty. The short-term analysis will also help the company introduce new methods and treatments. This can be done on a seasonal basis like new packages and treatments for wedding seasons, winter season, summer, festival season, etc. The management can also arrange for special rewards for employees if the salon gets more customers than expected during a certain season. Employees can also be rewarded with free beauty treatments, which would be very much encouraging and welcoming.

The environment also forms a major factor in attracting customers and ensuring their loyalty and other factors like right pricing, offers, discounts, quality of service, staff experience, and ability to determine skin quality. Correlation analysis between dependent and independent variables showed a weak relationship between various variables like the distance between salon and residence. Still, factors like experience and ability of staff to determine the skin type and to suggest appropriate treatments considering the requirement of the client had a positive correlation to chances of revisit, the recommendation to others and preferring Panache Salon over other brands. Other factors that showed a positive correlation were the quality of services and the environment at the salon. Hence it is very important to ensure that the salon provides a good and relaxing environment for its clients.

Customers spent a good amount of time at beauty salons as any treatment; however, it takes at least twenty minutes to finish. Usual treatments like facial will take a minimum of thirty minutes or more, and

hence, it is important to make sure that the atmosphere at salons is comfortable and relaxing for the clients. From the literature review, it was understood that women consider beauty parlours as a place to get their beauty treatments done and as places of relaxation where they can spend some quality time to calm down their body and mind. Thus, the parlour must provide an environment where customers find themselves comfortable enough to spend whatever time they wish to be there. It is also likely for a customer who is spending more time at the salon to choose for some other treatments which she had not intended while visiting. As quality and professionalism count equal to the environment, Panache Salon should ensure a good atmosphere at the parlour. This can be done by facilitating mild entertainment facilities, like providing books and periodical or watching television or enjoying music.

Introducing a customer referral campaign among customers and the staff is also an effective method. Such campaigns provide double benefit by driving in new business and increasing the reach and brand awareness through mouth publicity, an added publicity method above regular ones adopted by the salon. Asking existing customers for referral, either in person during the visit or by other means of communication like a phone call, message, mail, or social media, is likely to be effective. Once the parlour is able to establish a positive relationship with the customers through friendly and quality service that meets their expectations, it is easy for the management to ask for their support.

Figure 15: Relationship management methods

Source: (Author, 2020)

Good service always ensures a positive relationship, which will be used for reaping benefits in the future. Reaching out to customers through emails and social media is also crucial, but it is also important to pay attention to frequency. Mailing should be limited to once or twice a week or during the announcement of special offers while social media campaign needs more attention. Having accounts on social media like Facebook, Instagram and Twitter, and keeping updated through the latest postings will help customers know about the latest offers and products/treatments available at the salon. Posts can be on various topics ranging from skin and hair care to new trends in nail designs or wellness measures and relaxation techniques.

As the beauty industry has become increasingly challenging and competitive, with more and more brands entering the field and several kinds of specialized treatments to choose from, it is important for Panache Beauty to adopt methods for customer retention. Panache Salon will have to introduce a mixed strategy consisting of campaigns, offers, discounts, improving service quality, skills and knowledge of staff, new products/treatments and equipping the salon with better facilities to ensure a relaxed and comfortable atmosphere.

Figure 16: Strategy to be adopted

Source: (Author, 2020)

Retention of existing customers is the primary concern; it will take time for new customers to develop a taste for the services and treatments offered at a salon and get a clear idea as to how it differs from other brands in the market.

Chances are more for new customers to look for other brands and not continue with Panache Salon after a single visit. Hence, the best strategy is to ensure customer retention by adopting new methods to satisfy those survey participants who gave a neutral opinion. It was found that for almost all questions, the majority of participants gave a positive reply while only one fourth or less than that number of customers had a negative opinion. It was found that almost the same number of customers had a neutral opinion with regard to various independent components like the experience of staff, the capability to judge skin type, quality of service etc. This shows that Panache Salon can considerably increase its customer base if they are successful in adopting and implementing strategies that could satisfy neutral customers. It is in line with this idea that the majority of recommendations are made in this section. The main intent is customer retention with better-skilled staff and special offers through acquiring new customers and forming a part of building a customer base.

References

- Abdullatif, A., Morhtar, S. & Yuseff, R (2010). The driver of efficient service delivery and caller satisfaction: A model of CRM customer contact cantors in Malaysia, *International of Management Studies*.
- Ackroyd, S. (1981). *Data collection in context*. Longman.
- Aihie, O. & Bennani, A. (2012). An exploratory study of the implementation of customer relationship management of strategic business process management, *Journal*, 13(1), 139-164.
- Al-Ababneh, M. M. (2020) Linking ontology, epistemology and research methodology. *Science & Philosophy*. 8(1). 75-91
- Ali, A., Khan, A., Ahmed, I. & Shahzad, W (2011). Determinants of Pakistani consumers' green purchase behaviour: Some insights from a developing country," *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(3), pp.217-226.
- Ali, Z., & Bhaskar, S. B. (2016). Basic statistical tools in research and data analysis. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*, 60(9), 662–669. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5049.190623>
- Alipour, M., & Mohammadi, M. H. (2011). The Effect of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) On Achieving Competitive Advantage of Manufacturing Tractor. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 11(5), 27–36.
- Allwood, C. M. (2012). The distinction between qualitative and quantitative research methods is problematic. *Quality & Quantity*, 46(5), 1417–1429. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-011-9455-8>
- Amado, A., Cortez, P., Rita, P., & Moro, S. (2018). Research trends on Big Data in Marketing: A text mining and topic modelling based literature analysis. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 24(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2017.06.002>
- Anastas, J., W. (1999). *Research Design for Social Work and Human Services. Flexible Methods: Descriptive Research* (2nd ed). New York: Columbia University Press.
- Angamuthu, B. (2015). Impact of customer relationship management on customer satisfaction and its role in customer loyalty and retention practices in the hotel sector. *BVIMSR's Journal of Management Research*, 7(1), 43-52.
- Angamuthu, B. (2015). Source: Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India. *Journal of Management Research*, 44(7), 3–5.
- Angelova, B. (2011). Measuring Customer Satisfaction with Service Quality Using (ACSI Model). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 232–258. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss.v1i2.35>

- Apostolico, A. A. et al., (2015). The “Salon Safety Quiz” For Pre-/Post-Evaluation Assessment When Training Young Cosmetology Workers In Public Secondary Schools. *Journal of Chemical Health and Safety*, 22(2), pp. 14-22.
- Armoudoum, P. & Ben-Shabat, H. (2012). *Beauty: Only as deep as Customer Experience*. A.T. Kearney.
- Arthur, W., & Villado, A. J. (2008). The importance of distinguishing between constructs and methods when comparing predictors in personnel selection research and practice. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(2), 435–442. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.93.2.435>
- Asian Beauty Secrets: Ancient and Modern Tips from the Far East*. (n.d.). Bush Street Press.
- Athanassopoulou, P., & Johne, A. (2014). Effective communication with lead customers in developing new banking products. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 22(2), 100–125. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652320410521719>
- Azzam, Z., A., M. (2014). The impact of customer relationship management on customer satisfaction in the banking industry –A case of Jordan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(32), 99-108.
- Baird, C. H., & Parasnis, G. (2011). From social media to social customer relationship management. *Strategy & Leadership*, 39(5), 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10878571111161507>
- Bandopadhyay, D., A. (2007). *Nutrition Survey of school children, Navi Nagar Mumbai*. *Medical Journal and Forum India*, 44(1), 31-34.
- Banerjee, A., & Chaudhury, S. (2010). Statistics without tears: Populations and samples. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal*, 19(1), 60–65. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-6748.77642>
- Banerjee, A., Chitnis, U., Jadhav, S., Bhawalkar, J., & Chaudhury, S. (2009). Hypothesis testing, type I and type II errors. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal*, 18(2), 127. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-6748.62274>
- Baran, R.J. & Galka, R. (2013), *CRM, the foundation of contemporary marketing strategy*. Routledge, 711 Third Avenue, New York: Routledge.
- Barnat, M., Bosse, E., & Trautwein, C. (2017). The Guiding Role of Theory in Mixed-Methods Research: Combining Individual and Institutional Perspectives on the Transition to Higher Education. In *Theory and Method in Higher Education Research* (Vol. 3, pp. 1–19). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Barnham, C. (2015). Quantitative and qualitative research: perceptual foundations. *International Journal of Market Research*, 57(6), 837–854.
- Beltman, E.P. 2013, *Customer relationship management*: Pearson Education Limited, Edinburg Gate.

- Berry, L. L. (2013), "Relationship marketing of service: Growing interest, emerging perspectives," *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 23(4), 236-245.
- Berry, L. L. (1983). Relationship marketing. In L. L. Berry, G. L. Shostack, & G. D. Upah (Eds.), *Services marketing conference proceedings*. Chicago: American Marketing Association.
- Berry, L. L. (2013). Relationship marketing of services - Perspectives between 1983 and 2000. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 1(1), 59 – 77.
- Betini, M., Volpato, E. S. N., Anastácio, G. D. J., de Faria, R. T. B. G., & El Dib, R. (2014). Choosing the right journal for your systematic review: Journals publishing systematic reviews. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, 20(6), 834–836. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jep.12196>
- Bhat, S. A., & Darzi, M. A. (2016). Customer relationship management: An approach to competitive advantage in the banking sector by exploring the mediational role of loyalty. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(3), 388–410. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-11-2014-0160>
- Bigné, J. E., Mattila, A. S., & Andreu, L. (2008). The impact of experiential consumption cognitions and emotions on behavioural intentions. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 22(4), 303–315. <https://doi.org/10.1108/08876040810881704>
- Bishop, M. (2017). Open Data Kit: Implications for the Use of Smartphone Software Technology for Questionnaire Studies in International Development. Transcription.
- Bogomolova, S. (2011). Service quality perceptions of solely loyal customers. *International Journal of Market Research*, 53(6), 793. <https://doi.org/10.2501/IJMR-53-6-793-810>
- Bolton, R. N., Kannan, P. K., & Bramlett, M. D. (2010). Implications of Loyalty Program Membership and Service Experiences for Customer Retention and Value. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 28(1), 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070300281009>
- Bose, R. (2012). Customer relationship management: Key components for IT success. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 102(2), 89 – 97.
- Bose, R. (2015). Customer relationship management: key components for IT success. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 102(2), 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02635570210419636>
- Botha, L. (2011). Mixing methods as a process towards indigenous methodologies. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 14(4), 313–325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2010.516644>
- Bowen, J.T. & Chen, S.L. (2011), "The relationship between customer loyalty and customer satisfaction," *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 2, 213-217.

- Brannen, J. (2005). Mixing Methods: The Entry of Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches to the Research Process. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 8(3), 173–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570500154642>
- Braun, R., Catalani, C., Wimbush, J., & Israelski, D. (2013). Community Health Workers and Mobile Technology: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *PLoS ONE*, 8(6), e65772. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0065772>
- Brown, K. M., Elliott, S. J., Leatherdale, S. T., & Robertson-Wilson, J. (2015). Searching for rigour in the reporting of mixed methods population health research: a methodological review. *Health Education Research*, 30(6), 811–839. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyv046>
- Browne, S., Bala, H., & Venkatesh, S. (2013). Bridging the Qualitative-Quantitative Divide: Guidelines for Conducting Mixed Methods Research in Information Systems. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 37(1), 21–54.
- Bruhn, M (2013). *Relationship marketing management of customer relationships*. Pearson Education Limited, England.
- Bruhn, M. (2011). *Relationship marketing*. NY: Vahlen GmbH.
- Bryman, A. (2012). *Social research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Budianto, A. (2019) Customer Loyalty: Quality of Service. *Journal of Management Review*. 3(1) 299-305.
- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G. (1979). *Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis*. London: Heinemann.
- Campbell, A. J. (2003). Creating customer knowledge competence: Managing customer relationship management programs strategically. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 32(5), 375–383. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501\(03\)00011-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501(03)00011-7)
- Chang, C. (2012). The effectiveness of advertising that leverages sponsorship and cause-related marketing. *International Journal of Advertising*, 31(2), 317–338. <https://doi.org/10.2501/IJA-31-2-317-337>
- Chang, H. H., Wong, K. H., & Fang, P. W. (2014). The effects of customer relationship management relational information processes on customer-based performance. *Decision Support Systems*, 66, 146–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2014.06.010>
- Chang, S., Stansbie, P., & Rood, A. S. (2014). Impulsive consumption in the experiential context. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 17(2), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2012.749843>
- Chase, S.D., (2013), *Customer service solution*. McGraw-Hill, United States.
- Chen, I. J., & Popovich, K. (2003). *Understanding customer relationship management (CRM): People,*

- process and technology. *Business Process Management Journal*, 9(5), 672–688. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14637150310496758>
- Chen, I. J., & Popovich, K. (2003). Understanding customer relationship management (CRM). *Business Process Management Journal*, 9(5), 672–688. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14637150310496758>
- Chen, I. J., & Popovich, K. (2013). Understanding customer relationship management (CRM): People processes and technology. *Business Process Management Journal*, 9 (5), 672 – 688.
- Chen, I.J., & Popovich, K. (2011). Understanding Customer Relationship Management (CRM): people, process, and technology. *Journal of Business Process Management*, 9(5), 672-688.
- Cheng, H. G., & Phillips, M. R. (2014). Secondary analysis of existing data: opportunities and implementation. *Shanghai Archives of Psychiatry*, 26(6), 371–375. <https://doi.org/10.11919/j.issn.1002-0829.214171>
- Chi, H., Zhang, Y., & Wang, J.-J. (2010). Customer loyalty analysis of a commercial bank based on a structural equation model (Vol. 1, pp. 289–298). WIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.2495/CF060281>
- Childs, M. L., & Jin, B. (2016). Do Status Symbols in Marketing Increase Product Evaluations? An Experimental Analysis of Group Differences in Product Evaluations for Scarce and Brand-Presence Products. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 28(3), 154–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08961530.2015.1102670>
- Choi, W., Rho, M. J., Park, J., Kim, K.-J., Kwon, Y. D. & Choi, I. Y. (2013). Information system success model for a customer relationship management system in health promotion centres. *Healthcare Informatics Research*, 19(2), 110–120. <https://doi.org/10.4258/hir.2013.19.2.110>
- Chow, S., & Holden, R. (2011). Toward an understanding of loyalty: the moderating role of trust. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 9(3), 275-298.
- Christoph, K. (2010). Exploratory Case Study. In *Encyclopaedia of Case Study Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Christopher, M., Payne, A., & Ballantyne, D. (2002). *Relationship marketing: Creating shareholder value*. Oxford: Butterworth.
- Coker, A. L., Davis, K., Arias, I., Desai, S., Sanderson, M., Brandt, H., & Smith, P. H. (2002). Physical and mental health effects of intimate partner violence for men and women. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 23, 260–268.
- Coltman, T. R. (2007). Can Superior CRM Capabilities Improve Performance in Banking? *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 12(2), 102–114. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.fsm.4760065>
- Coviello, N., Brodie, R., & Munro, H. (2014). An Investigation of Marketing Practice by Firm Size. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 15, 523–545.

- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. Sage Publications, Incorporated.
- Creswell, J. W., & Clark, V. L. P. (2007). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage publications.
- Crowther, D., & Lancaster, G. (2009). *Research Methods: A Concise Introduction to Research in Management and Business Consultancy*. Routledge.
- Cuthill, M. (2002). Exploratory Research: Citizen Participation, Local Government, and Sustainable Development in Australia. *Sustainable Development*, 10, 79-89.
- Cutler, P. & Armstrong, G (2011), *Principles of marketing*. Union – Publisher, Tehran.
- Damm, R., & Monroy, C. R. (2011). A review of the customer lifetime value as a customer profitability measure in the context of customer relationship management. *Intangible Capital*, 7(2), 261–279.
- Day, G. S. (2004). The capabilities of market-driven organisations. *Journal of Marketing*, 58, 37 – 52.
- Debnath, R., Datta, B., & Mukhopadhyay, S. (2016). Customer Relationship Management Theory and Research in the New Millennium: Directions for Future Research. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 15(4), 299–325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332667.2016.1209053>
- Dick, A.S. & Basu, K. (2004). Customer loyalty: Toward an integrated conceptual framework. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 22(2), 99-113.
- Dickinson, J. B. (2013). Customer loyalty: a multi-attribute approach. *Research in Business and Economic Journal*, 9(1), 1–18.
- Dopico, D. C., & Porral, C. C. (2011). Analysis of value chain and sources of differentiation in international fashion markets. *European Research Studies Journal*, 14(1), 15–28.
- Draugalis, J. R., & Plaza, C. M. (2009). Best Practices for Survey Research Reports Revisited: Implications of Target Population, Probability Sampling, and Response Rate. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 73(8). Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2828303/>
- Drolet, A., & Wood, W. (2017). Introduction to Special Issue: The Habit-Driven Consumer. *Journal of the Association for Consumer Research*, 2(3), 275–278. <https://doi.org/10.1086/695139>
- Durmaz, Y. (2014). The Influence of cultural factors on consumer buying behaviour and an application in Turkey. *Global Journal of Management And Business Research*.

- Dutu, C. & Halmajan, H. (2011). *CRM processes and the impact on business performance*. Proceedings of the 5th WSEAS International Conference on Economy and Management Transformation, Romania.
- Dwita, V., Megawati., Leni, P and Mulya, J. (2020) The Effect of Customer Relationship Management on Brand Loyalty: A Case Study on the Body Shop Indonesia's Customers. Proceedings of the 4th Padang International Conference on Education, Economics, Business and Accounting (PICEEBA-2 2019). *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*.
- Dwyer, R., Schurr, P., & Oh, S. (2007). Developing Buyer-seller Relationships. *Journal of Marketing*, 11-27.
- Dyché, J. (2012). *The CRM Handbook: A Business Guide to Customer Relationship Management* (1st Ed.). London, UK: Addison-Wesley Educational Publisher Inc.
- Edmonds, W, A and Kennedy, T, D (2016) An Applied Guide to Research Designs: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Methods. United States: SAGE Publications.
- Emir, O., (2016). A study of the relationship between service atmosphere and customer loyalty with specific reference to structural equation modelling. *Economic Research-Ekonomiska Istraživanja* , 29(1), pp. 706-720.
- Fionda, A. M., & Moore, C. M. (2009). The anatomy of the luxury fashion brand. *Journal of Brand Management*, 16(5–6), 347–363. <https://doi.org/10.1057/bm.2008.45>
- Firat, A., Kutucuo, K., Saltik, A., & Tuncel, O. (2013). Consumption, Consumer Culture and Consumer Society. *Journal of Community Positive Practices*, (1), 182–203.
- Foss, B., Stone, M., & Ekinci, Y. (2008). What makes for CRM system success — Or failure? *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 15(2), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dbm.2008.5>
- Foss, B., Stone, M., & Ekinci, Y. (2008). What makes for CRM system success — Or failure? *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 15(2), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dbm.2008.5>
- Foss, B., Stone, M., & Ekinci, Y. (2008). What makes for CRM system success — Or failure? *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 15(2), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dbm.2008.5>
- Gartner Group, (2010). *PRISM for Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*. Gartner Group.
- Giannakis-Bompolis, C., & Boutsouki, C. (2014). Customer Relationship Management in the Era of Social Web and Social Customer: An Investigation of Customer Engagement in the Greek Retail

- Banking Sector. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 148(Supplement C), 67–78.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.018>
- Gilovich, T., Kumar, A., & Jampol, L. (2015). A wonderful life: experiential consumption and the pursuit of happiness. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 25(1), 152–165.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2014.08.004>
- Gilovich, T., Kumar, A., & Jampol, L. (2015). A wonderful life: experiential consumption and the pursuit of happiness. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 25(1), 152–165.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2014.08.004>
- Given, L., M. (2007). Descriptive Research. In *Encyclopaedia of Measurement and Statistics*. Neil J. Salkind and Kristin Rasmussen, editors. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Grant, R. M. (1998). *Contemporary strategy analysis* (3rd Ed.). Malden: Blackwell.
- Grion, R. S. (2002). Rethinking Customer Acquisition. *Journal of Integrated Communications*, 7.
- Gronroos, C. (2000). *Service management and marketing: A customer relationship management approach* (2nd ed.). West Sussex: Wiley.
- Thakurta, S, G and Chetty, P. (2015). Understanding research philosophy. Retrieved from <https://www.projectguru.in/publications/research-philosophy/>
- Gummesson, E. (2007). *Relationship marketing as a paradigm shift: Some conclusions from the 30R approach*. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.39.5182&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.
- Gutjahr, G 2011, *Consumer relationship management*. Gabler Verlag, p.131.
- Hackley (PhD), C., Tiwsakul (MSc (Birmingham), R., & BA (Chulalongkorn)). (2006). Entertainment Marketing and Experiential Consumption. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 12(1), 63–75.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13527260500358608>
- Hajikhani, S., Tabibi, S. J., & Riahi, L. (2016). The Relationship Between Customer Relationship Management and Patients' Loyalty to Hospitals. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 8(3), 65–71.
<https://doi.org/10.5539/gjhs.v8n3p65>
- Hammer, M. (2006). *Beyond Reengineering*. New York: HarperCollins.
- Han, Y. J., Nunes, J. C., & Drèze, X. (2010). Signalling Status with Luxury Goods: The Role of Brand Prominence. *Journal of Marketing*, 74(4), 15–30. <https://doi.org/10.0.5.229/jmkg.74.4.15>
- Harrison, R. L., & Reilly, T. M. (2011). Mixed methods design in marketing research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 14(1), 7–26. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13522751111099300>

- Hassan, R. S., Nawaz, A., Lashari, M. N., & Zafar, F. (2015). Effect of Customer Relationship Management on Customer Satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, 563–567. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00513-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00513-4)
- Hawkins, D. I., & Mothersbaugh, D. L. (2010). *Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy. Publish.*
- Heller Baird, C., & Parasnis, G. (2011). From social media to social customer relationship management. *Strategy & Leadership*, 39(5), 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1108/108785711111161507>
- Henneberg, S. C. (2008). An Exploratory Analysis of CRM Implementation Models. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 4(3–4), 85–104. https://doi.org/10.1300/J366v04n03_06
- Hennigs, N., Wiedmann, K. P., Behrens, S., & Klarmann, C. (2013). Unleashing the power of luxury: Antecedents of luxury brand perception and effects on luxury brand strength. *Journal of Brand Management*, 20(8), 705–715. <https://doi.org/10.1057/bm.2013.11>
- Heunis, S., Dekenah, M., & Setlhogo, L. (2014). Domestic load research data collection using Open Data Kit. In *Domestic Use of Energy (DUE), 2014 Proceedings of the Twenty-Second* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Hewege, C. R., & Perera, L. C. R. (2013). In Search of Alternative Research Methods in Marketing: Insights from Layder’s Adaptive Theory Methodology. *Contemporary Management Research*, 9(3), 343–360. <https://doi.org/10.7903/cmr.9978>
- Hillebrand, B., Nijholt, J. J., & Nijssen, E. J. (2011). Exploring CRM effectiveness: an institutional theory perspective. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39, 592–608. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-011-0248-3>
- Hillebrand, B., Nijholt, J. J., & Nijssen, E. J. (2011). Exploring CRM effectiveness: an institutional theory perspective. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39(4), 592–608. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-011-0248-3>
- Hirst, I. R. C., & Reekie, W. D. (2013). *The Consumer Society*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis.
- Hofacker, C. F., Malthouse, E. C., & Sultan, F. (2016). Big Data and consumer behaviour: imminent opportunities. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 33(2), 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-04-2015-1399>
- Hofman-Kohlmeyer, M. (2016) Customer loyalty program as a tool of customer retention: Literature Review. *CBU International Conference Proceedings*. 4(1). 199-203
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (2010). *Cultures and Organisations: Software of the Mind, Third Edition. McGraw-Hill Education; 3rd edition.* <https://doi.org/10.2307/2393257>

- Hosseini, S. M. S., Maleki, A., & Gholamian, M. R. (2010). Cluster analysis using data mining approach to develop CRM methodology to assess customer loyalty. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(7), 5259–5264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2009.12.070>
- Hox, J. J., & Boeije, H. R. (2005). Data Collection, Primary vs Secondary. *Encyclopaedia of Social Measurement*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-12-369398-5/00041-4>
- Hox, J., & Boeije, H. R. (2005). Data Collection, Primary vs Secondary. *Encyclopaedia of Social Measurement*.
- Hult, G. T. M. (2012). *Boundary-Spanning Marketing Organisation: A Theory and Insights from 31 Organisation Theories*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Isaac, S & Michael, W. B. (1971). *Handbook in research and evaluation*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage publications.
- Iversen, A., Liddell, K., Fear, N., Hotopf, M., & Wessely, S. (2006). Consent, confidentiality, and the Data Protection Act. *BMJ*, 332(7534), 165–169. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.332.7534.165>
- Izvercian, M., & Potra, S. A. (2014). Prosumer-oriented Relationship Management Capability Development for Business Performance. *Procedia Technology*, 16, 606–612. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.protcy.2014.10.009>
- Jamieson, G., & Loi, N. (2014). *An Empirical Test of Tellegen's Model of Absorption: Instrumental and Experiential Sets and the Phenomenology of Trance Induction*.
- Jayesh, S. S. & Pradip, M., (2014). To Study the Perception of Women as Customers towards Beauty Service in Western Mumbai. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Reviews*, 3(4), pp. 52 - 64.
- Jeffrey-Coker, F., Basinger, M. & Modi, V. (2010). Open data kit: Implications for the use of smartphone software technology for questionnaire studies in international development. Columbia: Columbia University.
- Jones, G. (2006). Globalizing the Beauty Business before 1980. *Harvard Business School*.
- Julian, L. (2012). Using Social Media to Increase Consumer Loyalty to a Brand. (June).
- Kangu, M., Wanjau, K and Kosimbei, G. (2017) Technology infrastructure: A customer relationship management dimension in maintaining customer loyalty. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, V (5), 88-106
- Kasim, A. & Minai, B. (2009). Linking CRM strategy, customer performance measure and performance in the hotel industry. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 3(2), 297-316.
- Kearney, A. (2012). Beauty: Only as Deep as the Customer Experience. *A.T. Kearney Korea LLC*, 1–8.

- Khan, P. I., & Tabassum, A. (2010). Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction of the Beauty-Care Service Industry in Dhaka: A Study on High-End Women's Parlours. *The Journal of Business in Developing Nations*, 12, 1–27.
- Khodakarami, F., & Chan, Y. E. (2014). Exploring the role of customer relationship management (CRM) systems in customer knowledge creation. *Information & Management*, 51(1), 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2013.09.001>
- Knupfer, N. and McLellan, H. (1996). *Descriptive Research Methodologies. Handbook of Research for Educational Communities in Technology*. New York. Macmillan.
- Kocoglu, D., & Kirmaci, S. (2012). Customer relationship management and customer loyalty; a survey in the sector of banking. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(3), 282–292. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09590550110696969>
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2009). *Marketing management* (13th ed.). New Delhi: Prentice-Hall.
- Kracklauer, A., Passenheim, O., & Seifert, D. (2011). Mutual customer approach: How industry and trade are executing collaborative customer relationship management. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 29(12), 515 – 519.
- Kubi, B. A., & Doku, and A. K. (2010). Towards a successful customer relationship management: A conceptual framework. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2005.02.022>
- Kumar, S. R. (2009). *Consumer Behaviour And Branding: Concepts, Readings And Cases-The Indian Context*. Pearson Education, India.
- Kumar, V. & Reinartz, W. (2010). *Customer relationship management: A databased approach*. N. Y.: Joh Wiley.
- Kumar, V. (2012). *Customer relationship management*. New York: Springer.
- Labus, M., & Stone, M. (2010). The CRM behaviour theory – Managing corporate customer relationships in service industries. *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 17(3–4), 155–173. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dbm.2010.17>
- Lahap, J., Ramli, N. S., Said, N. M., Radzi, S. M., & Zain, R. A. (2016). A Study of Brand Image towards Customer's Satisfaction in the Malaysian Hotel Industry. *Procedia -Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 224, 149–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.430>
- Lam, M., Reichheld, N. & Sasser, V. 2010, *Service Marketing*, (5th Ed). Irwin Publisher, Burr Ridge, IL.
- Lam, T. Y., & Maguire, D. A. (2012). Structural Equation Modelling: Theory and Applications in Forest Management. *International Journal of Forestry Research*, 2012, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/263953>

- Leavy, P. (2017) *Research Design: Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed Methods, Arts-Based, and Community-Based Participatory Research Approaches*. Guilford Publications
- Lee, E. W. (2012). Data mining application in customer relationship management for hospital inpatients. *Healthcare Informatics Research*, 18(3), 178–185. <https://doi.org/10.4258/hir.2012.18.3.178>
- Leventhal, R., C (2006), *Customer loyalty, retention, and customer relationship management*. Emerald Group Publishing Ltd, Bradford, GBR.
- Liang, C.J. & Wang, W.H. (2014), “Attributes, benefits, customer satisfaction, and behavioural loyalty – An integrated research of financial service industry in Taiwan,” *Journal of Services Research*, 4(1), 1-35.
- Lipiäinen, H. S. M. (2015). CRM in the digital age: implementation of CRM in three contemporary B2B firms. *Journal of Systems and Information Technology*, 17(1), 2–19. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSIT-06-2014-0044>
- Lipiäinen, H. S. M. (2015). CRM in the digital age: implementation of CRM in three contemporary B2B firms. *Journal of Systems and Information Technology*, 17(1), 2–19. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSIT-06-2014-0044>
- Liu, M., Lu, W., Shore, R. E., & Zeleniuch-Jacquotte, A. (2010). Cox regression model with time-varying coefficients in nested case-control studies. *Biostatistics (Oxford, England)*, 11(4), 693–706. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biostatistics/kxq037>
- Liu, R., Pieniak, Z., & Verbeke, W. (2013). Consumers’ attitudes and behaviour towards safe food in China: A review. *Food Control*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2013.01.051>
- Lofman, B. (1991). Elements of Experiential Consumption : An Exploratory Study. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 18(1), 729–735.
- Long, C. S., Khalafinezhad, R., Ismail, W. K. W., & Rasid, S. Z. A. (2013). Impact of CRM Factors on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Asian Social Science*, 9(10). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n10p247>
- Madsen, D., Storsveen, M., Klethagen, P., & Stenheim, T. (2016). The diffusion and popularity of Lean in Norway: An exploratory survey. *Cogent Business & Management*, 3, 1258132.
- Magatef, S. G. & Tomalieh, E. F., 2015. The Impact of Customer Loyalty Programs on Customer Retention. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* , 6(8), pp. 78-93.
- Malik, G. (2015). Impact of customer relationship management on customer loyalty and customer retention with reference to the automobile sector. *University Journal of Research*, 1(1), 70-90.
- Mandic, M. (2011). Important Elements in Customer Relationship Management. *International Journal of Management Cases*, 13(3), 347–351. Retrieved from

<http://content.ebscohost.com.nuncio.cofc.edu/ContentServer.asp?T=P&P=AN&K=65535169&S=R&D=buh&EbscoContent=dGJyMNLr40SeprM4yOvsOLCmr0qep69Sr6+4TLCWxWXS&ContentCustomer=dGJyMPGuslCzr7dMuePfgeyx4Ivn%5Cnhttp://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=buh&AN=65535169&site=bsi-live&scope=cite>

- Mandina, S. P. (2014). The contribution of CRM strategies in enhancing customer loyalty. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 8(2), 69–87.
- Manrai, L. A., & Manrai, A. K. (2010). The Influence of Culture in International Business Negotiations: A New Conceptual Framework and Managerial Implications. *Journal of Transnational Management*, 15, 69–100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15475770903584607>
- Markides, M. (2011). The importance of good communication between patient and health professionals. *Journal of Paediatric Haematology/Oncology*, 33, S123–S125.
- Martin, C. & Bush, A. (2000). Do Role Models Influence Teenager's Purchase Intentions and Behaviour? *The Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 17 (5), 441-463.
- Massey, A. P., Montoya-Weiss, M. M., & Holcom, K. (2011). Re-engineering the customer relationship: Leveraging knowledge assets at IBM. *Decision Support Systems*, 32(2), 155 – 170.
- MDG Marketing , (2018). *Affluent Consumers in 2018: Demographics and Spending Habits*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.mdgadvertising.com/marketing-insights/affluent-consumers-in-2018-demographics-and-spending-habits/> [Accessed 20 January 2019].
- Mendoza, D. Y. (2010). Commodity, sign, and spectacle: retracing Baudrillard's hyperreality. *Journal KRITIKE*, 4, 45–59.
- Merilyn, L. (2017) Customer relationship marketing in hair and beauty salon. *Theseus*. 1-28
- Mintel Press Office (2012) Women More Likely To Visit A Salon, But A Growing Number Of Men Interested In These Services. [Online] Available at: <http://www.mintel.com/press-centre/beauty-and-personal-care/women-more-likely-to-visit-a-salon-but-a-growing-number-of-men-interested-in-these-services> [Accessed 20 October 2018].
- Mishra, A. & Mishra, D. (2009). Customer Relationship Management: Implementation Process Perspective. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 6(4).
- Mohammed, A. A., & Bin Rashid, B. (2012). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) in the Hotel Industry: A framework Proposal on the Relationship among CRM Dimensions, Marketing Capabilities and Hotel Performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2(4), 220–230. Retrieved from www.econjournals.com

- Mohammed, A. A., & Bin Rashid, B. (2012b). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) in the Hotel Industry: A framework Proposal on the Relationship among CRM Dimensions, Marketing Capabilities, and Hotel Performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2(4), 220–230.
- Mokhtar, N. F., Hasan, Z. R. A., & Halim, M. A. S. A. (2016). Applying Technology Organisation and Environment (TOE) Model in social media marketing adoption: The case of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kelantan, Malaysia. *Social Sciences (Pakistan)*, 11(21), 5139–5144. <https://doi.org/10.3923/sscience.2016.5139.5144>
- Morgan, R. M. & Hunt, S. D. (2004). The commitment – Trust theory of relationship marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 58, 20 – 38.
- Morgan, R. M., & Hunt, S. D. (1994). The Commitment-Trust Theory of Relationship Marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(3), 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356766710391135>
- Myler, L. (2016). Acquiring New Customers Is Important but Retaining Them Accelerates Profitable Growth. Retrieved December 16, 2017, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/larrymyler/2016/06/08/acquiring-new-customers-is-important-but-retaining-them-accelerates-profitable-growth/>
- Nagasawa, S. ya, & Irisawa, Y. (2013). Luxury Strategy of Beauty Products by Chanel. *International Marketing Trend Conference*, 1–25.
- Nam, L. G., Thi, N. D. N., & Quynh, N. T. T. (2017). Relationship Marketing and Customer Loyalty in Vietnam Cosmetics Market. *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*
- Namjoyan, M., Esfahani, D. A. N., & Haery, D. F. A. (2013). Studying the Effects of Customer Relationship Management on the Marketing Performance (Isfahan Saderat Bank as a Case Study). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(9). <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v3-i9/211>
- Narver, J. C. & Slater, S. F. (2010). The effect of market orientation on business profitability. *Journal of Marketing*, 54, 20 – 35.
- Ndubisi, N., (2005). Relationship marketing and customer loyalty. *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 25(1), p. 98–106.
- Nguyen, N., Leclerc, A. & LeBlanc, G (2013), “The mediating role of customer trust on customer loyalty,” *Journal of service science and management*, 6(1), p.96.

- Nulty, D. D. (2008). The adequacy of response rates to online and paper surveys: what can be done? *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 33(3), 301–314. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930701293231>
- Oladimeji, A. M., Gidado, S., Nguku, P., Nwangwu, I. G., Patil, N. D., Oladosu, F., ... Poggensee, G. (2015). Ebola virus disease – gaps in knowledge and practice among healthcare workers in Lagos, August 2014. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, 20(9), 1162–1170. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.12528>
- Oliver, R.L., (2009), Whence consumer loyalty?" *The Journal of Marketing*, pp. 33-44.
- Oluka, O. C., Nie, S., & Sun, Y. (2014). Quality Assessment of TPB-Based Questionnaires: A Systematic Review. *PLOS ONE*, 9(4), e94419. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0094419>
- Osarenkhoe, A., & Bennani, A. (2007). An exploratory study of the implementation of a customer relationship management strategy. *Business Proc. Manag. Journal*, 13, 139-164.
- Østergaard, P., & Fitchett, J. (2012). Relationship marketing and the order of simulation. *Marketing Theory*, 12(3), 233–249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470593112451393>
- Oztas, M., Sevilmis, A. & Sirin, E. F., (2016). The relationship between the atmosphere, satisfaction, and loyalty: Sample of a fitness centre. *Turkish Journal of Sport and Exercise*, 18(2), pp. 103-112.
- P, F. A. B. K. & Panjaitan, H. (2014). Analysis of Customer Loyalty through Total Quality Service, Customer Relationship Management, and Customer Satisfaction. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 3(3), 142–151.
- Panache Beauty, (2015), *Company Profile*. Retrieved from: <http://panachebeautymaidstone.co.uk/herbstattoo-treatment.html>. [5 March 2017].
- Pandey, J. (2018) Deductive approach to content analysis. IGI Global
- Paradis, E., O'Brien, B., Nimmon, L., Bandiera, G., & Martimianakis, M. A. (Tina). (2016). Design: Selection of Data Collection Methods. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 8(2), 263–264. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-D-16-00098.1>
- Park, J. J. (2012). *Future information technology, application, and service: Futuretech 2012. Volume 2*. Dordrecht; New York: Springer.
- Paulson, S., (2008). “Beauty Is More Than Skin Deep.” An Ethnographic Study Of Beauty Therapists And Older Women. *Journal of Aging Studies*, 22(3), pp. 256-265.
- Payne, A. (2010). A strategic framework for customer relationship management. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 69, pp. 167-76.

- Peelen, E., Montfort, K. van, Beltman, R., & Klerkx, A. (2009). An empirical study of the foundations of CRM success. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 17(6), 453–471. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09652540903371695>
- Peppers, D., Rogers, M., & Dorf, B. (2009). Is your company ready for one-to-one marketing? *Harvard Business Review*, 77(1), 101 – 119.
- Peter, J. P., & Olson, J. C. (2009). *Consumer Behavior & Marketing Strategy*. Dana.
- Petrescu, D. (2013a). Advances in Environmental Sciences - International Journal of the Bio flux Society Consumer behaviour towards organic, natural and conventional skincare products: a pilot study. *International Journal of the Bio flux Society*, 5(3), 274–286.
- Pithers, E. (2014). Counterintelligence: Undercover at the John Lewis beauty hall. Retrieved August 20, 2017, from <http://fashion.telegraph.co.uk/beauty/news-features/TMG10587612/Counter-Intelligence-Undercover-at-the-John-Lewis-beauty-hall.html>
- Poba-Nzaou, P., Raymond, L., & Fabi, B. (2008). Adoption and risk of ERP systems in manufacturing SMEs: a positivist case study. *Business Process Management Journal*, 14(4), 530–550. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14637150810888064>
- Podrug, N. (2011). Influence of National Culture on Decision-Making Style. *South-East European Journal of Economics and Business*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10033-011-0004-0>
- Ponto, J. (2015). Understanding and Evaluating Survey Research. *Journal of the Advanced Practitioner in Oncology*, 6(2), 168–171.
- Popper, K. (2004). *The Logic of Scientific Discovery*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis.
- Potts, J., Hartley, J., Banks, J., Burgess, J., Cobcroft, R., Cunningham, S., & Montgomery, L. (2008). Consumer co-creation and situated creativity. *Industry and Innovation*, 15(5), 459–474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662710802373783>
- Punniyamoorthy, M., Mahadevan, B., Shetty, N. & Lakshmi, G. (2011). A framework for the assessment of brand loyalty score for commodities. *Journal of Targeting, Measurement and Analysis for Marketing*, 19(3/4), 243-260.
- Püsküllüoğlu, M., Tomaszewski, K. A., Zygulska, A. L., Ochendusko, S., Streb, J., Tomaszewska, I. M., & Krzemieniecki, K. (2014). Pilot Testing and Preliminary Psychometric Validation of the Polish Translation of the EORTC INFO25 Questionnaire: Validation of the Polish version of INFO25—a pilot study. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 9(3), 525–535. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-013-9250-x>

- Rahi, S (2017) Research Design and Methods: A Systematic Review of Research Paradigms, Sampling Issues and Instruments Development. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*. 6(2).
- Rahman, A., & Khan, M. (2017). An Assessment of Data Mining Based CRM Techniques for Enhancing Profitability. *International Journal of Education and Management Engineering (IJEME)*, 7(2), 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijeme.2017.02.04>
- Ramani, G., & Kumar, V. (2008). Interaction Orientation and Firm Performance. *Journal of Marketing*, 72(1), 27–45. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.72.1.27>
- Reinartz, W. J., Krafft, M., & Hoyer, W. D. (2013). Measuring the customer relationship management construct and linking it to performance outcomes. *Working Paper Series of the Teradata Centre for Customer Relationship Management*, Duke University.
- Reinartz, W., Krafft, M. & Hoyer, W.D. 2014, “The customer relationship management process: Its measurement and impact on performance,” *Journal of Marketing Research*, 41(3), pp.293-305.
- Reiss, S. (2012). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation. *The teaching of Psychology*, 39(2), 152–156. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0098628312437704>
- Retail Economics (2016), *UK health and beauty*. Available at: < <http://www.retailconomics.co.uk/download/Sample%20-%20UK%20Health%20and%20Beauty%20Sector.pdf> >. 23 July 2017.
- Retail Economists. (2007). What are you looking for? <https://doi.org/10.1145/1240624.1240690>
- Reynaldo, J.A. & Santos, A. (1999). Cronbach’s Alpha: A Tool for Assessing the Reliability of Scales. *Journal of Extension*, 37, 1-4.
- Richards, K. A., & Jones, E. (2008). Customer relationship management: Finding value drivers. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 37(2), 120–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2006.08.005>
- Ritzer, G. (2003). *The globalization of nothing*. London: Pine Forge Press.
- Rogers, M. (2010), “Customer strategy observation from the ranches,” *Journal of Marketing*, 69, 262-263.
- Roggeveen, A. L., & Grewal, D. (2016a). Editorial. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 33(2). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-12-2015-1649>
- Roya, A. & Salmiah, M. 2010, *The customer relationship management strategies: A Personal needs assessment of training and customer turnover*. Number 1.
- Ryals, L. (2013), September). Making customers pay: Measuring and managing customer risk and returns. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 11, 165 – 175.

- Saarijärvi, H., Karjaluoto, H., & Kuusela, H. (2013). Extending customer relationship management: from empowering firms to empowering customers. *Journal of Systems and Information Technology*, 15(2), 140–158. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13287261311328877>
- Saewan, N., & Jimtaisong, A. (2015). Natural products like photoprotection. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*, 14(1), 47–63. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.12123>
- Samuel Craig, C., & Douglas, S. P. (2006). Beyond national culture: implications of cultural dynamics for consumer research. *International Marketing Review*, 23(3), 322–342. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02651330610670479>
- San-Martín, S., Jiménez, N. H., & López-Catalán, B. (2016). The firm's benefits of mobile CRM from the relationship marketing approach and the TOE model. *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 20(1), 18–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reimke.2015.07.001>
- Santin-Janin, H., Hugueny, B., Aubry, P., Fouchet, D., Gimenez, O., & Pontier, D. (2014). Accounting for Sampling Error When Inferring Population Synchrony from Time-Series Data: A Bayesian State-Space Modelling Approach with Applications. *PLoS ONE*, 9(1), e87084. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0087084>
- Saunders, M., Lewis P. and Thornhill A. (2009) *Research Methods for business student* 4th edition Pearson education limited
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2012). *Research Methods for Business Students* (6th ed.). London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A & Bristow, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). England: Pearson Education, pp. 1–617.
- Saunders, M. N. K and Loudoun, R. (2020). *How to Keep your Doctorate on Track: Insights from Students' and Supervisors' Experiences*. United Kingdom: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Sayedi, M, Mousavi, A, Heidari, S., H, Elahi, S, & Heidari, B. (2009). *Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*. Tehran: Commercial Publishing Company.
- Šebjan, U., Bobek, S., & Tominc, P. (2014). Organisational Factors Influencing Effective Use of CRM Solutions. *Procedia Technology*, 16(Supplement C), 459–470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.protcy.2014.10.113>
- Segoro, W. (2013). The Influence of Perceived Service Quality, Mooring Factor, and Relationship Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Procedia – Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 81(28), 306-310.
- Sekaran, U and Bougie, R (2016). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach* (7th Ed). New York: John Wiley & Sons.

- Shahin, A. & Teymuri, H. (2008), *Customer loyalty concepts and patterns*. Jihad University
- Shahnam, L. (2013). *What's really CRM?* Available at: http://www.crm2day.com/what_is_crm/.
- Shalehah, A., Trisno, I, L, O., Moslehpour, M. and Lin Cor, P. (2019) The Effect of Korean Beauty Product Characteristics on Brand Loyalty and Customer Repurchase Intention in Indonesia. *16th International Conference on Service Systems and Service Management (ICSSSM)*, Shenzhen, China. 1-5
- Shang, S. S. C., & Lin, S. F. (2010). People-driven processes in customer relationship management. *The Service Industries Journal*, 30(14), 2441–2456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642060802712780>
- Shani, D & Sujana, C. (2008). Exploiting Niches Using Relationship Marketing. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 9(3), 33-42.
- Shaon, S., & Rahman, M. (2015). A Theoretical Review of CRM Effects on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Central European Business ...*, 4(1), 23–36. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/openview/4f1883dd7537944ccd7953d2a8e5d042/1?pq-origsite=gscholar>
- Sharon, S., & Rahman, M. (2015). A Theoretical Review of CRM Effects on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Central European Business ...*, 4(01), 23–36.
- Shaw, R. (2013). European Centre for Customer Strategies: Customer concepts. Retrieved from http://www.eccs.uk.com/eccs/resources/customer_concepts.asp.
- Shen, B., & Bissell, K. (2013). Social Media, Social Me: A Content Analysis of Beauty Companies' Use of Facebook in Marketing and Branding. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 19(5), 629–651. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496491.2013.829160>
- Shoemakers, N & Hewis, R. 2009, "Customer Loyalty: the future of hospitality marketing," *Hospitality Management*, 18(8), 385-370.
- Singh, S and Singh, A. (2016) Customer relationship management (CRM): A statistical perspective. *International Journal of Current Research*, 8 (2), 26771-26776
- So, K, King, C., Sparks, B., & Wang, Y. (2016). Enhancing Customer Relationships with Retail Service Brands: The Role of Customer Engagement. *Journal of Service Management*, 27, 170-193.
- Sofi, M. R., & Hakim, I. A. (2014). Customer relationship management and customer loyalty in the service sector. *Clear International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, 5(4), 19-25.
- Song, Y., Hur, W., & Kim, M. (2012). Brand Trust and Affect in the Luxury Brand –. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 40(2), 331–338. <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2012.40.2.331>

- Sorayaei, A., ReazValiollahi, H., Hossein Zadeh, M., Hossein Ghoryshian, S., & Masoud Dinari, A. (2014). Impact of customer relationship management (CRM) on marketing performance: A case study in Mellat bank of Mazandaran Province. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences: Proceedings*, 2(3 (s)), pp–2612.
- Srinivasan, S. R., & Srivastava, R. K. (2010). Creating the futuristic retail experience through experiential marketing: Is it possible? An exploratory study. *Journal of Retail & Leisure Property*, 9(3), 193–199. <https://doi.org/10.1057/rlp.2010.12>
- Srivastava, R. K., Shervani, T. A., & Fahey, L. (2009). Marketing, business processes, and shareholder value: An organisationally embedded view of marketing activities and the discipline of marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 63, 168 – 179.
- Stiles, K. E., Love, N., Mundry, S. & DiRanna, K., 2008. *The Data Coach's Guide to Improving Learning for All Students*. Singapore: Corwin Press.
- Stimpert, J. L., & Duhaime, I. M. (1997). Seeing the big picture: The influence of industry, diversification, and business strategy on performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 40(3), 560–583. <https://doi.org/10.2307/257053>
- Sulaiman, M. A., Baharum, M. A. A. & Ridzuan, A. (2014a). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Strategies Practices in Malaysia Retailers. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 130(Supplement C), 354–361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.042>
- Sutton, J., & Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative Research: Data Collection, Analysis, and Management. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*, 68(3), 226–231.
- Taber, K. (2017). The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Research in Science Education*, 1573-1898.
- Tajeddini, K. & Nikdavoodi, J. (2014). Cosmetic Buying Behaviour: Examining Effective Factors. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science: Bridging Asia and the World*, 24(4), 395-410.
- Tan, X., Yen, D. C., & Fang, X. (2012). Internet integrated customer relationship management. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 77 – 86.
- Tanner Jr, J.F., 2014, *Analytics and dynamic customer strategy: big profits from big data*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Tauni, S., Khan, R., I., Durrani, M., K., & Aslam, S. (2014). Impact of customer relationship management on customer retention in the telecom industry of Pakistan. *Industrial Engineering Letters*, 4(10), 54-58.
- Tavakol, M. & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *Int J Med Educ.*, 2, 53–55.

- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 2, 53–55. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>
- The Nielsen Company LLC, (2018). *The Future Of Beauty The Future Is Being Rewritten*, USA: The Nielsen Company LLC.
- The Times of India, (2018). *Facials According To Your Skin Type*. [Online] Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/beauty/Facials-according-to-your-skin-type/articleshow/11616369.cmshttps://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/beauty/Facials-according-to-your-skin-type/articleshow/11616369.cms> [Accessed 20 September 2018].
- Thompson, P. (2004). Researching family and social mobility with two eyes: some experiences of the interaction between qualitative and quantitative data. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 7(3), 237–257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1364557021000024785>
- Tiemo, A. (2013). Conceptualizing customer relationship management using a descriptive approach. *Sljetems Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 4(3), 337–342.
- Tuu, H.H. & Olsen, SO 2016, *The satisfaction-loyalty relationship in marketing: A critical review and future research*. McGill.
- Ulusoy, E. (2016). Experiential responsible consumption. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(1), 284–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.07.041>
- Uncles, M. D., Dowling, G. R., & Hammond, K. (2003). Customer loyalty and customer loyalty programs. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 20(4), 294–316. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363760310483676>
- University of Witwatersrand. (2018). Research Support: Research Methodology. Available at: <https://libguides.wits.ac.za/c.php?g=693518&p=4914913>.
- van Doorn, J. (2016). Commentary: Why Do We Waste So Much Food? A Research Agenda. *Journal of the Association for Consumer Research*, 1(1), 53–56. <https://doi.org/10.1086/684462>
- Van Holm, E. J. (2014). Leisure choices of the creative class. *Cities*, 41(PA), 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2014.05.006>.
- Veblen, T. (1992). *The theory of the leisure class*. London: Transaction Publishers.
- Verhoef, P. C. (2003). Understanding the effect of customer relationship management efforts on customer retention and customer share development. *Journal of Marketing*, 67(4), 30–45.
- Verhoef, P. C., & Lemon, K. N. (2013). Successful customer value management: Key lessons and emerging trends. *European Management Journal*, 31(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2012.08.001>

- Verma, D., & Verma, D. S. (2013). Managing Customer Relationships through Mobile CRM In Organized retail outlets. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, 4(5), 1697–1701.
- Vesel, P., & Zabkar, V. (2009). Managing customer loyalty through the mediating role of satisfaction in the DIY retail loyalty program. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 16(5), 396–406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2009.05.002>
- Viljoen, M., Bennett, J. A., Berndt, A. D., & Van Zyl, C. R. (2005). The use of technology in customer relationship management (CRM). *Acta Commercii*, 5(1), 106–116. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ac.v5i1.75>
- Wali, A. F., Uduma, I. A., & Wright, L. T. (2016). Customer relationship management (CRM) experiences of Business-to-Business (B2B) marketing firms: A qualitative study. *Cogent Business & Management*, 3(1), 1183555. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2016.1183555>
- Walker, J., Kumar, A., & Gilovich, T. (2016). Cultivating gratitude and giving through experiential consumption. *Emotion*, 16(8), 1126–1136. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000242>
- Walker, T. (2004). *Customer Relationship Management for Luxury Skin Care Brands in the Selective Cosmetics Sector A situational analysis considering communication tools, opportunities, and limitations*.
- Wang, Y., Po Lo, H., Chi, R., & Yang, Y. (2004). An integrated framework for customer value and customer-relationship-management performance: a customer-based perspective from China. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 14(2/3), 169–182. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520410528590>
- Weber, J. M., & Villebonne, J. C. de. (2002). Differences in purchase behaviour between France and the USA: the cosmetic industry. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 6(4), 396–407. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13612020210448673>
- Webster, F., E. (1992). The Changing Role of Marketing in the Corporation. *Journal of Marketing*, 56(4), 1-17.
- Williams, P., Ashill, N., & Naumann, E. (2017). Toward a contingency theory of CRM adoption. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 25(5–6), 454–474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2016.1149211>
- Williams, R. H. (1991). *Dreamworlds: mass consumption in late nineteenth-century France /Rosalind H. Williams*. Berkeley [u.a.: Univ. of Calif. Press.
- Wilson, D., T. (2014). An Integrated Model of Buyer-Seller Relationships. *Journal of the Academy Marketing Science*, 23(4), 335-45.

- Wirtz, J. (2016). *Winning in Service Markets: Success through People, Technology and Strategy*. World Scientific.
- Witt, P. a, & Bishop, D. W. (2009). Situational Antecedents to Leisure Behavior. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 41, 337–350.
- Xu, M.& Walton, J. (2005), “Gaining customer knowledge through analytical CRM,” *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 105(7), 955-971.
- Yaghoubi, M., Asgari, H., &Javadi, M. (2017). The impact of customer relationship management on organisational productivity, customer trust and satisfaction by using the structural equation model: A study in Iranian hospitals. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 6. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_32_14
- Yang, X., Jayashree, S., & Marthandan, G. (2012). Ideal types of strategic innovation an exploratory study of Chinese cosmetic industry. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(17), 78. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v7n17p78>
- Yilmaz, K. (2013). Comparison of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Traditions: epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences: European Journal of Education. *European Journal of Education*, 48(2), 311–325. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12014>
- Yogesh, D. (2009). *Handbook of Research on Contemporary Theoretical Models in Information Systems*. IGI Global.
- Zablah, A.R., Bellenger, D., N. & Johnston, W., J (2014). An evaluation of divergent perspectives on customer relationship management: towards a common understanding of an emerging phenomenon. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 33, 475-489.
- Zeb, H., Rashid, K., & Javeed, M. B. (2011). Influence of Brands on Female Consumer’s Buying Behaviour in Pakistan. *International Journal of Trade, Economics, and Finance*, 2(3), 225–231. <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJTEF.2011.V2.107>
- Zineldin, M. (2006). The royalty of loyalty: CRM, quality, and retention. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 23(7), 430–437. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363760610712975>.

Appendices

Appendix A: Questionnaire

Demographics and General Information of Customers		
1.	Name	
2.	Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female
3.	Age Group	18 - 24 25 - 34 35 - 44 45 - 54 54 +
4.	Status of Employment	Student Employed Self-Employed
5.	How far is Panache Beauty from your residence?	Less than 2 Miles Between 2 - 10 Miles More than 10 Miles
6.	How do you come to know about Panache Beauty?	SMS Email Twitter Facebook Friends or Family Other (Please Specify) _____
7.	How long have you been a customer of Panache Beauty?	Less Than 1 Month 1 to 6 Month 7 to 12 Months More than 12 Months
8.	How frequently you visit Panache Beauty?	On a Daily Basis On a Weekly Basis

		On Fortnightly Basis
		On a Monthly Basis
		Very Occasionally

Please rate the services provided by Panache Beauty from a scale of 1 to 5 where (1= Strongly Disagree and 5= Strongly Agree)?

No.	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
9.	The Staff at Panache Beauty is Very Well Trained and Professional					
10.	The Staff at Panache Beauty is Expert and Experienced in Their Jobs					
11.	The Behaviour of Staff at Panache Beauty is Very Good (e.g. Friendly and Sincere)					
12.	The Quality of Services Provided at Panache Beauty is Excellent					
13.	Services Provided at Panache Beauty Suits My Skin Very Well					
14.	Services Provided at Panache Beauty Are Rightly Priced According to Their Quality					
15.	The Overall Environment and Atmosphere of Panache is Very Good and Relaxing					
16.	Panache Beauty Offers Good Packages and Discount Deals to All of Its Customers					

17. Panache Beauty also Offers Special Packages and Discount Deals to Its Regular Customers
18. Panache Beauty Informs Its Customers About New Packages or Discount Deals (e.g. through Social Media, Email, SMS etc.)

Please rate your opinion on the following from a scale of 1 to 5 where (1= Very Unlikely and 5= Very Likely)?

No.	Question	Very Unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very Likely
19.	How Likely You Want to Visit Panache Beauty Again?					
20.	How Likely You Will Prefer Panache Beauty Over Other Beauty Parlours or Saloons?					
21.	How Likely You Will Recommend Panache Beauty to Your Family and Friends?					

Appendix B – Interview Questions

1. What is your opinion on the behaviour of staff at Panache Beauty?
2. Do you think that the staff at Panache Beauty is very well trained and professional?
3. Do you think that the staff at Panache Beauty is expert and experienced in their jobs?
4. What is your opinion on the quality of services provided at Panache Beauty?
5. What is so unique about the services provided at Panache Beauty that forces you to return to them?

6. What do you have to say about the overall environment and atmosphere of Panache Beauty?
7. Do you feel that Panache Beauty offers good packages and discount deals to customers?
8. Do they offer special packages and discount deals to their regular customers?
9. How likely are you expected to visit Panache Beauty again?
10. How likely you will recommend Panache Beauty to your family and friends?

Appendix C- Gantt Chart

Major Tasks	AUG – DEC 2016	JAN- MAR 2017	APR- AUG 2017	SEPT- DEC 2017	JAN- MAR 2018	APR- AUG 2018	SEPT-OCT 2018	NOV-DEC 2018	JAN- FEB 2019	MAR-MA 2019
Research design and proposal preparation										
Proposal Discussion, Review and Planning										
Literature Review Research Methodology										
Review chapter 1,2,3 & Apply for Ethics approval										
Date collection										
Compare, review, analyse the findings & data, outcome preparation,										
Thesis review and amendment										

Compile results and prepare the final draft										
Presenting final draft & submitting										

Appendix D- Ethics Approval confirmation

15/02/2018

Dear Suprim Jha,

Your application 1738: The Impact of Customer Relationship Management, on Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention within SME Beauty Organisations in the U.K.: A Case Study of Panache Beauty, submission 1845, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr A Kourouklis

Appendix E- Participant Invitation

Participation invitation

Email: [REDACTED]

Researcher: Mr Suprim Jha

Invitation

This is an invitation to participate in this research. Participation in this study is based on volition and is not mandatory in any way. Before you make the decision to participate, it is critical that you understand the reasons for conducting this study. Please take time to go through the information that follows and discuss with others if you feel there is need to do so. You can ask the principal investigator anything you wish to clarify before during or after the study.

Thank you for reading this.

What is the purpose of the study?

The aim of the research is to understand the relationship between customer relationship management and customer loyalty and retention in the beauty industry. In specific, the research seeks to:

- To understand CRM systems in beauty industry
- To find out if the CRM systems are effective in making consumers loyal
- To assess the underlying factors that make the CRM systems effective

Why have I been chosen?

You have been included in this study because you are either experienced in the CRM system or you have had your buying experience impacted by the CRM system.

Aim to interview 120 customers, 40 customers from first time visitor, 40 customers from regular customer least been visit more than three time to salon, 40 customers from the mall around walking distance. 30 members of staff, 2 Manager from the salon.

Do I have to take part?

Participation is voluntary, and it is up to you to decide whether to participate in the study.

Appendix F- Participant Consent form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

NAME OF PARTICIPANT:

Title of the project: **The Impact of Customer Relationship Management, on Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention within SME Beauty Organisations in the U.K.: A Case Study of Panache Beauty**

Main investigator and contact details: Suprim Jha [REDACTED]

Members of the research team: one

1. I agree to take part in the above research. I have read the Participant Information Sheet for the study.
I understand what my role will be in this research, and all my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
2. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the research at any time, without giving a reason.
3. I am free to ask any questions at any time before and during the study.
4. I understand what will happen to the data collected from me for the research.
5. I have been provided with a copy of this form and the Participant Information Sheet.

Data Protection: I agree to the UWS processing personal data which I have supplied. I agree to the processing of such data for any purposes connected with the Research Project as outlined to me*

Name of participant (print)..... Signed..... Date.....

**PARTICIPANTS MUST BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP ADD
DATE**

I WISH TO WITHDRAW FROM THIS STUDY.

If you wish to withdraw from the research, please speak to the researcher or email them at [REDACTED] the title of the research.

- You do not have to give a reason for why you would like to withdraw.
- Please let the researcher know whether you are/are not happy for them to use any data from you collected to date in the write up and dissemination of the research.

Appendix G- Certificate of Participation in International conference on Business and science

